

*COACHING PRACTICES IN ELITE
VOLLEYBALL IN IRAQ: A MIXED METHODS
CASE STUDY*

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To My Father and My Mother

DECLARATION

This dissertation is the result of my own work and includes nothing, which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except where specifically indicated in the text. It has not been previously submitted, in part or whole, to any university or institution for any degree, diploma, or other qualification.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated elite volleyball coaching in Iraq from the perspective of players and coaches from four elite level volleyball teams located in northern Iraq. Quality of the coaching experience has been shown to be a critical factor for assisting players to realise their athletic potential, and for improving team performance. Players themselves value certain kinds of coaching approaches and practices and their experience of coaching influences their engagement in sport and sports performance.

This case study of elite players in two men's teams and two women's teams, along with the perceptions of their male coaches about volleyball coaching and of coaching practices was undertaken using a mixed-method, sequential explanatory research design. For the purposes of this study, the 'case' comprised volleyball players and coaching staff of teams competing in an advanced level volleyball competition, from which players were eligible for selection for Iraq's national and international competition teams. Following the mixed-methods sequential explanatory approach, quantitative data was collected using an internationally validated sports psychology questionnaire, the Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP), administered to all players from the four participating teams. Audio-visual recordings were then made of one coaching session for each of the four participating teams ($n = 4$). The final phase of data collection involved semi-structured interviews conducted with head and assistant coaches from the four participating teams ($n = 8$) and four players each of the teams ($n = 16$). Quantitative data collected from the PSPP was analysed using descriptive statistics and single variable ANOVA. Video recorded data was analysed using video observation and notational analysis. Semi-structured interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. The theory of practice architectures informed the study's theoretical framework and assisted with the analysis of qualitative data.

Findings indicated that coaching approaches and coaching practices were dominated by a tradition where what was most valued was derived from knowledge and technical skills experienced by coaches as a former elite players, which were then passed on to a new generation of players in the sport. This led to a style of coaching, confirmed by video observational analysis and interview findings, that was autocratic, focused on physical training and skill development through drill practices, with little variation to training formats across different clubs or between male and female teams. This autocratic approach was reinforced by complex Iraqi socio-cultural norms regulating coach behaviours and coach-player relationships, especially between coaches and their female players and families. This pointed

to a coaching environment reflecting socio-political, material-economic and cultural-discursive arrangements extant in broader Iraqi society.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CAIS	Coach Analysis and Intervention System
CY-PSPP	Physical Self-Perception Among Children and Youth
FIVB	Federation Internationale de Volleyball
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISIS	Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant
IVF	Iraq Volleyball Federation
NSECHR	The National Statement of Ethical Conduct in Human Research
NVIVO	Analysis Software
PSPP	Physical Self Perception Profile
TA	Thematic Analysis
TGfU	Teaching Games for Understanding

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction to the Research Problem

Sport plays a central role in the lives of many people, even when other parts of their lives are under enormous pressures, such as in the setting of this study in Northern Iraq during the war with ISIS (2016-2018). According to Jarvie (2013) and Gems and Pfister (2009), it is impossible to completely understand any society or culture without acknowledging the place of sport. Stirling and Kerr (2009) further contend that the relationships between coaches and players depends upon social structures in place and the connections that come with having regular contact on and off the field or court.

Even at an elite level, players may vary in technical ability, fitness, self-perception, motivation, decision-making and communication skills. Coaches play a very important role in progressing individuals along their own paths of achievement as well as harnessing their collective strengths into a high functioning team. As such, at various points in the coaching relationship, coaches need to be many things, including motivators and character developers, fitness and conditioning trainers, and tactical and technical educators (Potrac, Gilbert, & Denison, 2013; Cassidy, Jones, & Potrac, 2016). Long term player participation in sport is dependent upon players' experiences of coaching and it is arguably the coach who possesses the greatest capacity to affect the quality of the experience of elite players in context of sport (Hansen, Larson, & Dworkin, 2003).

There are many empirical studies on the topic of coaching styles and approaches, coaching behaviour and its impact on players (Becker, 2009, 2013; Côté & Gilbert, 2009; Cowden, Anshel, & Fuller, 2014; Jowett, 2017). However, in context of Iraq, few research studies are available into particular coaching practices at the elite level (cf. Hanona, 2020). This research has the potential for the development of what Armour, Quennerstedt, Chambers and Makapoulous (2017) described as contextually relevant professional learning, capturing the complexity of sites and their arrangements. Such arrangements, which can have cultural-discursive, material-economic and social-political dimensions, have been described by Kemmis and Grootenboer (2008) as the 'practice architectures' - the way things 'hang together' - underpinning practices within and across sites. The theory of practice architectures has been

adapted in sports coaching settings by Phelan and Griffiths (2019) and Whatman (2016), and in Physical Education settings by Goodyear and Casey (2015), Goodyear, Casey and Kirk (2016), Petrie (2016), and Petrie and Kernaghan (2017), to illustrate what arrangements constrain current conditions and practices in sport coaching/teaching settings, and yet, can also enable change and development.

The purpose of this study is to provide a point in time analysis of coach and player perceptions of coaching approaches and practices in elite volleyball clubs in Iraq. Drawing on two high performing clubs in northern Iraq, the coaches and players of two men's teams and two women's teams are included as participants. It seeks to understand how these coaches' philosophies, approaches and practices, along with players' physical self-perception and their own ideas about coaching, might be connected (Chase & Martin, 2013). This enables us to identify aspects of coaching which are well regarded and those that are less valued by coaches and players.

The purpose of Chapter 1 is to unpack the research problem under investigation and to outline the structure of the thesis to come. An understanding of coaching philosophies frames this investigation as well as my positioning as an insider researcher, which is explored in more detail in Chapter 3. The context of sport in Iraq is important to understand in relation to the research problem and sub-questions, as are the theoretical resources being used to assist with the analysis. The research problem and research questions are outlined in this chapter as well as the significance of the topic.

1.2 Understanding Sports Coaching Philosophy

Sports coaching by definition is the task of assisting players to achieve the best possible level of achievement (Cassidy et al., 2016). Côté and Gilbert (2009) and Lyle (2002) have argued that having a well-articulated coaching philosophy sets the context and boundaries within which players and coaches can operate. A coaching philosophy is a set of values and principles which underpin the coach's repertoire of practices, building the culture of trust central to effective, holistic approaches to coaching (Cassidy et al., 2016). When the coach shares their values, they establish credibility with athletes. Bennie and O'Connor (2010, p. 314) suggested that the coaching approaches that stem from such philosophies should account for a clear role for the coach, as well as the education and development of players on and off the field. Cassidy et al. (2016) would add that *holistic* coaching is more than just the consideration of 'the whole person', in that players and coaches should also be regarded as emotional, political, spiritual and cultural beings (*ibid*, p.10). It means that coaching, as a bundle of

arrangements which can be considered as socio-political, material-economic and cultural-discursive in nature (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008), while somewhat universal (such as typical coaching practices in volleyball) should be contextualised to the site (in patriarchal, war-afflicted Iraq).

A coaching philosophy extends beyond the coach's planning practices; it includes the establishment of a program for the athletes, and the conditions, standards and relations between coaches and players (Jenny, 2013; Olson, 2014). Attempting to define sports coaching is a far more contentious definition (Côté & Gilbert, 2009). According to Martens (2012) and Cassidy et al. (2016), effective or successful coaching begins with a coach who understands the importance of a coaching philosophy and the coaching approaches which are congruent with it. Olson (2014) argued that having a coaching philosophy enables coaches to practice care in their coaching relationships, to communicate effectively and demonstrate transparent behaviour. Dohsten, Barker-Ruchti, and Lindgren (2020) asserted that in elite sport, a caring approach is required to enable athletes to maintain their wellbeing, manage pressure and maximise performance. They argue that a caring approach creates a pedagogical climate where coaches can fulfil the individual's needs and encourage the athlete's ethical development. A coach must possess practical wisdom, be able to ascertain individual needs and create opportunities for athletes to reflect on their development (Dohsten et al., 2020).

The inclusion of caring as an ethical principle might entail particular kinds of listening strategies that privilege the voice of athletes and scheduling coach-athlete interaction time beyond regular training sessions. Cronin and Armour (2019) stated that empathizing with the challenges that players face and supporting them in times of conflict would form part of a caring coach's repertoire. Jones's (2009) notion that a smile at the right time can make all the difference to a player is congruent with the idea that empathy for players throughout the coaching relationship enables coaches to create an atmosphere that fulfils their players' holistic needs, supporting athletic development and performance progression.

The path to becoming a caring, knowledgeable and arguably effective coach is complex. Firstly, coaches must have relevant knowledge to teach their players. Secondly, they have to design programs congruent with their coaching philosophies to share with the players (Abraham & Collins, 1998; Abraham, Collins, & Martindale, 2006; Cassidy et al. 2016). However, some coaches lack experience in their coaching role. For example, Ehrmann and Jordan (2011) argued that coaches require basic knowledge of programming to develop their athletes and improve their levels of performance. Coaches who fall into the role of coaching via previous playing experience may have vicarious experience of programming, but no formal

training or qualifications. Having deep knowledge of the sport is very important with elite teams. Some coaches develop their knowledge base via an experiential and ‘apprenticeship pathway’ (Lyle, 2002) established through observational and oral traditions (Taylor & Garratt, 2013) from elite playing to elite coaching. Other coaches develop their knowledge from a combination of playing experience at any level with mentoring and on-going professional development via coaching courses (Armour et al., 2017).

Whatever their pathway, Lyle (2002) noted that coaches need to continually develop a knowledge base which should comprise general coaching knowledge and sport specific knowledge. Lyle and Cushion (2016) argued that knowledge, which a coach believes is valuable and then shares with athletes, is inextricably linked to deliberate, critical professional learning experiences. They claimed that coaches’ knowledge includes the realization of which bodies of knowledge and core competencies are relevant to their practice, along with the establishment and enactment of a code of ethics. Obtaining such knowledge can be facilitated by coaching clinic experiences and mentoring relationships. Such experience enables the coaches to develop reflective learning skills in the context of training and integrates this knowledge to facilitate effective coaching processes and practices.

Coaches, in addition to teaching sport skills and developing fitness, must help players grow and develop, and motivate their players to reach optimum performance (Lyle, 2002; Martens, 2012; Lyle & Cushion, 2016). Martin, Rocca, Cayanus and Weber (2009) stated that the coaches spend a lot of time with their players when they implement the full remit of their coaching role. How coaches see their role is tied to their coaching philosophy, underscoring consistent and positive approaches to players (Cassidy et al., 2016). Coaches must know players’ strengths, and weaknesses and areas for improvement while acknowledging the obstacles they encounter (Martindale, Collins & Abraham, 2007). All coaches operate under a coaching philosophy of some kind (Cassidy et al, 2016; Martens, 2012). It may be by instinct, or it may be formally documented and well thought out. Irwin, Hanton, and Kerwin (2004) asserted that coaches who follow a well-defined coaching philosophy will help their players reach their goals and, for that reason, they argue that the development of a formal coaching philosophy statement is essential for all coaches.

1.3 Social and Economic Conditions in Iraq Influencing Sport Participation

This section outlines the social and cultural aspects of Iraq society impacting on this study’s context. It covers topics such as governance structure in Iraq, the importance of religion

and the theocratic governance based on Islam, patriarchal social structures and the social status of women in Iraq and considers the issue of women's rights. This context is important in understanding how elite coaching is conducted in this context and why certain coaching styles may be adopted in Iraq.

Iraq is a country with a long history of important civilizations with many contributions to humanity. As the centre of the Babylonia empire (606-536 BC), Iraq was an important cultural, religious, and economic hub of the Middle East. Iraq today, with its capital in Baghdad, is a state of multicultural religion, doctrine, multiple nationalities and traditions. The population of 37 million comprises of different ethnic group that are 77% Arabs, and 19% Kurds and others such as Armenians, Assyrians, and Turkomens. Regardless of different ethnic groups, the majority of Iraq's population comprises of Muslims (Commisceo, 2021).

The cultural heritage of Iraq has been devastated by extensive destructive effects of war that have had extensive coverage across worldwide media. Multiple conflicts and consequences spanning more than 30 years include the Iraq-Iran war and Kuwait war, with the further debilitating effects of international sanctions. In 2003, Iraq was invaded by the USA and its allies over claims that Iraq had failed to disband its chemical weapons program. From 2013, Sunni militant groups belonging to the terrorist group Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) took control of large areas of northern Iraq. This included the major cities of Fallujah and Mosul, in which this study was conducted. In 2014, a US-led international coalition assisted Iraq's security forces to intervene against ISIS. In 2017, ISIS lost control of Mosul, the largest Iraqi city under its control. Iraq then is a nation attempting to recover its social, economic and cultural heritage from years of conflict, poor economies, and geo-political factors (Matthews et al., 2020).

Vernez, Culbertson, Constant, and Karam (2016) note that Iraq is a nation currently contending with a raft of social and economic challenges following war-driven social disruption. The country has struggled to nurture talent across a variety of domains, including academics, information and communication technology (ICT), and sport. For young people, sports participation has been undermined by issues relating to its' low social priority, limited community support for sport, concerns about personal safety and security, and a lack of funding for sports facilities, equipment and resources. Iraqi elite sports participation and coaching cannot be fully understood without acknowledging the long periods of armed conflict Iraq has experienced since the early 1980s and the subsequent impoverished material-economic circumstances under which sport (and life) in Iraq is attempting to be rebuilt.

1.3.1 Demographics and Governance of Iraq

This section is included to assist with understanding the physical and social geography of Iraq, depicting regional support for sporting club competition, and how the ethnic groups found in various regions are part of the reason for sport participation. The total area of Iraq is 438 320 km². The country is bordered by Turkey to the North and Iran to the East. It shares its western border with Syria and Jordan. Saudi Arabia, Kuwait and Persian Gulf are located to the South.

Figure 1. Map of the Middle East, featuring Iraq and its nearest neighbours.

Iraq is a federal parliamentary republic that includes 19 provinces or governorates. The government is conducted and administered through legislative, executive and judicial institutions. Although Iraq is considered a single state, it is both ethnically and religiously diverse. Iraq has an Islamic Constitution. As such, it can be referred to as a theocratic state. Iraq has a population of around 38 million of which around 99% of population are Muslims. That total comprises around 60% Shiite and 40% Sunni. Moreover, Sunnis are an ethnically diverse group including Turkish, Kurdish and Arab Sunnis. In addition, there is smaller section of the population who identify as Christians (Al-Shamsi & Othman, 2017). Hasan (2019) stated that Islam is considered Iraq's main form of religion. Much public expenditure is invested in shrines, mosques, land and religious sites of cultural significance which are also supported by

charities. Donations are received from philanthropists and pilgrims. Shrines and mosques such as the Imam's Husain Shrine and others are considered the main focal points for public gatherings. These venues provide platforms for reinforcing religious authority, as they act as centres for information dissemination about the social importance of Islam and daily religious observance (Al-Shamsi & Othman, 2017). Venues for religious observance, schools and universities attract more Government and philanthropic funding than other types of venues, such as sporting stadiums or clubs, meaning that support for sport is more likely to be found in the education sector.

1.3.2 Patriarchal Family Relations and the Social Status of Women

In general, Iraqis are accustomed to and accepting of religious and ethnic diversity. Nevertheless, the culture of Iraq is intolerant towards any deviation from conventional norms and behaviours. Abbas, Nasif, and Alwan (2019) note that Iraqi society is highly conservative, with rules and traditions both strictly observed and policed. Strict standards for public and private behaviour are governed in accordance with Islamic values. In Iraq, it is a cultural norm that criticism is rarely direct. However, praise is expected to be offered generously and accepted graciously by the receiver (Mayer, 2018).

The culture and traditions of honour are important aspects of family life with family and personal honour protected at any cost (Abbas et al., 2019). Respect and obedience are accorded to family members and others based on age. There is a gender-based hierarchy of authority in Iraqi society with women having low social status and power. In Iraq, women are expected to act in a reserved manner and be submissive to men. Iraqi girls have poorer educational outcomes than males across most key measures of achievement (for example, schooling completion). On completing schooling, girls have limited access to the labour market and paid employment (UNOCHA, 2020a). Accordingly, women account for less than 25 per cent of management positions in Iraq. Gender inequality is exacerbated by traditional religious beliefs, social or cultural norms, and the limited rights allowed to women by legal and other institutional barriers. Iraq is recognised as a collectivist society due to the almost universal observance of Islam in which the interests of the group supercedes the goals of individuals with preferential treatment and social status accorded to group members (Kinbar, 2016).

In Iraq, family is considered the focal point required to maintain cultural identity and values for diverse ethnic groups. Family influences, patriarchal family relations and cultural norms restricting the social participation of women combine to shape the participation of young

Muslim girl in sports, physical activity and other community-based activities (Goodman, Knotts, & Jackson, 2007). Within this context, female athletes face barriers to sporting participation because female sporting participation has a low social priority: permission to participate may be withheld by families; women's movements are both restricted and supervised outside of the family home; traditional behavioural expectations of girls and young women are based on religious beliefs, and the woman's familial duties and responsibilities have priority within patriarchal family structures (Goodman et al., 2007). El-Siade (2015) found that most of sporting teams, including most Olympic teams in Arab-speaking countries were male teams because of restrictions to female sport participation and a lack of familial support (Eydi, Abbasi, & Ibrahim, 2013). Fleddermann, Heppe, Eils, and Zentgraf (2016) identified factors limiting the participation of women in volleyball teams. These restrictions, reflecting the findings of Goodman et al. (2007) including the lack of financial support, security issues, familial restrictions, and religious traditions that limit women's freedoms.

Despite these limitations, researchers have noted the growing rate of female participation in sports across a number of Iraqi regions (Conte, Favero, Niederhausen, Capranica, & Tessitore, 2016). This appears to arise from the significant social and economic changes associated with national reconstruction in the aftermath of conflict across the entire Middle East resulting in a shift in attitudes towards female sports participation. However, Conte et al. (2016) have indicated that the growth in female participation has been uneven across different regions, noting that most Iraqi female teams come from the Nineveh Plain area in the northern part of Iraq (see Figure 2). They attribute this to better security conditions and cultural values that support female sporting participation.

These changing attitudes to women's sport participation are particularly significant for Kurdish Iraqi female players, a traditionally marginalised ethnic group who comprise a substantial number of this study's participants from the northern part of Iraq. As Iraq enters a period of post-war reconstruction, these young women are experiencing a complex set of interwoven societal influences relating to gender, religion, and identity. These aspects are continually being reshaped by the athletes themselves (Harkness, 2012). Acknowledging this positive trend in women's participation, Khasawneh (2015) has proposed that attracting more women into volleyball coaching roles may achieve a better gender balance within the sport and may serve as an effective strategy to encouraging yet more young women to take up volleyball.

1.3.3 Coaches' Relationships with Players and Their Families in Iraq

Iraqi coaches must develop strong working relationships with players' families to facilitate their participation in sport and this is something I have extensive first-hand knowledge of. This is particularly true for families of female players in order to overcome the historical and societal barriers that discourage females sporting participation. Families grant permission for female players to attend coaching sessions based on their approval of the coach. Hence, a good relationship that engenders trust between the coach and the player's family is essential. Coaches are often expected to communicate information about the coaching session to family members, including extended family members like Uncles and Grandmothers, about the training schedule prior to volleyball coaching sessions and matches. Iraqi coaches are often seen as responsible for the athlete's care before, during and after training sessions and over the season. Such care might mean providing transport and returning female players safely and with escort to their homes, something I have done many times as a coach of women's volleyball teams. Where a coach does not have sufficient contact with the player's family or fails to nurture a respectful and trusting relationship with the family, it is unlikely that a female player will be granted permission to attend training sessions nor be able to commit to the team over the course of a competition (Hamdia, Naji, & Algeribawi, 2020).

Partly because of this complex relationship dynamic, coaches tend to adopt a more flexible approach towards female players' participation and training attendance as compared to their male counterparts. Coaches are expected to provide male players with support both on and off the court. At an elite level, the role of Iraqi coaches often includes advising players regarding work or study. The coach is seen as a respected figure and trusted advisor within the community (Al-Sinani, & Benn, 2011). In contrast, Western coaches may not always develop close relationships with player's families, nor will the lack of such a relationship impact on the players' continuation in the sport. Western coaches' interactions with female players usually occurs at some social distance from other family members. Moreover, in the Western societal context, it is not usually regarded as important for family members, regardless of gender, to know the coach at a personal level (Schailleé, Theeboom, & Van Cauwenberg, 2017).

1.3.4 The Aftermath of Armed Conflict and Civil Unrest in Iraq

Against the backdrop of war and conflict, sanctions and rebuilding, and more recently with COVID-19, a new government has been formed. The government has now eliminated a political deadlock between powerful groups which has paralysed Iraqi administration post-war, however, the political rivalries, fiscal pressures and restricted capacity of various government

institutions creates hurdles in effective deployment of reforms. For instance, tackling corruption and strengthening corporate governance are crucial for stability of Iraq in the long term across the entire region (USIP, 2021).

Since 2017, Iraq has experienced a phase of reconstruction. Parliamentary elections were held in May 2018 and a national development plan entitled *Iraq Vision 2030 for Iraq* (Ministry of Planning, 2019) was established. This vision outlined planned progress towards greater gender equality and opportunities for young people. (Vilardo & Bittar, 2018). Ironically, under the first national priority, termed *Man Building*, Vision 2030 states that “More women should be empowered and encouraged to enter the labour market, generate income and diversify their family’s sources of income (p. 13)”. Since 2018, Iraq has experienced a phase of reconstruction. Parliamentary elections were held in May 2018 and a national development plan entitled *Iraq Vision 2030 for Iraq* (Ministry of Planning, 2019) was established. This vision outlined planned progress towards greater gender equality and opportunities for young people (Vilardo & Bittar, 2018). Ironically, under the first national priority named *Man Building*, Vision 2030 states that “More women should be empowered and encouraged to enter the labour market, generate income and diversify their family’s sources of income” (p. 13).

Figure 2 provides an overview of the humanitarian effort planned to track and relocate displaced persons in northern Iraq’s Ninewa Governorate following the conflicts with ISIS. Ninewa contains the area of al-Mosul and the city of Mosul.

Figure 2. Ninewa Governorate humanitarian response (UNOCHA, 2020b).

Iraq Vision 2030 indicates that Iraq has “one of the largest youth population groups in the world with those under 19 years old accounting for about 50% of the population” (p. 14). Moreover, extended periods of war and civil unrest plus the rise of religious extremism resulted in a large number of disenfranchised and alienated youth (Vilardo & Bittar, 2018). Internal division created by religious intolerance and ethnic conflict has resulted in Iraqi youth being divided and segregated based on negative perceptions of people from different ethnic backgrounds or religious affiliations. Vision 2030 comments:

Hopefully, all of this [Iraq Vision 2030] will be achieved as a result of monitoring, evaluation, accountability, transparency of all efforts. The youth and

women will play an effective role as part of their collective participation. At the same time this sends a strong message to all citizens and the world that Iraq is finished with wars, conflicts, sanctions, terrorist groups and is ready to start a new phase of development, building, construction and alleviation of poverty and unemployment, a stage in which the interest of the country and its citizens are prioritized in partnership with all parties and societal and political administration (p. 9).

In acknowledgement of these deep and longstanding social divisions, sport-based initiatives for teaching the communication and negotiation skills required for relationship building and conflict resolution have been developed. Those programmes aimed at Iraqi youth have been designed to build community relationships based on a vision of shared responsibility for a reimagined Iraqi future in which all Iraqi people identify themselves first as Iraq citizens and secondly as members of disparate ethnic or religious groups (Ministry of Planning, 2019).

According to UNOCHA (2020a), Iraq declared that 9 pilot sports colleges would work in consultation with 5 UK sports colleges in order to deliver a revised sports and physical education curriculum. Sports Colleges are an initiative which Penney (2004) explained dates back to 1993 where secondary schools in England could apply to be designated as a “Specialist School”, signalling ‘expertise’, innovation and a commitment to a particular ‘identity’ and ethos, such as sport (p.228). These 5 schools formed connections with primary and secondary schools across Iraq to create a network of about fifty schools. More than 250 supervisors and teachers are training to deliver these new pedagogies. Further training is being provided for close to 85 master trainers. The new resources in HPE curriculum are designed with a view towards inclusion of young people who are differently abled. Leadership skills training programmes have been developed using sport as a main vehicle, with more than 600 people benefiting from access. New mutually beneficial relationships are being developed across the community including with private businesses.

Westrheim and Manger (2014) argue that sport has been used by many countries to build strong relationships and leadership skills among young people. Over time, this social project has increased opportunities for young people to participate in high-quality physical education and sports programs. However, Al-Husseini and Elbeltagi (2016) noted that the social and economic disruption in the aftermath of war, has seen many Iraqi schools struggling to provide adequate physical activity and sports programs.

1.4 Sports Administration in Iraq

Popular sports such as football, volleyball and basketball are administered by Ministry of Youth and Sport. This agency is responsible for the national management of sports and youth affairs. In May 2020, Adnan Dirjal, a high-profile Iraqi footballer, was appointed Minister of Youth and Sport. Megheirkouni (2017) notes that Iraq, through the Ministry of Youth and Sport, has outlined policies and governance structures for the administration of sports and sports clubs. While there are slight differences across regions or governorates, sport is administered in similar ways throughout Iraq.

Iraqi schools and sports clubs are key organisations for exposing children and young people to sport. Children are first introduced to sport in the primary school through physical education lessons and junior school sport programs. The organisation and focus of these programs differ in schools across local communities. However, most primary school sports programs include football (soccer), athletics and low organisation games enjoyed by young children. Soccer is the most popular sport in Iraq in terms of participation. (Karakaya, Abdulla, & Sadeq, 2016). School sport is regarded as valuable to children's physical development and motor skills development, an important activity for enriching the school experience and a complement to the schools' broader mission. School sport in Iraq makes a vital contribution to the student's education. Sport is used to teach children important values and life skills that children take into adulthood. These include sportsmanship, fair play, respect, and the valuing of exercise for maintaining health (Bayer, 2019; Soliman, 2020). School sport is regarded as valuable to children's physical development and motor skills development, an important activity for enriching the school experience and a complement to the schools' broader mission. School sport in Iraq makes a vital contribution to the student's education. Sport is used to teach children important values and life skills that children take into adulthood. These include sportsmanship, fair play, respect, and the valuing of exercise for maintaining health (Bayer, 2019; Soliman, 2020).

Iraqi secondary schools expose students to more diversity in the sports that are offered. Students can participate in soccer, basketball, badminton and volleyball among others. However, soccer remains the most popular choice. Inter-school sporting competitions are organised for upper primary, middle school and high school. It is in these school competitions that students usually have their first exposure to competitive volleyball (Hamza, & Helil, 2019).

Across Iraq, there are many sports clubs that enrol students and other young people no longer attending school. Sports clubs and venues typically host a range of sports such as

volleyball, badminton and basketball. Students often participate in club sports in order to spend time with friends, learn new skills and engage in competition. One constraint on Iraqi sport development is poor financial support for coaches working in sporting clubs. The Ministry of Youth and Sport provides limited funding to assist sports clubs, however, Badr (2019) noted that this support is insufficient to pay wages for coaches and their assistants. Sports clubs utilise funding to pay rent and utilities. Sports clubs also support players' transport costs when competing in other cities and regions.

The youth sporting participation is seen as offering significant individual and societal benefits. However, in Iraq the lack of funding, qualified coaching staff and poor resourcing has led to a lack of high-quality programs. Nevertheless, communities and schools strive to maintain quality youth sport programs by training and educating coaches employed in school and university settings. In essence, physical education - internal and external to school, colleges and universities - is critical to supporting youth development programs (Said & Jaff, 2019).

There is limited opportunity for athletes to extend their training and make a career out of professional sport in Iraq. This is partly due to the long history of unrest but also due to limited formalised sports programs available within Iraqi universities. This is a significant difference between Iraqi and western universities, where the identification and development of sporting talent is actively encouraged through scholarships, high-level intervarsity competitions, and selection pathways that access elite programmes and professional careers in a wide range of sports. There is also a minimal return on investment for sports programs that identify talent; the athletes have no clear progression available and Abdul-Karim (2019) notes that Iraq's ability to engage in international sporting competition is also compromised. However, despite the apparent lack of established formal pathways in youth sport, or methods of identifying high performing athletes, talent identification still occurs through an informal system of professional networks. These networks comprise school teachers, club coaches and university staff. The networks rely on interpersonal relationships for their functional success. For example, players with a particular talent for volleyball may be identified by school sports teachers. These teachers may then use their professional networks to refer players to coaches in clubs or at universities. Kadhim and Hatif (2016) noted that it would be commonplace for a secondary school teacher with a particular sporting interest to contact a sports teacher in the primary school to identify promising players.

University or college coaches may also consult junior sports organisers to scout for players moving towards elite competition. Students advancing through university-based sports may be eligible for national and international selection and Iraq's Champion Sports League. In

some universities, lecturers with a sporting interest will make contact with secondary school sport teachers to identify talented players. These contacts and professional networks may be developed through university-run professional development opportunities for teachers coaching school teams or providing physical education classes (Abbas, et al., 2019). These relationships support the delivery of the physical education curriculum in schools. These partnerships are mutually beneficial and provide valuable support to schools providing resources and expertise. According to Al-Oun and Al-Leheeb (2015), the main obstacles relating to the delivery of the Iraqi physical education curriculum include a lack of appropriate facilities, environmental constraints, poor technical knowledge regarding skills development and sport science.

I mention these informal networks as I have first-hand knowledge of them and the relationships they create. As an academic employed at Mosul University's Sports College, I routinely contacted sports teachers in local schools and conducted volleyball coaching sessions with school-aged players. Volunteering my time as a coach in the school sector achieved two important purposes: 1) developing the coaching knowledge of physical education teachers in volleyball and 2) strategically identifying and recruiting future talented senior players for my own club. The pathway to elite volleyball participation in Iraq starts in the schooling sector.

1.4.1 Volleyball Participation and Administration in Iraq

Mili (2016) noted a recent increase in young people participating in Iraqi volleyball, with players actively engaged across a large number of sports clubs and centres. This growth in participation was attributed to young people's desires to achieve physical fitness and a tendency to regard team membership as a source of moral and social support and friendship.

Volleyball is widely regarded as the second most popular sport in Iraq, after football. The sport is administered by the Iraq Volleyball Federation (IVF), the peak governing body responsible for sport development and regional funding for clubs (Mohammed et al., 2019). Renowned Iraqi volleyball sports clubs include Al-Habbaniyah (Baghdad), Naft Maysan, (Amarah, Iraq), Erbil, Shaqlawa Sport Club, Al Rasheed (Baghdad), Al Shorta (Baghdad), Peshmerga (Kurdistan), Gas Al-Janoob and others. Players from the most successful regional teams may be selected for the national team in order to represent Iraq in international volleyball competitions. The national team is selected and managed by the IVF, who also appoints the national coach (Goodman et al., 2007).

Internationally, Iraq competes in the Arab Championships and the Asian League. Iraq has a history of participating in different championships and sports events, some of which are

illustrated in the table below. In addition, the Women's National Beach Volleyball team of Iraqi has also participated in international friendly invitation matches (Al-Ghafily, 2018).

Table 1

Iraq's History of Participation in the Arab Championships and Tournaments (Said & Jaff, 2019)

	Result	Host country	Year	Tournament name
1	Fifth	Lebanon	1957	Arab Session
2	Fourth	Kuwait	1970	Arab Session
3	Fourth	Egypt	1975	Arab Session
4	Fourth	Syria	1976	Arab Session
5	Fifth	Kuwait	1977	First Arab Championship
6	Third	Lebanon	1978	Arab Session
7	Fourth	Syria	1980	The Second Arab Championship
8	Sixth	Tunisia	1984	The Fourth Arab Championship
9	Second	Morocco, West	1985	Arab Session
10	Second	Jordan	1986	Arab Session
11	Second	Jordan	1986	The 5th Arab Championship
12	Third	Saudi	1988	The 6th Arab Championship
13	Fourth	Algeria	2004	Arab Session
14	Ninth	Bahrain	2006	The 15th Arab Championship
15	Tenth	Egypt	2008	Arab Session
16	Ninth	Diameter	2011	Arab Session
17	Fifth	Bahrain	2012	The 18th Arab Championship
18	Tenth	Kuwait	2015	The 19th Arab Championship
19	Third	Egypt	2016	Arab Championship
20	Fifth	Egypt	2018	The 21th Arab Championship

1.4.2 Coaching Qualification Pathways in Iraq

Few Iraqi sports coaches have formal training below elite appointments. However, there are training pathways for those interested in coaching. An Iraqi coaching certificate is usually obtained after successfully completing a formal coach education program conducted by a club under experienced coaches, which is how I acquired my first formal certificate. It can also be obtained as part of a university undergraduate sports education program. Despite formal training being available, most academic and professional coach education programs are outdated, partly as a result of Iraq's extended isolation from the international sporting community. Once the basic coaching certification is obtained, there are few opportunities to obtain advanced coaching qualifications as no advanced certification for coaches is available within Iraq. The nearest high performance coaching centre for volleyball is located in Bahrain (FIVB, 2020). To obtain advanced qualifications, coaches must travel outside Iraq. For many

Iraqi nationals, the cost of doing so is prohibitive. The extended social disruption and isolation during war and civil unrest has led to a decrease in the exchange of information, knowledge and ideas between Iraq and other countries, resulting in what Al-Wattar, Hussein and Hussein (2011, p.249) have described as a “stagnation of innovation” with respect to sport development and coach education, exacerbated particularly in women’s sport.

As a consequence of typical social-cultural mores in a patriarchal, Islamic society like Iraq, autocratic coaching styles are typically adopted by coaches and assistant coaches. In the case of coaching of elite teams, head coaches are responsible for planning of every detail of the training session. This is in part because coach development in Iraq follows an apprenticeship model (Lyle, 2002), whereby an assistant coach will work under the sole direction of a head coach until it is their turn to be head coach. Coaches therefore replicate the methods of coaching they experienced and model these practices with their players, who may also become future coaches. The assistant coach typically provides additional assistance to athletes improving their technical skills or overseeing drills assigned by the head coach. There is a clear hierarchy of authority with the expectation that the head coach will control and manage all aspects of the training session. This style of volleyball coaching appears to mirror aspects of early coaching models that emerged with the codification of sport in the United Kingdom and Europe in the 19th century (Taylor & Garrett, 2013).

1.5 Background to the Study

As explained previously, the government only financially supports coaches who are concurrently teachers or lecturers: no funding is provided for club level coaching. Thus, essentially, schools and universities provide coach wages in Iraq. This policy to support teachers who coach in schools but not to support professional coaches in clubs explains why most coaches study to become teachers, and most coaches in the club system are teachers or lecturers (Rhoades, Eisenberger, & Armeli, 2001). This material-economic arrangement (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008) is likely to be significant in how coaching unfolds in context. Despite the lack of professional salaries for sports coaches, Iraqi volleyball teams often have a head coach and an assistant coach, supported by their teaching salaries. Elite players in the highest ranked teams may train up to three times a week. The Iraq Volleyball Federation (IVF) has four levels for players: junior, youth, advanced and international, for both genders. This study involves players and teams from the advanced (elite) level. Members of the international teams were also included among the participants. The four teams have been de-identified in this study and given as pseudonyms the names of two rivers in northern Iraq: Dejlah and Furat,

to indicate generally which region of Iraq the teams are based without identifying them. Due to the highly sensitive social-political circumstances of Iraq, guaranteeing the anonymity of participants was critical in this study.

Iraqi coaches tend to use traditional, long-established and uncontested training programs that are characterised by exercises to improve players' fitness and technical skills as the main means to achieve their outcomes (Basher & Qlata, 2013; Haddi, Khalaf, & Khalaf, 2005; Khalaf & Diachenko, 2015). In conjunction with, and perhaps as a consequence of these practices, Iraqi researchers tend to focus on fitness, skills and biomechanics in their sport research, with a view to improving player performance through advances in biomechanical analysis (Al-Dulaimi & Sabaeh, 2013; Khmal, 2013; Obaid, Kadim, & Nemah, 2013). Iraqi coaches who deliver these traditional programs and participate in biomechanical research studies are not aware of the newer approaches more common in the English-speaking world, such as Game Sense (Stolz & Pill, 2016), Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) (Butler & Griffin, 2010) and non-linear pedagogy (Chow et al., 2007; Chow, Davids, Button, & Renshaw, 2015). The dominant coaching style in Iraq could be described as a traditional system of pursuing biomechanical performance, driven by coach knowledge bases depending on a biomechanical research tradition, combined with the past playing experiences of the coaches (Al-Dulaimi & Sabaeh, 2013). Iraqi researchers have reported that fitness affects an athlete's skills to achieve their goal whilst it is also stated that the biomechanics can improve skills and fitness for the players (Al-Dulaimi, & Sabaeh, 2013; Allo, 2005; Almashhadany, 2002; Hasawi, 2006; Kasem, 2005; Khalef, 2015; Khmal, 2013). Most of this research focusing on the training effect of fitness on the athlete's skills rather than how the athletes are being coached, or what the coaching practices to improve fitness might be. What athletes think or value about their coaching program is largely absent in the sports coaching literature in Iraq.

Like other elite sports, competitive volleyball is comprised of social dynamics that are influenced by coach and player motivation and anxiety. Having an understanding of sport psychology is important, where coaches and players learn to appreciate the impact of different psychological factors on performance (Sum, Wallhead, Ha, & Sit, 2018). Nicholls (2017) stated that sports psychology supports player sensitivity and positivity, promoting the winning mentality required to conquer the adversities - such as injury, illness or poor performances - that may arise during a season. There is abundant research in Iraq that indicates the importance of psychology for players to enhance their skills and fitness to achieve their aims. Al-khafaf (2002) stated that the psychological awareness is related to achievement of cognitive abilities and skill improvement in volleyball. Perceived efficiency in motivation and its relationship

with the psychological and social climate for the handball players was considered by (Al-Hyalli, 2011). Thus, Iraqi research in psychology focuses upon performance outcomes *of the players more than the coaches*. This cultural-discursive arrangement (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008) is one that could possibly maintain the status quo of biomechanical and physiological emphases in Iraqi coaching practices and also make investigation of coaches as well as players a sensitive inquiry.

Research into coaching indicates that the success of an athlete is linked to both the coach's knowledge and the athlete's abilities (Trudel, Culver, & Werthner, 2013). Volleyball has different skills to many sports that requires exceptional fitness to use these skills. Several consistent techniques have evolved in volleyball, including spiking, blocking, setting and serving which require high levels of fitness from players to perform (Weldon et al., 2021). Some players are content to follow the set exercises of the main coach, while other players prefer to seek additional skills from another coach or conditioning trainer. This means volleyball coaches have different programs and different strategies that vary between the volleyball teams.

As can be seen, the existing studies have focussed on either the importance of psychology for player performance or the effect of the acquisition of fitness and skills on player performance. Rarely are Iraqi coaches' practices under the research gaze. Coaching literature asserts that coaches must integrate more than just psychology or fitness and skills but also engage, educate and grow their players through their coaching approaches (Cassidy et al., 2018; Trudel et al., 2013). There is little research in Iraq that considers all of these factors together. This study will be a first, with Arabic participants, which intends to consider the coaches and players' perspectives on coaching approaches and attendant practices and how and why they are valued. This research will advance the profession's understanding generally about what is valued in volleyball coaching and have the potential to identify gender differences in perceptions and preferences as this is absent from the existing research.

1.6 Statement of the Problem

Sports coaching is a current topic of interest given the value society places on sport and the role coaches can play in shaping their athlete's lives and their communities. Jones, Armour and Potrac (2004) noted that coaching can go beyond influencing athlete performance or results and shape the people they become whilst Gilbert (2006) stated that these holistic dimensions of coaching are under-theorized. This view of coaching can be better understood by examining coaching philosophies, coaches' approaches and practices and the elite athlete's perceptions of

them (Miller, Lutz, & Fredenburg, 2012). Working out what it is that coaches and players value in coaching might be possible by asking the coaches about their coaching philosophies of the volleyball coaches and observing their practices in coaching sessions in a naturalistic setting.

Iraqi culture means that sporting experiences are different for men and women. Men can play sport throughout their lives. Girls and women can play segregated sport from preschool to secondary school but are highly limited in their involvement with university and clubs. Iraqi culture and traditions presuppose that girls and young women will stop playing sport during secondary school. Most families will not allow their girls to continue to play sport after finishing high school. Female sporting participation at university or club level is rare. Al-khakani's (2011) research showed that families and school staff prefer girls to spend more time on their school lessons than play sport. It is quite unusual then to have two high performing women's teams in Iraq so what motivates them to play and train at the elite level despite these challenges?

From my perspective and experience as an Iraqi volleyball coach and educator, Iraqi volleyball teams are still utilising traditional coaching programs and approaches without having updated to more modern techniques. This means the coaches prefer to focus on developing player fitness and biomechanical skills and proceed without recourse to sports psychology. Concepts relating to motivation, perception and the assessment of different coaching styles are generally not incorporated in coaching practices. Sports psychology methods are sometimes applied where they can enhance an athlete's performance in those sports attracting national or international attention but are not considered in relation to coaching practices *to better understand coaching*. Nonetheless, Iraq is still recognised as underdeveloped with respect to its use of contemporary sports psychology practices and techniques. Currently, there is no association of sport psychology in Iraq, no ethical guidelines are observed in this area. It is therefore a genuine puzzle as to how elite volleyball coaching practices endure without the levels of support enjoyed in other countries.

As the Iraqi context has limited access to current sports psychology knowledge and advanced coaching applications and in the absence of home-grown research and exposure to international coaching practices, coaches wanting to improve their practice must actively seek support and information from other countries. Iraqi coaches maintain their interest in developing their players' game skills and fitness levels. However, they are constrained to these domains unless they choose to source information elsewhere. Coaches are not encouraged to develop new coaching programs, yet they need to consider more than just 'fitness, skills and drills' to engage, educate and grow their players as peace returns to the region. This research

project seeks to understand coach and elite player's perceptions of coaching approaches and associated practices they value. This research will be intrinsically important to player associations, youth sport development systems and schooling systems.

1.7 Research Aim and Sub-Questions

This research focuses on coaches', assistant coaches' and players' perceptions of volleyball coaching and coaching practices to understand how and why they are valued. It seeks to identify if there are differences in the way in which men and women are coached and what they value in terms of coaching philosophies, approaches and practices. This study is intended to benefit Iraqi coaches, improving awareness of influential coaching practices in use elsewhere. This research will use a mixed method, sequential explanatory case study to answer the research questions. This approach supports the integration of quantitative data collected through questionnaires about players' physical self-perception and observational checklists, and in-depth, qualitative observational notes and interview data with coaches and players (Yin, 2015).

Three focused research sub-questions are:

1. What are the coaching philosophies that inform volleyball coaching approaches in Iraq?
2. What coaching approaches do the coaches and players value?
3. How and to what extent do coaching practices align with valued coaching approaches of men and women players of volleyball?

These questions were refined from understandings in the literature of the importance of and relationships between coaching philosophies, coaching approaches and practices in particular sites with particular athletes (Cassidy et al., 2016; Cushion, Griffiths, & Armour, 2019; Martens, 2012).

1.8 Significance of the Study

This study is of intrinsic value to me as the researcher to improve knowledge and practices relating to volleyball coaching and teaching. However, the study may also have instrumental outcomes and implications for player associations, youth sport development systems and schooling systems. Investment in sports development programs is a significant

undertaking by local, state, national, and international sporting organisations. Such programs should be concerned with sports attrition and failure to transition athletes into elite sport levels. Reasons for such failure can be a consequence of factors outside of volleyball, a reflection of wider community issues such as cultural pressures and the effect of the war, but they can also be attributed to factors within the sport such as coaching quality, coach education and professional learning, and player support (Taylor & Garratt, 2013). As previous studies have not focused on Iraqi coaching approaches, nor what players think of them, this study has the potential to shape coach education and professional learning in ways that improve coaching quality.

Coaches should be interested in their own continuing development and professional learning (Lyle and Cushion, 2016; Armour et al., 2017) but opportunities for coach learning have been reported as inconsistent and dependent upon mentored communities of practice (Cushion, Nelson, Armour, Lyle, Jones, Sandford & O'Callaghan, 2010, p.38). Holistic approaches to coaching emphasise reflective practice as a form of coach learning and self-development and a focus on the development of the whole athlete (Jones et al., 2012). The quality of experiences of players has been argued to support long term player engagement and longevity in the sport (Crane & Temple, 2014). Additionally, coaches should benefit from understanding player differences and how coaching practices may be adapted to individualise coaching experiences for players, developing in particular their interpersonal knowledge (Lyle & Cushion, 2016; Crane & Temple, 2014). Coaching may be improved by a knowledge of the differences between males' and females' motivation to engage in sport, the coaching practices they value, and to develop coaching programs that reflect and build upon that insight. This study may further encourage coaches to acknowledge the wide range of competencies and knowledges that contribute to quality coaching as a source of self-reflection on their own coaching practice. This includes sports science knowledges that Iraqi coaches may not have been exposed to including sports psychology and alternative forms of sport pedagogy that focus on tactical awareness and capabilities (e.g., Teaching Games for Understanding). For coaches in Iraq, this may lead to the take-up of a wider range of coaching practices to improve coaching effectiveness.

Coach learning may also be understood as a form of ethical practice (Cassidy et al., 2016). Enacting a holistic form of coaching from the perspective of player preferences may prompt coaches to develop a coaching philosophy that is inclusive of players and encapsulates the common values of the Iraq 2030 plan of solidarity, tolerance, justice and freedom (Ministry of Planning, Iraq, 2019). One significant outcome that may result is a consideration of how the

male coaches may enact coaching programs that recognise differences in team gender. Programs that are delivered with an explicit acknowledgment of gender may result in more girls and young women being attracted to and retained in volleyball.

Taking a broader social perspective, the findings of this thesis may have implications for policy makers who may see the value of sport as a means for community cohesion and renewal and strategic partnerships for collaborative resourcing. Volleyball is the second most popular sport in Iraq after football (soccer) (IRFAD, 2021). As the participation rate of young people in volleyball continues to increase, it is reasonable that players should have access to high quality coaching that would enable talented and motivated players to be identified for selection in teams competing at national and international levels. The schooling systems in Iraq already support coaching practice therefore investment in coach professional learning and volleyball resources can have mutual benefits for the schooling sector and for furthering the aspirations of future elite players. New resources and approaches could be added to the expertise sharing already occurring between schools and clubs as coaches are the critical links in knowledge networks between school and club systems.

The idea of knowledge networks, or ‘communities of practice’ (Lave & Wenger, 1991) has implications for volleyball administrators interested in progressing advanced level volleyball in Iraq including the country's potential to engage more extensively in international competition. Findings from this study may indicate that the level of volleyball played in Iraq may be improved by more open competition between clubs located in the Bagdad competition and clubs located in Kurdish northern Iraq. Such arrangements might not only benefit players who would gain opportunities for high quality competition but could also provide a forum for knowledge transfer and knowledge sharing among coaches in Iraq.

This study has methodological and broader research significance. It is unique in design in that all of the data collection was carried out by third parties in Iraq while the author was in Australia due to concurrent military conflict at the research sites. The resulted in a unique blend of data collection tools used within the mixed methods design and corresponding data sets. Finally, this study is significant as a comprehensive search of the research literature on volleyball coaching in Iraq revealed that this is the first English language empirical study focusing explicitly on coaching practice in that country.

1.9 Structure of Thesis

1.9.1 Chapter 1: Introduction

The introduction section provides an overview of the nature and rationale for the topic and provides direction for the rest of the thesis. This chapter highlights the topic under investigation and its importance, not only in Iraq coaching contexts but for sport coaching in general. The chapter presents the introduction, social cultural and economic conditions and coaching context of Iraq, Statement of the Problem, Background of the study, Research Aim and Sub-Questions, Significance of the study, Theoretical Framework, Thesis Structure and Summary.

1.9.2 Chapter 2: Literature Review

Chapter 2 presents detailed reviews of literature on past studies relevant to the topic. Broad categories of research include coaching philosophies, holistic coaching practices, motivation, self-efficacy and self-esteem, coaching effectiveness, coach knowledge and coaching styles. The synthesis of these fields of literature assists with identifying pertinent gaps in knowledge and the literature that this study seeks to fill.

1.9.3 Chapter 3: Methodology and Research Design

In Chapter 3, the methodology and research design are presented. This chapter outlines the research questions and the choice and rationale for methodologies and methods that will be employed to answer the research questions. The rationale is given for the mixed methods case study, my role as an insider-researcher, and why employ quantitative and qualitative methods in a sequential explanatory procedure. The selected data collection methods include questionnaire, video recordings and interviews. The research setting of elite volleyball in Iraq is explained, including who are the participants, which, in this study, are the coaches and players of two men's and two women's teams from two high performing clubs in northern Iraq (four teams). The questionnaire, observational analysis of video, including inter-rater reliability, and the interview protocols are detailed. This is followed by the coding procedures, featuring NVivo, coding samples and how the thematic analysis was conducted. This chapter includes the ethical considerations for conducting such a study, which must address important issues of privacy rights, de-identification, confidentiality and anonymity, participant welfare and free and informed consent. Samples of each data collection tool are provided in this chapter, as well as included in full in the Appendices.

1.9.4 Chapter 4: Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) Findings

The first of three findings chapters, presented in order of sequential data collection, Chapter 4 presents the results of the Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) questionnaire (Fox & Corbin, 1989; Fox, 1990). PSPP summary results, descriptive and ANOVA statistics for each player across the four teams are presented ($n = 48$), including Dejlal Men's team, Dejlal Women's team, Furat Men's team and Furat Women's team. It is followed by a discussion of the PSPP results, including those individual constructs and sub-domains that were valued most highly, those that were least valued, those that had consensus across teams and genders, and finally, those which had most disagreement across teams and genders.

1.9.5 Chapter 5: Observational Analysis of Coaching Sessions

Chapter 5 is the second findings chapter, presenting the observational data analysis from the four coaching sessions (one per team). This chapter includes researcher narratives of each coaching session and descriptive statistics of phases of coaching sessions and primary coaching behaviours evident in each team. Comparative statistics by gender and analyses of observed practices are drawn from these findings and later discussed in Chapter 7.

1.9.6 Chapter 6: Interview Findings

This chapter presents the third data set of coach and player interviews, conducted after the PSPP surveys and video recordings had been analysed. In-depth, semi-structured interviews, drawing on 13 questions around coaching philosophies, approaches, practices and preferences were conducted with the four head coaches, four assistant coaches ($n = 8$) and four players from each team ($n = 16$). Thematic analysis of the 24 interview transcripts using NVivo was conducted, generating 20 initial codes used to elicit 6 'parent' codes or themes. These six themes include participant context, coaching philosophy, coaching approach, holistic coaching, coach professional learning and player development.

1.9.7 Chapter 7: Discussion

This chapter presents the major findings from all data analysis chapters and the discussion is connected to the review of literature. The three primary research questions are revisited and answered in this chapter via ensuing discussion.

1.9.8 Chapter 8: Implications and Conclusion

This chapter of the thesis presents the implications of the six key findings discussed in the previous chapters and offers conclusions to the study. Strengths and limitations of the research are included here as well as recommendations for future research. This chapter provides the opportunities for the realization of the significance of the study, including for coach learning, coach development, player learning, and regional sport development.

1.10 Conclusion

I hold with great respect and responsibility the task of investigating coach and player perceptions of volleyball coaching approaches and valued practices in Iraq with a view to advancing my own and my colleagues' professional educational practice and volleyball sport development. This chapter has outlined the background, importance and significance of the study. It has also outlined the social, economic and cultural context of Iraqi sports coaching. Several major social and economic circumstances related to extended periods of armed conflict have impacted on sporting participation due to safety and security issues, a lack of funding for equipment and sports venues and the availability of trained coaches. The cultural context in Iraq including patriarchal family relationships, the social status of women and the traditions of Islam were shown to impact the level of participation of female athletes in Iraq and the conditions under which participation in sport occurs. No studies have been undertaken to examine the potential barriers to female participation in volleyball using data gathered from players themselves.

Iraqi administration of volleyball was considered, paying attention to coach training and development. This review indicated that although formal coaching certification was available, the training was outdated and not widely available. This section indicated that volleyball coach training is conducted within an apprenticeship model and exhibits similarities with the traditional models of sport coaching originating in 19th century Europe. However, coaching approaches observed in elite volleyball are shaped in specific ways by social and cultural values extant in Iraq society. A key focus of this social context was to understand the social dynamics for elite volleyball coaching in Iraq including the contribution of cultural traditions, hierarchical social relations and their influence upon coach development. No study to date has been conducted to investigate the social and cultural dynamics of elite volleyball coaching in Iraq.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this study is to provide a point in time analysis of coach and player perceptions of coaching approaches and practices in two elite volleyball clubs in Iraq, seeking to understand how the coaches' philosophies, approaches, and practices, along with players' physical self-perception and their own ideas about coaching, might be connected (Chase & Martin, 2013). The research question and sub-questions intend to identify aspects of coaching which are well regarded and those that are less valued by coaches and players. Chapter 2 includes a review of literature designed to inform the research problem and is structured as follows. Section 2.1 provides the overview to the chapter. Section 2.2 is concerned with what the literature says about the motivation, self-esteem, and self-efficacy of players in team sports, particularly at a high or elite level. Section 2.3 critiques literature about domains of sports coaching, including from where knowledge is derived, how it is connected to the context of coaching, such as the type and level of sport, and the particular needs of athletes with whom coaches work. Coaching roles and competencies are also critiqued here. Section 2.4 addresses the ideas and research into coaching styles that are typical in team sports like volleyball, from "traditional" approaches often described as being on a continuum from "autocratic" to "democratic" (Martens, 2012). Much research has investigated how coaching sessions are organised and the practices within, being concerned with "skills and drills" (Doozen & Bae, 2016) to evolving approaches such as Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU; Bunker & Thorpe, 1982). Section 2.5 focuses upon a particular approach to coaching known as "humanistic" (Cassidy et al., 2016), whereby coaches and players co-create learning environments designed to improve player autonomy and decrease reliance on external forces of control (Falcão, Bloom, & Bennie, 2017). Research into this approach to coaching is important to "close the loop" between player self-efficacy and coaching practices. Section 2.6 then presents a small but important field of literature concerning the use of practice theory and practice architectures (Kemmis et al., 2014). The theory of practice architectures (TPA) appears

to offer a robust theoretical lens with which to analyse coaches and players' views on their most valued approaches to coaching and their practices, which are captured in video recordings. Section 2.7 concludes this chapter, with a synthesis of key ideas taken from each section and how they inform our understanding of coach and player perceptions of valued coaching approaches and practices in two elite volleyball clubs.

The research problem is particularly concerned with sports pedagogy. Sport pedagogy is the academic field of study located at the intersection between sport and education (Li & Cruz, 2008; Stiller, Würth, & Alfermann, 2004). Armour (2011) stated that sport pedagogy is concerned with the learning, teaching, and instruction in sport, physical education, and related areas of physical activity. Sports pedagogy is underpinned by general education theories and practice theories, bringing together the fields of sport science and education (Tinning, 2008). Understanding sport pedagogy assists in the development of highly qualified, skilled coaches who can effectively engage players at different levels of ability and career. Developments in sport pedagogy provide coaches with a chance to learn new techniques, theories, approaches, and principles, enhancing their professional skills.

Sports pedagogy is theoretically supported by sport psychology and theories of skill acquisition such as Fitts and Posner's (1967) three-phase model. This model suggests that skill learning progresses through identifiable phases that Fitts and Posner labelled cognitive, associative, and autonomous. These phases are characterised by the psychological processes involved in skill acquisition and supported by learning environments and coaching feedback. Such a model may provide support for a "linear" approach to sport pedagogy that privileges the teaching of games skills (Kee, 2019). Alternative models of game learning (e.g., TGFU, Games Sense) have more recently provided support for "non-linear" pedagogies that focus on game appraisal, decision-making, adaptation, and skill application (Kendellen & Camiré, 2019). These models contribute to the development of a coaching philosophy by shaping the coaching context and player-coach relationships. These alternative approaches are discussed in detail in Section 2.4 of this chapter.

The following section zooms in on research into what motivates players to play, what factors have been found to affect their self-esteem, and the conditions that produce higher or lower self-efficacy. Understanding what motivates players and what researchers have found to improve self-efficacy becomes an essential part of professional coaching knowledge which, it could be argued, coaches of elite volleyball players should know.

2.2 Motivation, Self-Esteem, and Self-Efficacy of Players

A key aspect of this study is to investigate athletes' motivation for involvement in elite sport in Iraq and the implications of this for coaches' professional knowledge and their coaching practices. The growing interest in sports psychology has led to motivation playing a more prominent role with respect to sports achievement and ongoing participation (Holden et al., 2017). Ntoumanis, Quested, Reeve, and Cheon (2018) argued that motivation is the main factor that explains a player's performance. Sallis and Patrick (1994) stated that psychological factors are important for sporting achievement and motivation to continue to engage with a sport. This section thus outlines some key definitions drawn from the literature before moving into the relationship between coaching approaches, motivation, and performance.

Achievement motivation is conceptualized as behaviour in which the player's goal is to develop or demonstrate—to self or to others—high ability, or to avoid demonstrating low ability: it has subjective meaning to which the player assigns success or failure (Nicholls, 1984, p. 328). Sports psychology research indicates that individual differences exist in achievement motivation and that such differences will impact on sport participation and performance (Holden, Pugh, & Schwartz, 2017). For example, some players need high levels of motivational input from coaches and significant others such as family and peers (extrinsic motivation), while others require little external motivation to maintain focus and achieve their aims (intrinsic motivation). Wigfield and Eccles (2000) found that there were gender differences in participation rates, forms of competition, and levels of physical activity. Accordingly, there appear different motivational forces underpinning male and female athletes' willingness to sustain their participation in sport and physical activity (Alesi, Gomez-Lopez, Borrego, Monteiro, & Granero-Gallegos, 2019).

Loffing, Hagemann, Schorer, and Baker (2015) distinguished between the *motivational climate* and *performance climate* in sport contexts. They argued that in establishing a performance climate, the coach places a focus on winning and outstanding outcomes, requiring significant ego involvement. Within a motivational climate, the emphasis is placed on learning new things, such as sports skills and tactics. Van Puyenbroeck, Stouten, and Vande Broek (2018) evaluated the role of motivational climate and the needs supportive coaching across various volleyball teams in Belgium. As Loffing et al. described, motivational climate can be established by focusing on learning more than performance, and rewarding behaviours that players themselves intrinsically value. In a sport setting, the role of the team is highly challenging, where coaches can benefit from proactive players who are taking initiatives for

providing feedback and suggestions. In Van Puyenbroeck and colleagues' study, the mediating role of motivational climate of performance and mastery was determined with respect to the proactivity of the team and psychological behaviours for needs- supportive coaching. The sample size comprised of 105 female and 75 male players who completed a questionnaire. Three kinds of proactivity approaches were identified: *upward communication, taking charge and athlete voice*. The results indicated that attending to needs support in coaching approaches have a positive relation with establishing a mastery climate.

Success and failure in sport, then, is largely dependent on motivational levels that enable the player and coach to attain pre-established goals (Alesi et al., 2019). Furthermore, an overemphasis on performance climate may discourage athletes, particularly females, from engaging and persisting with a sport (Loffman et al., 2015). The coach can create a positive atmosphere that enhances the athlete's motivational levels, leading to improved performance (learning and refinement of skills and tactics) and successful achievement of goals. Loffman et al. (2015) argued that these two orientations are useful in establishing motivation and performance as these orientations may inform their coaching philosophy and the resultant coaching styles and approaches enacted. They argued that in the performance climate the trainer places a focus on winning and outstanding outcomes with significant ego involvement. Within a motivational climate, the emphasis is placed on learning new sports skills and tactics. The next section examines the kinds of approaches which the literature has shown to influence player motivation and performance, distinguishing between the motivational climate and performance climate in sport contexts.

2.2.1 Coaching Approaches Influencing Motivation and Performance

Gillison et al.'s (2017) research into performance in physical activity argued that there are four key challenges for optimising performance. These challenges can be summarised as (a) knowledge-based, (b) procedure-based, (c) resource-based, and (d) motivation-based challenges. Where knowledge or skills are lacking, the individual's ability to perform specific tasks, procedures, and processes will be hampered. With elite volleyball players in Iraq, knowledge of the game will not be lacking, nor will performing routine skills, but perhaps knowledge of new ways of learning skills could be lacking. Where procedures or processes are inadequate, so participants' effectiveness, their quality, and their safety may be impacted. This may become important in terms of the effectiveness of the coach. The relative availability of resources can limit players' ability to complete specific tasks, which could be an issue in war-affected Iraq, where resources to play, resources to travel, and resources to offer sustained high-

level competition are lacking. When motivation is lacking, tasks remain incomplete even when players know how to perform the task. Accordingly, when a coach develops a focus on the broad range of factors that influence performance, such as knowledge, procedures, resources, and motivation, they are better able to motivate their athletes to achieve higher levels of performance (Gillison et al., 2017). Focusing on how players develop new knowledge about their game, or new ways to develop essential skills, can generate the conditions that can lead to better reflection, persistence, and problem solving (Milistetd, Peniza, Trudel, & Paquette, 2018).

Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2012) categorises motivation in terms of extrinsic or intrinsic factors. In sporting contexts, players with greater levels of intrinsic motivation tend to enjoy the process of skills improvement and performance strategies aligned with their personal values and goals. They are highly passionate and tend to actively engage in sports, following the ethical norms associated with competition. The players exhibiting more extrinsic motivation tend to strive towards achieving external rewards rather than achieving goals in alignment with their values. As a consequence, these participants tend to be less invested in the particular sport and its ethical norms (Alesi et al., 2019). Understanding what motivates elite volleyballers in this study will contribute to understanding the approaches they value, and how or if such approaches reflect their coaches' approaches, including what knowledge, procedures, resources, and motivation they bring to the coaching setting.

One study (McLean & Mallet, 2012) has illustrated that player expectations can influence the quality of interaction between athlete and coach, the types of interaction that occur, as well as frequency of feedback provided. Expectancy theory proposes that coaches' feedback patterns will differ according to whether their players have high or low expectancy with respect to their own performance (Burton & Raedeke, 2008). Players having lower expectancy obtain minimum support and less opportunity for demonstrating their skill level. In Burton and Raedeke's (2008), they found at the commencement of the competitive season that players had less expectancy of obtaining feedback from their coaches. Over the course of the season, feedback focusing on technical skill execution tended to be offered to players who expected it, becoming even more evident as the season progressed. This indicated that the coach adapted his or her communication patterns to players with different levels of expectancy in accordance with critical periods of competition across the season (Burton & Raedeke, 2008).

It is clear that the approaches that coaches select to motivate their players to learn and achieve their goals are critical to player performance. Over time and with sustained engagement, players need to believe in their ability to perform at even higher levels. The next

section looks at self-efficacy, how it is developed, and its role in elite player performance, such as that expected of the elite volleyball players in this study.

2.2.2 Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is defined as a person's belief in their ability to perform a specific task (Bandura, 1977). According to Sum et al. (2018), self-efficacy is based on the beliefs the individual holds about their capabilities within the organisation, their abilities to carry out required tasks, and the resources they can draw on to manage certain situations. Barlow and Banks (2014) examined the relationship between self-efficacy and the impact of verbal persuasion and emotional arousal on players, factors that are key in the coaching context. For example, how and when do coaches speak to their players? How do they increase or decrease players' emotional states, in training or in match play? Investigating the verbal interaction between coaches and players during training can shed light upon coaches' approaches to building player self-efficacy.

Hepler and Feltz's (2012) study investigated the relationship between decision-making performance in sport and players' self-efficacy, finding that their decision-making ability is dependent on their self-efficacy. The authors found that positive associations between self-efficacy and decision-making also influenced the player's motivation: the player needs to believe they make effective decisions in training and competition in order to find the motivation to train and continue in their sport. How, then, do coaches support player decision-making in training? How do they collect or provide feedback on when the right decisions were made? Observation of coach and player interactions on critical play-making moments in training may provide insights into how this occurs.

Song and Kim (2018) suggested that a wide variety of factors, including team or individual success, physical health, performance, coping strategies in stressful situations, mental health, team morale, and motivation levels have both direct and indirect impacts on self-efficacy. As established earlier, sports coaches need to remember that players deal with an extensive array of psychological and emotional factors that can affect their performance (Cassidy et al., 2016). The mental game can be fostered to unlock their maximum potential through a better understanding of the psychological dimensions of athletes' performance, such as self-efficacy (Song & Kim, 2018). This again points to the need to collect data around players' perceptions of their physical ability to perform and connect these data to observable coaching practices that support their perceptions.

Barlow and Banks (2014) suggested that physical conditioning is an important contributor to self-efficacy, which in turn underpins the athlete's motivation towards performance. Similarly, Laureano, Grobbelaar, and Nienaber (2014) argued that enhancing a player's physical fitness supports skill development and impacts on their self-efficacy. In this study, it would be helpful to ask and to take a form of measurement of the relationship between physical conditioning and players' self-efficacy or self-perception.

Coaching approaches should support player self-efficacy; that much is clear from the research. The next section moves to examine self-esteem and self-concept, examining evidenced connections between coaching approaches that support them.

2.2.3 Self-Esteem, Physical Conditioning, and Coaching Approaches

Self-esteem is different from self-efficacy. Self-esteem relates to one's self-concept and self-acceptance. Self-esteem can be influenced by sport competence, physical strength, and physical condition. Skills gained while participating in sport can lead to a greater perception of self-worth (Ebbeck & Gibbons, 1998), along with other aspects such as perceived strength and endurance fitness. For example, Mills, Munroe, and Hall (2000) argued that a coach must be able to evaluate players' physical abilities, skills, and talent in order to help them improve the psychological dimensions of performance. Conversely, players must recognise that their self-efficacy can be influenced by different variables including mental and physical fitness, leadership capabilities, environmental influences, and social interactions (Ebbeck & Gibbons, 1998). It will be important in this study to ascertain players' physical self-perception and self-worth and to make connections to coaching practices which enhance physical fitness and conditioning.

The opportunity to develop physical conditioning is fundamental to players' ability to improve in their fitness and physical skills. Some players have high levels of personal fitness and skills but lack the motivation to seek team selection. Others may have been highly motivated, giving the coach a useful resource to draw on. Opportunities to participate in physical conditioning may have to be provided in coaching time, given the resourcing contexts of particular clubs, the safety of players, and their own socio-economic backgrounds.

Physical ability, personal motivation, and self-perception all contribute to a player's desire to improve their sport skills and fitness (Fox & Corbin, 1989). Improvements in skill levels, which are connected to physical conditioning and learning, are associated with improvements in physical self-concept and physical self-efficacy (Miller & Aloise, 1989), which in turn increase player motivation and performance. Song and Kim (2018) suggested

that an individual's self-efficacy is a useful predictor of behavioural attitude. Individuals with a greater sense of self-efficacy are prone to participate more frequently and readily in a related activity. Gillison et al. (2017) and Sum et al. (2018) confirmed that higher levels of self-efficacy directly correlated with greater efforts, willingness, and persistence of participants in carrying out physical tasks, indicating that coaches should pay close attention to how their practices support player self-efficacy.

Fox (2000) showed that global self-esteem could be enhanced through a physical conditioning program lasting 12 weeks or more. Increased physical self-esteem is the goal of such a program and may be a key psychological factor for improvement in performance. Moreover, success in physical performance has an effect on physical self-efficacy, which in turn impacts on the individual's self-esteem. Physical self-esteem has been measured in numerous studies, including Fox and Corbin (1989) and Fox (2000), and has been shown to have a significant positive impact on behaviours related to physical activity and exercise (cf. Şahin & Bastık, 2019).

Francis and Jones (2014) stated that equating performative success with coaching effectiveness often focuses on approaches by coaches that create enthusiastic and motivated athletes. However, these authors cautioned that the team's success is not the sole responsibility of the coach. Jowett (2017) confirmed that coaching approaches that prioritize motivation can lead to successful performance outcomes, evaluated on the basis of individual player development, win/loss percentages, and positive psychological response outcomes in athletes. Success then encompasses outcomes related to athletes' self-esteem, perceived abilities, satisfaction, and enjoyment of their sport. May, Els, and Viljoen (2014) disputed the focus on competition success within the sports environment in Iraq, arguing that exposure to sport offered male and female athletes professional development and life skills, as well as technical proficiency. As a result, this study intends to investigate what drives observed coaches' practices and what they value by asking them about their coaching philosophies and their coaching approaches. It is also why players should be asked what approaches they prefer and value and why.

2.3 Types of Knowledge and Roles Required in Sports Coaching

According to Culver et al. (2009), sports coaching comprises three interrelated domains: the coaches' knowledge, the coaching context, and the athletes' needs and outcomes. All three domains impact on coaching approaches and practices. In elite sporting contexts, extensive sport-specific knowledge is an integral element of coaching. The coach's knowledge

base is applied systematically to devise programs that ensure incremental improvements in the athlete's performance. The source of coaches' knowledge may arise from their experience as a player and/or through formal coach education programs (Stodter & Cushion, 2019). It may be that the coach's knowledge has been sourced from past practices which have not had any opportunity to be updated in the present.

The coach must also take into account the specific context or environment in which coaching takes place. The coaching context encompasses the social and cultural context, the sport's norms and traditions, and the level of competition (Cassidy et al., 2016). The coaching context varies considerably in elite sports and may include national or international competition, club and youth development, or recreational sporting involvement. Schempp (1993) argued, like Culver et al. (2009), that supporting athletes to meet their aspirations is highly dependent upon the knowledge that coaches require to perform various tasks and to meet certain obligations. Rylander (2016) also suggested that coaching can be enhanced by developing interrelated skill sets and knowledge so the coach can interact with all the actors influencing sporting performance. Moreover, Gilbert and Trudel (2001) have argued that coaches must possess the sound knowledge foundation to problem solve, make decisions, and reflect critically on their own coaching practices.

It appears, then, that coaches must draw on a diverse knowledge base from disciplines including motor learning and exercise science, as well as philosophy and pedagogy. Coaches must also draw on a set of what Woodman (1993) called "soft skills" to build team cohesion, focus, and productive relationships with individual athletes. Although a number of ways of describing coaching knowledge foundations have been proposed (Greenwood, Davids, & Renshaw, 2012; Stodter & Cushion, 2019), Côté and Gilbert (2009) and Milistetd et al. (2017) have argued that the domain of coaches' knowledge can be further characterised by three key components: their professional knowledge, interpersonal knowledge, and intrapersonal knowledge. The following sections thus examine these forms of coaches' knowledge that contribute to effective coaching practice.

2.3.1 Coaches' Professional Knowledge

Professional knowledge may be consistent across many sports, including how coaches should behave and treat athletes, or coaches' ethics, for example (Cassidy et al., 2016; Martens, 2012). Anderson (1985) and Arroyo et al. (2016) suggested that professional coaching knowledge consists of declarative and procedural knowledge. A coach's declarative knowledge typically concerns the "what" of coaching, including coaching in general and coaching specific

to the sport. For example, knowledge about energy systems, sports-specific training and conditioning methods, biomechanics, and motor learning principles can be applied across many sports, but skill-related technical knowledge, rules, and game strategy are specific to the sport. This form of knowledge is typically gained from being a player and also from coaching education programs.

Procedural knowledge in coaching refers to the practical elements of the role: knowing how to coach and how to implement specific programs in practical coaching or competitive situations (Anderson, 1985; Arroyo et al., 2016). Schempp (1993) argued that procedural knowledge enables coaches to improve athletes' technical skill proficiency and tactical awareness. As procedural knowledge is often tacit and harder to articulate than declarative knowledge, it is sometimes associated with the "art" of coaching (Collins & Martindale, 2006). Typically, procedural knowledge is developed through the coaches' participatory experience (as athlete, coach, or both) in addition to the strategies and practices required for the task at hand. Procedural knowledge can be enhanced through coach education programs focusing on pedagogy and dealing with structuring coaching sessions and programs, skill teaching progressions, questioning techniques, and providing feedback. It will be important to consider what kinds of professional learning coaches have had access to under circumstances of prolonged conflict in Iraq, which may (or may not) have enabled them to develop their procedural knowledge, or the art of their coaching.

These types of coaching knowledge are comparable to the knowledge required when developing teaching expertise. Shulman (1986) suggested that effective teachers must possess high levels of content knowledge—the facts pertaining to their chosen subject as well as the conventions of structuring and expressing that knowledge. This can be compared to declarative knowledge. Teachers also require pedagogical content knowledge—an understanding of learning theories, the factors influencing knowledge transfer and acquisition, and the teaching styles that enhance student learning (Shulman, 1986). This pedagogical knowledge represents coaching procedural knowledge.

Anderson (1985) suggested that both declarative and procedural knowledge were essential for the development of expertise in any domain. Elite coaches require high levels of procedural knowledge gained from extensive experience in the high-performance setting to successfully develop and monitor coaching programs and to support players during competition (Duffy et al., 2011). As knowledge can be acquired through lived experience (Reynaud, 2004), expert coaches can draw on a wealth of experience in different programming and competitive contexts to improve outcomes. Coaches in elite settings need extensive,

specialised knowledges in their chosen sport, including sport science, psychology, and pedagogy. Much of this knowledge is derived from research conducted at elite competition sites, such as the Olympics. For example, Palao, Santos, and Ureña (2004) found that the differentiating skill between the top-performing men's volleyball teams at the Sydney Olympics was their blocking ability, whereas for women's volleyball teams it was the quality of the spike (p. 50). Holley (2009) noted that elite coaches must draw on their experience to develop effective teamwork and on their sports science knowledge to achieve optimum player performance. Possessing a wide knowledge base is considered a defining characteristic of an expert coach (Côté & Gilbert, 2009). Having the opportunity to engage in elite-level research, or to attend forums in which such research is shared, would be crucial for coaches to be able to develop their declarative knowledge (the what) and procedural knowledge (the how).

2.3.2 Coaches' Interpersonal and Intrapersonal Knowledge

Beyond their professional knowledge, coaches must also be able to collaborate with others, particularly their players. The capacity of the coach to develop the quality of coach-player relationships is partly dependent on the coach's *interpersonal knowledge*, including their emotional intelligence (Fox, 2011). This is particularly important for sustaining athlete motivation and for developing 'team spirit' (Fox, 2006). Côté and Gilbert (2009) defined interpersonal knowledge as the ability to interact with others, drawing on a range of approaches. Coaches draw on interpersonal knowledge to identify ways of relating to players that build and maintain productive relationships (Becker, 2009). Additionally, Côté and Gilbert (2009) suggested that while it is important that the coach has an effective technical knowledge base in their chosen sport, this knowledge is only brought to life through positive coach/player relationships. The coach needs to create and maintain relationships through communication, positive reinforcement, and personal availability and trust building. Côté, Bruner, Erickson, Strachan, and Fraser-Thomas (2010) noted the key importance of coaches' interpersonal knowledge in building empathy towards athletes, nurturing positive attitudes, motivating, and inspiring athletes. Interpersonal knowledge is important for building player-coach relationships, founded on trust, through which ethical and personal issues can be effectively addressed and managed.

Interpersonal knowledge supports the coach's role as a leader, an active communicator, and a facilitator of teamwork, problem solving, and positive relationships between coaching staff (Côté & Gilbert, 2009). Underscoring the importance of interpersonal knowledge, Irwin et al. (2004) suggested that coaches should be encouraged to develop their skill sets to develop

more effective and appropriate forms of communication with their athletes. How coaches communicate with their athletes is an observable behaviour during coaching sessions which can be notated. Such notations can provide insights into what kinds of interpersonal knowledge coaches of volleyball teams in Iraq possess and how they use them in their approaches.

Another important type of knowledge is *intrapersonal knowledge*. Côté and Gilbert (2009) indicated that intrapersonal knowledge is the understanding of oneself drawn from reflection upon chosen behaviours. Intrapersonal knowledge enables a coach to reflect on their own practice, to identify areas for improving their coaching performance, and to quickly adapt to contingencies arising in the complex and dynamic competitive environment. Intrapersonal knowledge supports coaches' understanding of the motivational forces needed to encourage individual players' development. Hall and Gray (2017) argued that coaches must develop intrapersonal knowledge by addressing their own learning requirements and reflecting on the social context of coaching. The coach's ability to maximise performance outcomes rests on the depth and breadth of their reflective habits as they develop interpersonal knowledge; a coach's systematic and regular reflection can enhance their intrapersonal knowledge (Kroshus, Kerr, DeFreese, & Parsons, 2017). Coaches may show reflective practice when engaged in problem solving or resolving issues via careful examination of the alternatives and critical reflection on the circumstances. Reflective practices induce self-awareness and contribute to critical thinking to facilitate learning through experience. Reflective practice entails thoughtful deliberation for analysing experiences to facilitate learning and critical thinking. It is vital for a coach to recognise, through self-reflection, the core values and competencies that lead to enhanced coaching abilities and personally sustainable approaches to coaching over an individual's career. Coaches who engage in systematic self-reflection may use voice recorders or journals/ diaries to record their thoughts and impressions of how coaching sessions unfolded and are practices which are potentially observable during coaching sessions.

Intrapersonal knowledge thus comprises self-awareness, reflection, and a disposition towards continuous improvement. With a sound grasp of these elements, a coach can offer support, help, and growth for others. Coaches' interpersonal knowledge can serve to inspire a specific goal and can push them to be accountable for their athletes' sporting proficiency (Weinberg & Gould, 2014). Intrapersonal knowledge ensures coaches perceive their own professional development as an ongoing process spanning their entire career and not as time-limited, episodic events (Kroshus, Kerr, DeFreese, & Parsons, 2017). This means coaches should strive to continuously improve their coaching through professional development. In addition, the development of a strong learning and support network that facilitate coaches'

professional learning may provide ongoing support for improving and maintaining effective coaching approaches (Light & Harvey, 2019). Along with any other practices that enhance reflection, learning, and therefore intrapersonal knowledge, it will be important to investigate where and how these coaches in Iraq build and sustain their networks in their present circumstances.

2.3.3 Coaching Roles and Forms of Knowledge

Harris-Reeves, Skinner, Milburn, and Reddan (2013) showed that sport coaching is a multifaceted activity with many responsibilities. Culver, Trudel, and Werthner (2009) studied the characteristics of coaching, identifying five key roles: motivation, communication, skills development, planning training/coaching exercises, and evaluating athletes. Each of these areas draws on specific kinds of coaching knowledge. So far, it has been established that coaches must have adequate knowledge of their specific sport (declarative, the what), knowledge of teaching strategies and program design (procedural, the how), and the interpersonal knowledge to effectively communicate with and motivate athletes. Coaches need to understand and be aware of the factors that influence the player-coach relationship and how this in turn impacts on player performance (Kuhlmann, 2016). Norman (2015) also agreed that sports coaches perform the roles of motivator, strategist, character builder, and teacher, among others. Coaching responsibilities require significant personal investment in terms of time and resources, which may have both negative and positive consequences (Krukowska, Poczwardowski, & Parzelski, 2015). According to Omiya et al. (2014), teaching is an essential dimension of sports coaching. Accordingly, coaches require effective communication skills to move teams towards success in their specific sport. The core competencies of coaching and their relationship to coaches' foundational knowledges, as identified by Milistetd, Galatti, Collet, Tozetto, & Nascimento (2017), are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Coach core competencies and knowledges (Milistetd, Galatti, Collet, Tozetto, & Nascimento, 2017, reproduced with permission under Creative Commons).

Figure 3 illustrates sport coaching as a dynamic, multi-dimensional process consisting of six core competencies that define coaching practice, which closely align with Cote and Gilbert's (2009) three domains. These core competencies were derived from the authors' research into coach education incorporated into Bachelor Education programs at university (Milistetd et al., 2017) and relate to the coach's complex array of leadership roles and responsibilities. For example, coaches are required to *set a vision and devise strategies* to fulfil performance objectives for competition. This function is informed by the coach's *values and philosophy* along with the knowledge of appropriate performance *goals to guide action*. Coaches are also responsible for enacting a vision in practice by *shaping the environment, conducting practices and building relationships* between players and coaching staff and within the team. Such functions may be informed by the coach's *professional knowledge* (e.g., declarative, such as knowledge of skill acquisition, and procedural, such as how to teach) and *interpersonal knowledge*. Finally, the coach's capacity to *learn and reflect* as a foundation for continuous improvements may be informed by their *values and philosophy* and *intrapersonal knowledge*. (Milistetd et al., 2017). It is argued that relatively inexperienced coaches perceived their self as less competent as compared to experienced coaches. It is also pointed out that additional training is required regarding the orientation of competition and practice, unwritten conduct, and unmatched expectation. The lack of core competencies and knowledge results in

mistakes, errors, and frustration, and leads to slower professional and personal growth. Moen and Federici (2013) found that greater levels of perceived competencies of coaching emphasising relational challenges produced greater satisfaction among elite athletes. Hence, player perspectives via interviews of the perceptions of the coach's competence is important for this study.

Recent research into coaching roles has shown that many facets suggested by Culver et al. (2009) and Milistetd et al. (2017) are still pertinent, but that in elite sport, these facets can be distributed across multiple personnel. McCullick, Dooley, Schempp, and Isaac (2020) evaluated the responsibilities and roles of elite-level coaching staff in basketball. They applied case study research design and conducted extensive observation, generating observation records and interviews as main sources of data. The data analysis revealed that the coaching framework revolved around three primary components—competition, organization, and training. Coaching responsibilities then were assigned on the basis of expertise of staff, where the entire staff possessed skill sets that permitted the overlap of roles. This enabled staff to move between roles (such as fitness motivator and game strategist) depending upon the components they were addressing (e.g., training versus competition). The idea of categories of coaching responsibilities addresses the idea that coaches often have assistant coaches and are not solely responsible for every role: those roles can be shared amongst multiple coaching staff. The division of labour amongst volleyball coaching staff in these elite clubs in Iraq would be interesting to observe and note as it could point to the status of each various role (e.g., is being a fitness trainer and motivator more important than being a strategy coach?), the frequency of these observed behaviours, and the value placed upon them by the coaches.

2.4 Coaching Approaches

As this study is concerned with what coaching approaches players and coaches value in elite volleyball clubs, it is necessary to understand the range and breadth of coaching approaches that could be drawn upon. Martens (2012) identified three kinds of coaching approaches—command, submissive, and cooperative—with each category characterised by various strengths and weaknesses. In the command approach, the role of the coach is to make all decisions, and the role of the athlete is to respond to those decisions. Martens (2012) asserted that this is considered by far the most prevalent form of coaching. The submissive style is less prevalent, though it does exist, and allows others to “dominate the conversation” (Martens, 2012). The cooperative coach can be understood as being along the same continuum of coaching approaches, at the opposite end, making it a “command-cooperative continuum”.

Command coaching can also be understood as an *autocratic* style, in which coaches prefer to have full control of their training programs and allow very little scope for athletes' opinions, whilst at the other end is the cooperative or *democratic* style in which players have more control (Lyle, 2002). Andrew and Kent's (2007) study of U.S. collegiate tennis noted that although many coaches tended to be autocratic, their athletes preferred more democratic approaches. Turner's (2015) research into female collegiate volleyball players confirmed that female athletes generally preferred coaching approaches which emphasised strategic and situational awareness, while an autocratic coaching style was regarded unfavourably. This proved true across all the independent variables investigated, with female athletes instructed by female coaches preferring greater levels of social support and positive feedback than male athletes instructed under male coaches. Horn, Bloom, Berglund, and Packard (2011) argued from their collegiate level research that not all players necessarily have the same preferences with respect to coaching approaches and that coaching approaches can impact athletes' attitudes and level of achievement. They suggested that considering individual players' preferred coaching approaches is imperative in order to maximise the coach's ability to improve both individual and team performances (Horn et al., 2011). In this study, it will be important to investigate how coaches take into consideration players' preferences for coaching approaches. Do they invite player input? Do they ask?

Edmunds, Ntoumanis, and Duda (2008) showed that the coach's approach has a positive impact upon athletes' performance, especially when that behaviour is supportive. Mann (2009) confirmed that coaches with supportive coaching styles tended to develop their players' self-confidence and motivation towards success. Wildman (2006) argued that a coach's ability to adapt and adjust their coaching to player's needs is critical for effective coaching and team performance. The command or autocratic coach is generally reluctant to discuss the coaching program, tends to be critical of player performance, and does not encourage athlete input into the coaching program (Martens, 2012). The submissive coach offers little guidance or leadership to players and tends to allow players to take organisational responsibility for coaching sessions. Cooperative or democratic coaching involves making decisions following consultation with players, establishing goals with realistic expectations, and resolving problems through collaborative processes (Martens, 2012). A key focus with the democratic or cooperative approach is to engender a sense of team loyalty whereby team performance and success is seen as the joint responsibility of both coach and athletes (Wardle, 2014).

Within the continuum of approaches to coaching are models for games teaching. Considered part of the procedural knowledge base of coaches (the how), these may range from traditional, linear models of skill to game progression, to newer, non-linear, or cyclical approaches to coaching in which the skill-to-game progression is deliberately interrupted. The following section introduces some of the most prevalent models of games teaching which could be expected to inform coaching approaches to elite volleyball in Iraq.

2.4.1 Traditional Models of Games Teaching

The following sections contrast traditional, linear models of coaching, of skill-to-game progression, with contemporary approaches including teaching games for understanding (TGfU) and games sense models (Light, Swabey, & Brooker, 2004). These latter two are models of coaching which I had no knowledge of from my years of coaching in Iraq. They are Western models of learning and teaching in sport about which I wanted to know more in order to look for their characteristics in coaching practices in Iraq. The traditional model is characterised by the structure of typical coaching sessions. This usually includes, in order, a general warm up, activities focus on game-specific skill development, and technical refinement of skills including direct instruction and skill drills, playing modified games, and full games (Doozan & Bae, 2016). The keystone philosophy underpinning this model is that the acquisition and technical refinement of specific games skills is of primary importance to players' game performance. Once the basic skills used in the game are mastered, players will be capable of playing the game by effectively performing the prerequisite skills in game situations (de Faria Pastore, de Azevedo Ferreira, da Costa, & João, 2016). A player's game performance is thought to improve largely as a result of developing and refining technical skill execution. Accordingly, traditional models of games teaching focus on developing the player's technical skills. The "linear" reasoning and the assumptions underpinning the traditional approach to games teaching are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The linear model of games teaching (Bunker & Thorpe, 1982, p. 5).

Day, Carter, and Carpenter (2013) suggested that the dominance of the traditional, linear model of coaching and games teaching has been sustained partly because of historical assumptions relating to the origins of coaching expertise. Day et al. argued that traditional approaches to sports coaching that have been documented in various forms of media and literature over the last 200 years have undergone little innovation because “[c]oaches generally emerged from within the activity as retired performers and often used the knowledge and practical skills developed during their competitive lifetime to formulate their own training methods, understanding of skills and approaches to contests” (p. 7). The transfer of knowledge and skills from “coach as retired performer” to new performers was often an oral tradition (Taylor & Garratt, 2013, p. 27) which did not travel far from its origin in sports participation through which performers interacted with each other within similar groups, or “communities of practice” (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1999), often confined to specific geographic locations. Consequently, there was little opportunity for innovation outside these bounded communities of practice and “little separation between the knowledge of and the ability to do coaching” (Taylor & Garratt, 2013, p. 28). This culture of knowledge is referred to as “tacit knowledge”, which Polanyi (2009) described as something that we can know more about than we can say or tell. As the codification of sports in the public schooling systems gathered pace through the 19th century, coaching came to be regulated through the communities of practice that were constituted around sports participation and the emerging domain of sports administration (Taylor & Garratt, 2013).

Coaching traditions in Iraq and the Middle East appear to have followed a similar developmental trajectory, albeit within quite divergent social and cultural contexts. In Iraq, coaching follows traditional patterns with coaches tending to emerge from the ranks of elite players who were acknowledged for their technical skill mastery and game play. In accordance with tradition, coaching across different sports in Iraq has focused on the development of technical skills using well-established skill drills and didactic teaching methods learned from the coaches’ experiences of being coached.

While most researchers and practitioners argue that aspects of the traditional linear games teaching model remain valid and applicable, more recently, proponents of alternative models of games teaching have argued that the traditional model is limited in its scope and effectiveness. These theorists have suggested that there is a need for revised approaches that refocus on tactical and decision-making dimensions of game play (Butler, 2006; Doozan & Bae, 2016). The following section reviews the TGfU approach to games teaching as one example of these alternative approaches.

2.4.2 Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) Model

The TGfU model was first suggested by Bunker and Thorpe (1982) and refined by Thorpe, Bunker, and Almond (1986) as an alternative to what they saw as the limitations to traditional skills-based models used for teaching games. Bunker and Thorpe and Thorpe et al. suggested that skill-based game instruction lacked authenticity as it tended to separate game skills from the context of performance in games. Furthermore, the traditional approach tended to produce game players who could perform skills competently, but nevertheless, lacked appropriate decision-making in games' contexts and players who were dependent on coaches for decision-making in games (Hay & Macdonald, 2008).

As an alternative approach, TGfU marks a radical shift away from the emphasis on acquiring technical skills, moving towards a tactical approach to the teaching of games. In this approach, tactical awareness of the game is introduced to players in the early stages of learning by engaging them in playing modified games which present opportunities for strategic decision-making regarding game strategy (Miri, 2015). These experiences foreground the tactical issues relating to game play based on a number of generic game types. These game types categorise games according to their structure and the generic strategies required to play them. These categories include invasion games (e.g., soccer, basketball, hockey); striking and fielding games (e.g., baseball, cricket); target games (e.g., archery, golf), and net/wall games (e.g., tennis, badminton). Volleyball is an example of a net/wall game (Mitchell, Oslin, & Griffin, 2013).

One of the advantages of grouping games into generic categories with similar strategies is that players can build tactical awareness and decision-making skills by playing modified games using whatever basic skills they currently possess (Chow et al., 2007). For example, learning generic tactics relating to attack, defence, and controlling space can then be transferred to specific sports (invasion games) that use those tactics, such as soccer, ice hockey, team handball, basketball, and field hockey. For Thorpe et al. (1986), appreciation of the tactical aspects of a specific game can result in a contextualised consideration of what to do (skill selection) and how to do it (skill execution), in contrast to the decontextualised teaching of skills prioritised in the traditional model of games teaching (Doozan & Bae, 2016; Hay & Macdonald, 2008). TGfU thus provides a learner-centred approach that prioritises including participants on the basis of the skills they currently possess over the need to gain prerequisite specialist skills in order to participate in the full version of any game. As a learner-focused model of teaching, the approach is intended to provide the learner with an understanding of the

technical and tactical skills necessary to be successful in a wide variety of game types and the motivation to maintain their engagement in learning how to play games and sports (Light, Swabey, & Brooker, 2004). From this explanation of the model, it would appear that a TGfU approach supports technical and skill development at the elite level and, as such, could be a feature of the coaching approaches taken up in Iraqi volleyball.

Emphasising the key role of game strategy, Bunker and Thorpe (1982) proposed a model for games pedagogy comprising six phases within a cycle (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Teaching Games for Understanding Model (adapted from Bunker & Thorpe, 1982, p. 6).

Each phase of the cycle is described briefly in Table 2.

Table 2

Teaching Games for Understanding—Description of Phases (adapted from Bunker & Thorpe, 1982)

1	Game	Students are introduced to a variety of game forms while building up to the full form of the game.
2	Game Appreciation	Students are taught to understand the rules of the game.
3	Tactical Awareness	Students develop an understanding of the necessary tactics to be used in the game.
4	Decision Making	Student learning is focused on making appropriate decisions during game play based on key strategies for playing the game. Students are taught what to do and how to do it.
5	Skill Execution	Skill execution relates to the production of the required movement within the context of the game. Skills are introduced according to the state of readiness and ability of the athlete to solve a strategic problem within the game.
6	Performance	Performance is regarded as the product of the appropriateness of movement responses and efficiency of movement sequences.

In the late 1980s, researchers began to investigate TGfU empirically, with most studies adopting an experimental design to compare TGfU with traditional skill-based games teaching approaches. Stolz and Pill (2016) observed that investigations on TGfU reported positive and significant results for students. The most significant finding emerging from research (Miri, 2015) suggesting that players who were taught using a TGfU approach tended to perform better with respect to their tactical knowledge and skill selection compared to those taught using a traditional skills-based approach. In addition, a number of studies (Griffin & Butler, 2005; Kirk & MacPhail, 2002; Parry, 2014) concluded that TGfU might be perceived by students and players as more enjoyable and engaging than the traditional techniques-based model, with the result that players may be more highly motivated to take part in learning activities. Much of this research was conducted in school settings rather than elite sports, but the principle of engaging teaching and learning practices is relevant to both settings.

While there has been some support regarding the efficacy of the TGfU approach, Vollmer and Curtner-Smith (2016) have suggested that, despite these promising results, research has not been able to provide conclusive support for the superiority of the TGfU approach over traditional linear games teaching methods, particularly at elite level. The authors have suggested that research findings have been inconsistent; hence, these findings have been difficult to compare due to variations in research design, differences in particular game focus, variables selected for investigation, participants' age, approach to measuring the different

variables, and the nature and length of the intervention. This study has the potential to contribute to international understandings of the characteristics and potential benefits of TGfU that could be translated into coaching practices, but it is not a TGfU intervention per se.

More recently, the TGfU model has been revised to highlight the notion that learning games is facilitated through active engagement with the subject matter and to emphasise the perceptual basis of the learning environment (e.g., cue perception) in the game-oriented approach. The revised model was proposed to illustrate that meaningful learning occurs in game environments that are situated and contextual. The revised model also illustrates that in the game-oriented approach, players learn in contexts in which they are interdependent, and that this relationship may provide positive support for learning (refer to Figure 6).

Figure 6. A model of player decision-making with TGfU (Miri, 2015).

TGfU offers an alternative tactical approach to games teaching that emphasises the coach's understanding of games and game types prior to skill development (Streat & Holt, 2000) and focuses on developing players' tactical knowledge and decision-making capability through integrating the cognitive and contextual dimensions of learning. Hence, TGfU can be conceptualised as a problem-based approach to games teaching wherein the learning of a

particular skill is contextualised with respect to the tactical dimensions of game play. Moreover, it redefines games skills as a means of solving specific strategic problems within games (Hay & Macdonald, 2008). As such, the TGFU approach suggests that it is *impossible to separate skills from tactics in games*. This strategic insight may motivate players to learn specific games skills to enhance their decision-making capabilities in games and problem-solving challenges within games contexts (Hay & Macdonald, 2008). Again, this understanding of how TGFU is intended to work can shed light on what kinds of skill and technique learning approaches seem to dominate in elite volleyball in Iraq.

The following section presents a critique of the literature concerning humanistic coaching, which draws together particular approaches, with particular forms of coach knowledge, and combines them with a deep respect for the context in which players engage in their sport.

2.5 Humanistic, Holistic Coaching

Humanistic coaching is based on the conceptualisation of humanistic psychology (Falcão, Bloom, & Bennie, 2017). It entails that individuals possess the innate tendency of self-actualisation for the development of their own mental and physical capacities. Humanistic coaching aims to enhance or maintain players' roles in improving autonomy and decreasing reliance on external forces of control. A close interpersonal relation among coaches and athletes is emphasised in humanistic coaching and can be realised via sharing decisions, emphasising a collaborative process. A humanistic coach gives greater encouragement to athletes to be self-regulating, encourages player identity development, and accepts different viewpoints, for instance, in establishing rules for the team. Humanistic coaching fosters holistic development by the adoption of caring practices and welfare processes and by always taking an educating approach. A holistic environment is created when three domains of learning have been met: performance, cognitive, and affective (Kidman & Hanrahan, 2011, p. 78). Humanistic approaches result in holistic coaching environments that decrease reliance on coaches and strengthen the reinforcement of player roles and control over their destiny versus coach direction (Falcão et al., 2017). It could be argued that a humanistic coach would incorporate time for players to take control over sections of coaching or have opportunities for input. These could be observable over the course of a coaching session.

Jowett (2017) argued that humanistic coaching practices enable autonomy, shared goal setting, and open communication, as well as well-programmed decision-making. Success can be evaluated against athlete individual goal attainment and self-actualisation, not just team

performance. Humanistic coaching is a person-centred approach that focuses on individual empowerment for achievement of personal objectives within an interpersonal coach-athlete relationship (Jowett, 2017). These approaches utilise different non-manipulative and collaborative methods. Jenny (2017) argued that competition is considered the main vehicle for reaching the full potential of athletes. Competition can be perceived as a central challenge dependent upon the motivation of each individual and the whole team for reaching their potential in a meaningful and skilled performance. Scoring or results are still purposeful for the humanistic coach as they provide assistance in the evaluation of quality of performance of athletes. The pursuit of the fulfilment of potential of the athlete is vital for a humanistic coach and competition is useful for facilitation of this goal. Collaborative decision-making is required as evidence of humanistic coaching practice, where athletes are required to reflect, analyse, and make critical decisions related to the determination and selection of future strategies, facilitated by coaches questioning and seeking player input. Under observation, then, humanistic coaching could be evident in coaches asking their players questions during training.

Like Jowett (2017), Falcao and Bloom (2018) emphasised that the benefits of humanistic coaching are more responsibility for athletes over their own destiny; the coach is no more the sole individual responsible for providing direction, wisdom, and knowledge. Falcao and Bloom argued that this creates an open culture instead of a blame culture, encouraging athletes to realise their maximum potential. It means athletes can become more self-reliant and independent, maintaining more control. However, Falcão, Bloom, and Bennie (2017) pointed out that humanistic coaching is often more focused on individual coaching instead of team coaching. They discussed that issues and conflict might arise if the individual goals of athletes are not aligned within the team.

2.5.1 Player-Coach Relationships and Care in Coaching

Officer and Rosenfeld (1985) suggested that the player-coach relationship is unique because it contains an assemblage of characteristics drawn from other interpersonal relationships. For example, the coach is part teacher, part friend, part professional adviser, and part parent, while the athlete plays the roles of student, friend, and client (Jowett & Timson-Katchis, 2005). Furthermore, coaches can be regarded as educators, acting as mentors and role models, assisting athletes to achieve their personal goals (Olson, 2014). The individual's capacity to effectively communicate in these varied roles is critical to the player-coach relationship. Relationships between coaches and players are neither easily made nor easily sustained; they require thoughtful action based on the coach's interpersonal skills and practical

knowledge. However, once established, a high-quality coach-athlete relationship can be powerful for both parties involved, providing the athlete with a unique level of support as well as information to guide their development (Jowett, 2005).

Smoll and Smith (2006) confirmed that the player-coach relationship can impact a range of dimensions including the athlete's physical performance, psychological state, motivation, and social well-being. Soheily, Manouchehri, and Tojari (2015) supported this, suggesting that coaches must work to ensure positive relationships with players, as effective communication is critical in maximising athletes' fitness, skills, and self-efficacy. The role of humour in establishing and maintaining positive coach-athlete relationships has also been highlighted. Grisaffe, Blom, and Burke (2003) stated that teachers who use humour in their teaching are more effective in improving student learning outcomes (Kaplan & Pascoe, 1977; Nussbaum, Comadena, & Holladay, 1985; Terry & Woods, 1975). Student evaluations of engaging teachers suggest that humour is an important teaching tool (Weaver, Cotrell, & Churchman, 1988). Burke, Peterson, and Nix (1995) and Neuliep (1991) confirmed that teachers' use of humour has positive outcomes for both students and instructors. Similarly, Burke et al. (1995) confirmed that the use of humour helped students to sustain positive perceptions of their teachers.

Recent literature has conceptualised the player-coach relationship as care in coaching (Dohsten et al., 2020; Purdy, Potrac, & Paulauskas, 2016). Caring can be perceived as a virtuous act, based on a moral sense of duty towards others as well as practical wisdom (Purdy et al., 2016). Care can reflect a virtuous disposition, informed by a strong sense of ethical conduct, as well as personal experience coping with moral and ethical issues. Personal experience equates to practical wisdom in these circumstances. An example here could be protecting the athlete from overtraining or from competing with an injury. A coach can utilize virtuous acts and practical wisdom to influence athletes and build trusting player-coach relationships (Purdy et al., 2016).

Caring within a sports coaching context is based on the coach's commitment to the athlete. It involves building and maintaining strong, productive relationships. Purdy et al. (2016) argued that Noddings' (2003) theory of care is applicable in a sports coaching context. Nodding focussed on the concepts of motivational displacement and engrossment. Engrossment refers to where the coach builds and maintains a caring relationship with the athlete. In motivational displacement, athlete-oriented coaching is preferred, based on prioritization of care. Applying Nodding's theory to the context of sports coaching, the role of

the coach can be compared to that of the parent, with the athlete taking the child's role in the care relationship (Purdy et al., 2016).

Cushion et al. (2019) also outlined ways in which coaches can create the required caring, pedagogical atmosphere that fulfills individual players' needs. They argued that this can be facilitated when coaches encourage ethical decision-making and compassionate behavior between athletes and competitors and towards the game itself. By adopting a care-centred ethical stance, coaches can support athletes in managing their personal health, performance, and psychological and social well-being. Purdy et al. (2016) argued that caring coaches recognise the athlete's individual needs and create opportunities for self-reflection. Interpersonal skills are needed where ethical and empathetic care underpins the coach's training philosophy. In the context of elite sport, a caring approach enables the coach to recognise their ethical obligation to balance desirable performance outcomes with the health and well-being of athletes. Coaches who combine ethical decision-making with practical wisdom tend to be more successful in maintaining the health of their athletes (Dohsten et al., 2020). The caring coach can build a supportive atmosphere that remains sensitive to athletes' holistic needs, encompassing long-term performance and personal development. Caring in coaching is fundamentally reliant on a coach's commitment towards athlete care. This supports high-quality and durable coach-athlete relationships based on empathetic and respectful communication, which is an observable behaviour in coaching practice.

A persistent ethical issue that exists at elite levels involves the perception that athlete performance can and should be treated as a commodity, the value of which can be enhanced (e.g., through training) and utilized instrumentally for specific purposes (e.g., competitive success; Dohsten et al., 2020). In this context, coaching may be focused on short-term goals and immediate competitive success with little or no consideration given to the athlete's longer term sporting career. The coach working from an ethical care perspective is likely to take a longer view in terms of the player's performance development (Dohsten et al., 2020). When an athlete's performance is viewed as a commodity and where an ethical coaching perspective is not embraced, the athlete runs the risk of exploitation. This could hinder their development and potentially compromise the sustainability of their long-term career. In the context of elite sport, the caring coach should take a position informed by ethical principles to act in the best interests of their athletes. When the coach models ethically informed behaviour, elite athletes may view them as a suitable role model who is trusted to treat them ethically while maximizing their sporting performance. Hence, the coach's role involves what Cassidy et al. (2016) described as a moral dimension with respect to their responsibilities for the individual athlete's long-term

development. Cushion et al. (2019) argued that such long-term ethical treatment by coaches, including open dialogue about players' health and well-being (Purdy et al., 2016), acts to safeguard the athlete from the pressures of commodification and the kinds of exploitation that lead to harmful outcomes such as player illness, injury, and overtraining. Cushion et al. determined that planning for athlete care was consistent with an athlete-oriented approach to coaching. In the context of elite sports, the coach is required to constantly evaluate the balance between performance pressures and the athlete's well-being. The coach's care ethics become essential in sustaining long-term athletic performance and maintaining the athlete's career longevity. Fry, Reid-Pinson, Iwasaki, and Thompson (2020) revealed that a coach's caring approach is a critical factor in improving elite sporting performance, enacted through a complex range of interrelated factors. They also argued that elite coaches should be sensitive to their athlete's needs, giving particular consideration to emotional, cultural, and social support issues.

Dohsten et al. (2020) argued that an approach to coaching that values such aspects as engagement in dialogue, empowerment, and the athlete's well-being has the potential for sustaining their long-term engagement in elite sport. Just as Van Puyenbroeck et al. (2018) found, upward communication from players to coaches—valuing the athlete voice—is required. This is particularly important in the context of intensely competitive sporting environments that are performance focused and characterised by risks associated with overtraining and selection pressures. Dohsten et al. conceptualised care in coaching in terms of the hegemonic (sport as commodity) and marginalized (sport as community) views of sport. In this context, *sport as commodity* suggests that sport is a product created for a consumer market in which athletic performance is one element of that commodity's production. In contrast, *sport as community* highlights the socially integrative and developmental aspects of sport participation, particularly for young people. Caring in coaching is represented as either an integrated or a peripheral consideration in hegemonic and marginal conceptualisations (Dohsten et al. 2020). Table 3 illustrates the relationship between care and hegemonic (sport as commodity) and marginal (sport as community) conceptualisations of sport.

Table 3

The Integration of Caring with Differing Conceptualisations of Sport

	Sport as commodity	Sport as community	Caring
Purpose of sport	Sport for market – emphasis on international medals; outcome orientation reflects a “market” and “marketability”	Sport for impact process-orientation; emphasis on social relevance; positive feedback from those who benefit from sport	Caring coaching practice Creating a pedagogical climate; emphasises the well-being and ethical development of athletes
View of athletes	Efficiency Athletes are seen in mechanistic terms; body-as-machine and economic resource; tight timeframes; cause-effect relationship between training and performance gain	Authenticity Athletes are accepted as intelligent and capable citizens who have a desire to engage in meaningful learning and overall development; involvement is intrinsically motivated	Cared-for athletes as the individuals cared for and the learners
Coach-athlete relationship	Instrumentality Coaching as transfer of predetermined and fixed goals; one coach authority; coach is knower – athlete is learner	Emancipation Athlete-centred coaching; high degrees of self-determination and transformation; room for co-creation and emergent objectives	Engrossment Coach establishes caring relationship, motivational displacement; Athlete-centred coaching; Prioritises the care process over results; Confirmation, affirming, and encouraging the best in others; Dialogue, talking, sharing, listening, and responding
Purpose of training	Focus on continuous growth; Purpose of training is athletic progress and normative targets; all aspects of life are planned in the pursuit of performance enhancement	Focus on dynamic qualities; Sporting institutions invest in athletes’ athletic/physical and personal growth and communal relations	Focus on ethical ideal modelling; Demonstration of caring, coaching the whole person; Practice athletes experience caring practice
Epistemological orientation	Empirical rationalism Scientific knowledge represents truth;	Socio-constructivism Co-creation of knowledge, pluralist	Social-constructivism Co-creation of

	biomedical knowledge is key; control and elimination of “distractions” is important; Scientific and technical knowledge is used to predict, control, and intervene in athletic training; trust in science; particular technical knowledge overrides other ways of knowing and doing	community and working ethics; uncertainty and unpredictability is a given; Phronesis; Ethically practical knowledge; context-specific value judgements; no “one-size-fits-all” philosophy	knowledge; Feminism – ethics educating role; Ethics of care; Relationship-based theory; the ethics of care act is situated, context-specific and determined in the unique relationship
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In Table 2, Dohsten et al. (2020) illustrated that coaches can be focussed on the decisions which reflect a commitment to that athlete’s long-term sustainability within their sport which, as mentioned earlier, reflects a holistic approach to coaching. In these cases, moral dilemmas arising from tensions between competitive demands and athlete well-being are resolved in favour of the athlete’s long-term interests. Daniels and Cronin (2019) asserted that care has become a significant element in the player-coach relationship, acknowledging that coaches owe athletes a duty of care. The minimal standardised approach to care is emphasised in risk assessment and safety, and the principle of doing no harm. Fry et al. (2020) argued that in the coaching context, caring and not harming are different orientations which inform coaching philosophy and behaviour, reflecting the polarised views of sport as commodity and sport as community depicted above. The sport as commodity view of athletes as “machines” and “economic resources” means they can be dispensed with when they no longer perform. The caring relationship, or sport as community, is essential for the development of trust in the processes applied to help athletes realise their potential in lifelong term. In this study, what sport as community, or caring for athletes, might look like in Iraq will be revealed in the attention paid to coaching sessions and interviews with coaches and players. It potentially has something quite different to offer in terms of the literature’s prevalent understandings of caring coaching, as sport endures under war-like conditions.

2.5.2 Gender Preferences for Coaching Approaches

As the participants of this study are drawn from two men’s teams and two women’s teams, one each from two clubs, it is possible that there are preferences for coaching approaches dependent upon gender. There is research that has identified a correlation between the athlete’s

gender and their preferences for coaching approaches (Harkness, 2012; Harkness & Hongsermeier, 2015; Philippe, Sagar, Hauw, & Gerber, 2016). Harkness and Hongsermeier (2015) noted that such gender preferences relate to player-coach relationships and particular styles of coaching. Harkness (2012) compared athletes' views on coaching styles and behaviours using a sample of 80 males and 60 females. The results revealed that female athletes preferred more *democratic coaching* and *social support* behaviours, while males preferred *autocratic* training approaches. In a later paper, Harkness and Hongsermeier (2015) confirmed the original findings of Harkness (2012), indicating that males preferred an instructive and autocratic coaching style while females tended to prefer more democratic coaching styles. These differences by gender in preferences for coaching styles were also supported by Siekanska, Blecharz, and Wojtowicz (2013); however, these researchers also found that there were *more similarities than differences* between female and male preferences for coaching styles and behaviours. In this study, all coaches of the women's teams are male. Given the tendency of coaches to reproduce the coaching approaches with which they are familiar (from their elite playing days), it will be important to ask and compare what are the influences upon coaching between the men's and women's teams.

Hall and Gray (2017) found that disengaged players preferred inquiry approaches to coaching with opportunities to ask questions and confer; this was consistent for males and females. In a related study with one elite female rugby union coach and players over a season, Hall, Gray, and Sproule (2016) found that the female players and female coach demonstrated preferences for physical fitness and conditioning activities (55.8%) and variable levels of questioning, and that the coach conferred with associates as much as 23.3% of total coaching time. In the context of Iraq, a study by Hamdoon, Osman, and Mohiuddin (2019) found that the female university athletes participating in the study preferred more social and interpersonal security support through friendships from their sport experience, including coaching. Ibrahim and Gwari (2011) also indicated that community-level female volleyball players often prefer higher levels of *positive verbal feedback*, *social support*, and *democratic coaching styles*. However, in community-level basketball, Ibrahim and Gwari (2011) found that male players preferred higher levels of situational and tactical discussion as well as social support from their coaches.

In summary, sports coaching is a domain that may replicate social roles and gender stereotypes found in society (Connell, 2005), such as the "naturalness" of having male coaches, in both male and female sport. Interestingly, Afonshin, Rozhentsov, and Lema (2016) recommended that coaches, while providing training to different athletes, needed to focus on

developing *participative leadership styles* to increase the success of coaching programs. Given the social and cultural status of women in Iraqi society, this study may shed light on whether there is a gender-related difference between elite volleyball athletes' coaching style preferences and the potential implication of this for the development of elite coaching in Iraq.

2.5.3 The Importance of Coaching Philosophy

Coaches' experience, professional knowledge, and the coaching approaches they employ are brought into existence by their coaching philosophy. Cushion and Partington (2016) asserted that there is much descriptive literature about coaching philosophy that does not necessarily define it. Cassidy et al. (2016) defined a coaching philosophy as a set of principles that guide an individual's practice, whilst Kidman and Hanrahan (2011) stated that it includes the coaches' values and principles. Juariyah and Adi (2017) defined coaching philosophy as the principles, values, and beliefs that provide guidance about characteristics and behaviour related to the individual's coaching practice. Martens (2012) offered that having a coaching philosophy is to know the condition of one's own mind. A coach's philosophy explicitly or implicitly frames how coaches conceptualise and conduct their coaching roles.

The coaches' beliefs and values underpinning a coaching philosophy ensure a consistent approach to coaching and the ability to prioritise relevant areas to achieve desirable outcomes. Cushion and Partington (2016) noted that coaches often take a "common-sense", practice-driven, unreflexive approach to their work, without actually dwelling upon the beliefs and values underpinning them. A well-defined and *understood* coaching philosophy facilitates a consistency to actions and effective judgment that underpins coaching decisions (Cassidy et al., 2016; Kidman & Hanrahan, 2011), which creates trust and respect among athletes and leads to high-quality coach-athlete relations. Coaching is a challenging activity characterised by complex and sometimes difficult decisions plus ethical dilemmas to be navigated (Martens, 2012). Having a well-developed coaching philosophy guides a coach in decision-making and provides direction, purpose, and support when faced with competing external pressures.

Burnie et al. (2018) argued that a sound coaching philosophy is the main ingredient of coaching and essential for providing athletes with a positive experience of sport. At the heart of any coaching philosophy is the relative importance of winning, fun, and personal development. Coaches are the interpreters and providers of sporting experience. The coach's philosophical approach is essential for developing a positive climate. The process of developing a coaching philosophy is highly complex and continuously evolving. Coaches are required to integrate and reflect on their coaching experience, their sports knowledge, and the

training demand relative to the level of competition. Coaches develop a philosophy in sport-specific contexts which impacts on the individual player's experience and performance. Cushion and Partington (2016) suggested that key components of a coaching philosophy include that coaches should: be self-aware, be able to discuss well-defined issues, treat athletes with respect, and identify an individual athlete's strengths and weaknesses, while remaining focused, goal oriented, supportive, and enthusiastic.

This means that a coaching philosophy defines how coaches conduct themselves and relate to their players. Player perceptions of how their coach relates to them and treats them (i.e., perceptions of fairness and equity) have also been found to translate into game performance. De Backer et al. (2018) evaluated Belgian athletes' perceptions of justice relating to coaching style and the circumstances of game results; their research set out to demonstrate the relationship between athletes' perceptions of their coaches' approaches and behaviours and its effect on their performance. This study adopted a longitudinal self-report questionnaire design for the examination of fluctuation of game results related to athletes' perceived justice of their handball coaches and elite volleyball coaches. The research method comprised of a questionnaire deployed for 6 consecutive weeks for the collection of data from 39 male handball players and 57 female volleyball players. The results showed that there was approximately 49% variance in perceived justice over the 6week period. In addition, the provision of decision-making and support by coaches was a positive predictor of athletes' perceived justice of their coaches. The study concluded that perceived justice varied from game to game, whereas consistent coaching behaviour was required to prevail over the negative game results.

Yi, Wah, and Polman (2018) also evaluated the influence of the behaviour of coaches on elite players of volleyball with respect to performance satisfaction and motivational climate in Malaysia. Like Loffing et al. (2015) and Van Puyenbroeck et al. (2018), Yi et al. defined motivational climate as being *concerned with learning* new sports skills and tactics. Positive coaching behaviours were proposed as being helpful for enhancement of athlete satisfaction and motivation, whereas negative coaching behaviours were suggested to lead to the opposite. The large research sample size of 328 elite players comprised 191 female and 137 male players. Three questionnaire surveys were used, including Athlete Satisfaction Questionnaire (ASQ), Coaching Behaviour Questionnaire (CBQ), and Perceived Motivational Climate in Sport Questionnaire (PMCSQ-2). These questionnaires are used to assess perceptions of athletes in relation to behaviour of coaches, providing a measure of satisfaction with coaching of elite players. The results indicated a positive relation between performance satisfaction and

motivational climate. For ASQ, team integration was found to be essential for influencing the satisfaction of athletes, suggesting that coaching behaviours that support team cohesion and team building are important. The mean score of CBQ found that coach support of players is essential, in direct contrast to negative coaching behaviours such as *sustained criticism and/or indifference*. For PMCSQ-2, a high mean value was found for climate task as compared to climate of ego-involved. The climate of ego-involving is created when performance outcomes are extrinsically rewarded by coaches. The motivational climate of task-involving is built when efforts and improvement are not only rewarded by coaches but intrinsically valued by players. Hence, Yi et al.'s study of Malaysian volleyball players argued, like Burnie et al. (2018) and de Backer et al.'s (2018) studies, that coaching behaviours must be considered as the basis for enhancement of athlete performance, underpinned by the way in which coaches build and support the motivational climate and players' ultimate performance satisfaction. These studies assist to inform the research design of this investigation in that coaching behaviours, such as criticism and indifference, are observable and can be documented through observation and interview accounts.

Pangastuti and Widi's (2017) study is particularly useful for this investigation, with similar participants and sample size of coach interviewees. They evaluated the coaching philosophies of national volleyball coaches in Indonesia ($n = 7$) who were former or current national coaches. Using a qualitative research design, they collected in-depth interview data along with documentation and observation artifacts. The results indicated that the philosophy of volleyball coaches in Indonesia conformed to the philosophy and objectives of international competitive volleyball and the enhancement of quality of life of players. Their philosophies valued *hard training* because they believed that competition is easier and more successful when players achieve their *maximum level of physical performance*. This study attempted to show connections between *coaching philosophy and optimal player fitness* as an integral part of elite coaching. Similarly, Weldon et al. (2021) evaluated the conditioning and strength practices from the viewpoint of players and coaches of volleyball. A quantitative research method was applied in this study based on an anonymous survey distributed to players and coaches registered with the Hong Kong Volleyball Association. The total sample size comprised of 60, where 30 of these were coaches included for being qualified coaches of elite players and currently engaged in resistance training programs. They fell in the age range of 34.5 ± 7.83 , with an average of 20 years of coaching experience. The other 30 participants were players from the same association, included because they were currently elite players engaged in resistance training. They fell into the age range of 22.03 ± 4.4 , with average playing experience

of about 10 years. The questionnaire comprised of six sections that included informed consent, background information, qualification, views on strength and conditioning, preferences and selection of exercise, and problems and improvement. A frequency analysis method was applied for reporting of responses for closed questions and, for the open-ended questions, a thematic analysis was conducted. The results confirmed that *strength and condition* are considered by coaches and players as *essential athlete attributes for volleyball proficiency*, injury prevention, and overall physical fitness. Nonetheless, an absence of specific expertise in strength and conditioning was identified in the survey results, indicating a gap in coaching practices. In addition, the results identified that achievement of player strength and conditioning is affected by the *absence of facilities and equipment, and sufficient time*.

The information obtained from Weldon et al.'s (2021) study is useful for this research investigation as it points to the stakeholders of coaching practices that develop strength and conditioning, such as coaches, sports associations, and players themselves. It also highlights that the socio-economic training context in which players find themselves can adversely impact upon their ability to develop elite levels of strength and conditioning. Similarly, Francis and Jones (2014) argued that a coach's philosophy may assist in improving overall athleticism and reduce the risk of injury, allowing young athletes to effectively develop more advanced technical and tactical skills. This can be achieved by providing progressive training techniques which increase the athlete's strength, speed, and endurance (Marques, González-Badillo, & Kluka, 2006; Marques, Van Den Tillaar, Vescovi, & González-Badillo, 2008).

It has been argued that the coach possesses great, if not the greatest, capacity to affect the player's quality of experience in a sport (Hansen et al., 2003). This suggests that a holistic approach to coaching may facilitate player experience, developing in them an understanding of how the coach's philosophical stance impacts on their decisions and their interactions with individual players. As the coach's philosophy is based on their values, principles, and practices, it impacts on their functioning and preferred method. There is no one typical coaching philosophy and no one right way to coach (Weinberg & Gould, 2014), as a coach's work influences athletes in different ways. Bennie and O'Connor (2010) evaluated the role and importance of coaching philosophies from the perception of sports coaches of rugby union, rugby league, and cricket in Australia. Results showed that the philosophy of coaches was connected to their perceived effectiveness. In professional settings, coaches can develop different programs to provide assistance to players for the acquisition of off- and on-the-field skills. Bennie and O'Connor also emphasized the importance of player improvement and coaching as a learning approach. These components of a philosophy encapsulate the humanistic

approach to coaching that emphasizes total individual development rather than winning at all costs (Bennie & O'Connor, 2010).

Bean, Kramers, and Harlow (2020) also explored “off the field” knowledge and life skill transfer among volleyball and hockey youth players. Sports is considered as a main vehicle for promotion of positive life experiences for youth, with an assumption that sport enables transferability to and adaptability of life skills. The sample size comprised of 47 youth athletes across 16 teams from both sports, accomplished via one semi-structured interview in the last week of their sport season. Various theories about life skill transfer (cf. Jørgensen, Lemyre, & Holt, 2019) were used as a framework for the subsequent thematic analysis. The results showed that youth can develop different skills such as independence and emotional regulation by means of participation of sport. The results also showed that contextual differences and the age of athletes influence the transfer of sports skills to life. This study demonstrated that coaches can often be motivated not only by competitive success but also by the futures they can assist players to build for themselves through transferable skills. Such beliefs are consistent with holistic and humanistic coaching philosophies (Kidman & Hanrahan, 2011) and the results of Bean et al.'s (2020) study are highly relevant to this investigation of coaching philosophies, approaches, and practices in elite volleyball in Iraq.

A coaching philosophy is considered essential to form a culture of trust within teams, which is very important to team success. In return, it allows integrating a holistic approach to coaching (Vierimaa, Erickson, Côté, & Gilbert, 2012). Physical education research (Cushion & Partington, 2016) has confirmed that a coaching philosophy provides a framework of expectations regarding the coach's priorities and values, in which specific goals for each athlete must be achieved. When the coach shares their values and daily life, they are able to establish credibility with athletes, encouraging and supporting success at all competitive levels (Baghurst & Mwavita, 2014). Thus, a coaching philosophy underlies the relationship-building process between coaches and their players (Olson, 2014). Olson's (2014) study identified three primary types of coaching behaviour: taking care with relationship building, effective communication, and transparent decision-making behaviour. Juariyah and Adi (2017) focused on an additional three components, including coaches' understanding of athletes, the athletes' personalities, and their view of themselves in terms of personal and professional competence. However, because there is no “one-size-fits-all” philosophy, coaching philosophies are often changed and altered over time to reflect different circumstances. Hence, a coach's philosophy is also shaped by the experiences gained through working with different players in various

contexts (Brackett et al., 2009) and their personal values, which are easier to apply and “live by” on a daily basis (Roy, Jakubikova, Guthrie, & Batista, 2009).

This review of the literature concerning coaching philosophy shows that it underscores the complete remit of a coach’s professional practice. Player learning, motivation, achievement, and performance, as well as future goals and transferable life skills, are comprehensively linked to the coach’s philosophy and coaching approaches. Coach knowledge, beliefs about models of teaching, and care for players are translated into coaching practices, which are further contextualised by the environment(s) in which they operate. It is therefore necessary to bring to the investigation an analytical lens that assists with understanding practices.

2.6 A Theoretical Framework for Analysing Coaching Practices

The theoretical framework selected for use in this study has resulted from a critical review of literature and articulation of the research problem. A theoretical framework which assists with coding and development of themes as units of analysis must have coherence with the extant literature, the problem itself, and the methodology and methods used to investigate it. This thesis draws upon constructivist ideas about research (Grant & Osanloo, 2014), whereby active construction of new knowledge is established on prior experiences. Constructivism contends that reality is constructed in the mind of the person, drawing on philosophical and psychological perspectives that individuals form (Yilmaz, 2008). Charmaz (2006) contended that the constructivist inquiry approach explains research participants’ meanings, which are in themselves interpretations, then producing theories from these interpretations. In this sense, constructivism discards the notion of a single reality where learning is also perceived as the interpretative and active procedure.

It has been revealed in the literature that sites of sports coaching can be considered communities of practice, following Lave and Wenger (1991). More recent research into site-based learning argues that these are actually communities of *practices* with various semantic, material, and social arrangements (Kemmis et al., 2014). The following section introduces the TPA, which presents the notion of arrangements and prefigurings that enable and constrain coaching approaches and practices in elite volleyball.

2.6.1 The Theory of Practice Architectures (TPA)

This study will employ TPA (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008) as an ontological approach to data analysis and exploration of findings. Stephen Kemmis and Peter Grootenboer

first published their theory of practice architectures in 2008, arising out of a broader collaboration with Scandinavian, Australian, South American, and English researchers (Kemmis & Mahon, 2017). These scholars were well versed in practical epistemology (see, for example, Wickman, 2004), practice theory (Schatzki, 2010; Schatzki & Schatzki, 1996), criticality (Carr & Kemmis, 1996), and action research (Kemmis & McTaggart, 1988). Kemmis and Mahon (2017) noted that TPA has been a long time in development. Kemmis recalled the evolution of his ideas about arrangements or pre-configurations upon learning as follows:

The initial form of the theory ... came to me when I was in a train from London to Norwich, after a day in London ... [in 1977]. I was musing about how people learn things as the train passed the town of Diss, where there was a view of the water (a mere or lake on the River Waveney), and a beach with little boats drawn up on it. "How do people learn to row a dinghy?" I wondered. And then I began to see how the dinghy plays an active role in "teaching" someone to row it. When you put the oars in the rowlocks, you discover you can't sit facing in the direction you want to go. The dinghy "teaches" you to sit in the middle of the boat with your back to the bow. And when you try to pull the oars, the oars "teach" you to hold them with the concave face backward, so you can get a purchase on the water, and so the oars don't slip out of the water. (Kemmis & Mahon, 2017, p. 221)

In the contemporary understanding of practice architectures, the idea that practices (such as rowing) shape and are shaped by arrangements (such as the row locks) is central. In recounting the genealogy of the theory, Kemmis recalled that David Hamilton's (1989) work, *Towards a Theory of Schooling*, crystallized the identification of the three dominant arrangements of practice: cultural, economic, and social:

(Hamilton) presents historical "case studies" of schooling at several moments of major transformation in schools and schooling describe (ing) major **cultural, economic, and social** trends of the period to show how new forms of schools and schooling **arose from** and, in turn, **contributed to**, contemporary historical circumstances. (Kemmis & Mahon, 2017, p. 225, **emphasis added**)

In this genealogy of the theory, Kemmis establishes that social-political, material-economic, and cultural-discursive arrangements arise from, and contribute to, individual and social action. Kemmis and Grootenboer (2008) suggested that this is an ontological theory, making sense of what people do, in order to understand the tension between the individual and the social, all the while indicating that a strong and powerful interrelation is present (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Practice, practitioners, and the theory of practice architectures, from Kemmis, Wilkinson, Edwards-Groves, Hardy, Grootenboer, & Bristol (2014). Reproduced with permission from Peter Grootenboer.

Kemmis et al. (2014) continued to refine TPA, and its accompanying visual semiotics, from its first appearance in Kemmis and Grootenboer's (2008) chapter, as depicted in Figure 7. They argued that on the side of the individual (the left-hand side above), the practitioner exhibits practices which are mutually constituted in action via typical sayings (cognitive), doings (psychomotor), and relatings (affective). The practitioner is initiated into these forms of understanding through semantic spaces of realised, shared language, fostering individual and collective self-expression on the side of the social (the right-hand side above). The cultural-discursive, socio-political, and material-economic conditions serve as prefigurings or architects

of specific practices, giving rise to the name of “practice architectures”. These prefiguring conditions can enable or constrain practices, such as what people are allowed to learn, how people relate to each other, and the conditions under which they work or perform.

The theory is further underscored by the notion of “praxis”, which Kemmis et al. (2014) defined as “a result of doing something—not in a pre-specific, rule-following kind of way, but action whose consequences are more or less indeterminate, only evaluated in light of the consequence—in terms of how things actually turn out” (p. 26). In arriving at their definition of “practice”, Kemmis et al. focused on the relationship between the practitioners, which could include coaches, and a particular practice, such as coaching volleyball, as being a relationship in which practitioners speak a language which is characteristic of that practice (*typical sayings*), engage in activities of the practice in typical ways (*typical doings*), and enter relationships with other people and objects characteristic of the practice (*typical relatings*). Whatman (2016, p. 51) noted that this can also mean that coaches and players have pre-existing relationships with equipment, training layouts, and routines. How they use or engage with these practices and objects becomes deeply entrenched habits particular to that sport. They can be both enabling (encouraging the practice) and constraining (preventing it from evolving).

Understanding the three kinds of arrangements in practice architectures assists with identifying these arrangements in the context of elite volleyball coaching practice:

- *Cultural-discursive arrangements* (in the semantic space) refers to the knowledge and language, such as coaches’ “tacit knowledge” (Nash & Collins, 2006). Such knowledge can both enable and constrain coaching practice. This might include relevant sports-specific knowledge or the culturally acceptable ways of describing and justifying training practices.
- *Material-economic arrangements* (in the medium or activity and work) include how the practice unfolds in “physical space-time” (Schiatski, 2010). These might include the physical and time resources that make the activity possible (weekly schedule and time of training sessions), and constrain what activities can be carried out—physical set-ups, location (availability of venues, ability for players to partake in the activity).
- *Socio-political arrangements* (power and solidarity in the social space) include the resources that mark the relationships between people and objects in the practice (organisational functions, rules and roles, and agreements about what to do). They include who organises the competition, who is a “knower”, who

can speak, who must remain silent, and who must be satisfied with all of the arrangements for the practice to continue (Kemmis et al., 2014, p. 27).

Research into coaching practice often focuses on coaches as products of a system. Coaches are influenced by their experiences, often as elite players. These experiences orientate coaches towards certain types of coaching approaches whilst inhibiting others (Cushion et al., 2019). Such practice is embedded in contexts supported by knowledge, beliefs, and assumptions about the “what” of coaching which is also entwined with the coach’s professional identity. For example, Stoszowski and Collins (2016) argued that novice coaches suffer from a “halo” effect: whatever more experienced or elite coaches do and say is perceived to be better than the novice’s opinions and actions. This results in unchanging practices with successive coaches. These orientations are also influenced by the cultural context in which coaching practice is embedded (Barker-Ruchti, Barker, Rynne, & Lee, 2016).

The sport coaching pedagogy research published thus far which employs TPA in their analyses have focused upon building communities of practice in unique sites and learning contexts. Studies might seek to understand innovation and/or lack of change in individual communities of physical education practice over time, such as Goodyear and Casey’s (2015) study in one comprehensive secondary school in the United Kingdom. Goodyear, Casey, and Kirk’s (2016) extended conceptual discussion of the earlier empirical example suggested that TPA could assist with program reform, again over time. The in situ, high-performance coach education, termed as “knowing-in-practice”, in Phelan and Griffiths’ (2019, p. 103) study also focused on one site. Goodyear et al. (2016) highlighted that TPA originated in Australia with Kemmis and colleagues (2014) and has not been widely used around the world, with the exception of Scandinavia. Studies like Whatman’s (2016) are also an exception, involving coaches from multiple international sites, brought together in wholly online coaching courses at a specific point in time. One of the strengths of the idea of communities of practice is the socialisation of the participants. Lave and Wenger (1991, p. 49) explained learning as increasing participation in communities of practice, which involves “the whole person acting in the world”. Learning via coaching then implies “not only a relation to specific *activities*, but a relation to *social communities*—it implies becoming a full participant, a member, a kind of person” (ibid, p. 53). This study will apply the ontological TPA into two elite sport coaching settings—two clubs, with four teams—adding to an embryonic field applying the theory to elite coaching practices. Using TPA to analyse practices between two coaching sites, and between

teams, has the potential to offer reflexive conclusions about its utility in cross-site comparisons and in a part of the world that has not previously featured in the research.

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter has reviewed the literature relevant to the study at hand. It began by defining sport pedagogy and supports for player motivation, self-efficacy, and self-esteem. It then turned to the contribution of various forms of knowledge required to coach, drawing together the complex interrelationship between professional knowledge (coach pedagogical knowledge and sport science knowledge) and other knowledge required to build critical relationships in the coaching domain (interpersonal knowledge) and to drive continuous improvement in coaching practice (intrapersonal knowledge).

Coaching approaches typical in team sports or games teaching were critiqued. This included the idea of a “traditional” linear approach to teaching games, which progresses from introduction through warm up, skills, drills, and game. An approach to teaching games which is novel to Iraq is that of TGfU, a cyclical way of increasing player learning and technical and tactical knowledge. The TGfU approach invites player input via coaches asking questions at key intervals in the cycle, which could or should translate to observable behaviours in coaching practice in elite volleyball clubs.

Research focusing on humanistic and holistic coaching was critiqued, establishing the importance of the player-coach relationship. This was followed by an exploration of the literature on care in coaching, dealing with player preferences for coaching approaches. This literature revealed some differences in preference for coaching approaches based on differences in sport played, and by gender. One of the aims of this study is to examine the coaching preferences of males and females in elite volleyball in Iraq through interviews and observations of coaching approaches for male and female players. To date, no study in an Arabic speaking country has investigated player preferences relating to coaching style in any sport, including volleyball, so this study will be the first to do so.

The chapter then turned to the importance of coaches having and enacting a coaching philosophy, where the literature suggests that coach behaviour can positively influence the learning, motivation, achievement, and performance of young athletes and inspire them in their lives outside of sport. Such behaviours include providing quality instruction, listening to athletes, offering feedback, monitoring learning, and motivating athletes to achieve their potential. No studies in Iraq have been conducted that focus on coaching approaches and practices in Iraq because research has tended to centre on the players. This study will address

a significant gap in the existing field, particularly into humanistic coaching approaches and what both coaches and players value in coaching.

Finally, this chapter presented the TPA that has been adopted as the theoretical framework for this study. This theory provided the framework for data analysis presented in Chapters 4 and 5 and its interpretation in the Discussion in Chapter 6. This study draws on the abovementioned dimensions of coaching to examine the research problem of the perceptions of coaching of elite volleyball players and their coaches in Iraq, and the approaches and practices of coaches. It is expected that this study's results will be used to improve sport experiences and sport programs in Iraq by improving the quality of volleyball coaching through evidenced-informed approaches. The following chapter details the methodology and research design adopted for this thesis.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises the study's research design, including epistemology, theoretical perspective, methodology, and methods of data collection and analysis. It describes the unique research approaches that were essential for the successful completion of an international study that was conducted remotely because of armed conflict with ISIS occurring in the study's location. The chapter is presented in 10 sub-sections. Section 3.2 discusses research design including research philosophy and beliefs, ontology and epistemology. Section 3.3 overviews the research design, including quantitative and qualitative approaches highlighting their strengths and limitations. This section also justifies the case study approach incorporating the mixed methods sequential explanatory approach adopted. Section 3.4 describes the research setting of two volleyball clubs in northern Iraq and details the procedures used for recruiting participants for the study. Section 3.5 describes my insider-researcher status as a volleyball coach and university lecturer in Iraq, as an extension to understanding the research setting and research design. Section 3.6. provides detail about the study's participants. Section 3.7 describes the data collection phases and the relationships between those phases according to the study's mixed methods design. It further explains the use of documentary evidence and describes the data collection phases and instruments used during each phase including: 1) Physical Self-Perception Profile, 2) Video- and audio-recordings of coaching sessions and 3) semi-structured interviews. Section 3.8 discusses the procedures used to analyse the three data sets generated for the study. It overviews the techniques used to analyse the various types of data including statistical procedures in the case of the PSPP data, video observational analysis and notational analysis for video-recordings of coaching sessions and Thematic analysis in the case of the semi-structured interviews. Section 3.9 discusses ethical considerations for conducting the study and 3.10 concludes the chapter with a brief summary.

3.2 Research Paradigms

A research paradigm describes a cluster of beliefs and dictates what should be studied, how research should be done and how the results should be interpreted (Bryman, 2008, p.696).

Within educational research, scientific and interpretivist views co-exist to solve social science problems (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018, p. 8). These views have different interpretations of ontological, epistemological and methodological practices. The *scientific view* “is concerned with discovering natural and universal laws regulating and determining individual and social behaviour” whilst the *interpretivist view* attempts to “describe and explain human behaviour, emphasizes how people differ from inanimate natural phenomena and, indeed, from each other” (Cohen et al., 2018, p. 8). These completing views, and their attendant differences in research approaches, stem from different beliefs about social realities, the nature of knowledge and how one can come to know. The following sections give an overview of ontology and epistemology, to explain the paradigmatic view taken in exploring the research.

3.2.1 Ontology

Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) stated that ontology informs theoretical aspects selected and what is meant by knowledge. A scientific view would argue that there is such a thing as an objective reality which exists independent of the individual and comprises causally interacting elements which are available for observation (Cohen et al, 2018, p.8). The interpretivist view encompassing relativism theories accept that individuals hold different opinions about the world. It reveals the diverse ways of knowing and thinking. It is considered as essential point as it enables the opinion of individuals to evolve with their engagement between players and professional coaches in Iraq. An interpretivist ontological view is feasible for investigation of the perceptions of coaches and players and valued coaching approaches and practices of Iraqi volleyball players. A relative ontology is based on the assumption that a subjective reconstruction of the reality of the volleyball players and coaches can be developed (Ivankova et al., 2006). For this investigation into coach and player perceptions of effective coaching, based on a case study of elite volleyball in Iraq, it can be said that a pragmatist philosophy underpins the research problem due to the mixed method design. It emphasizes attention on any specific situation and utilizes different pluralist approaches for critiquing situational knowledge. It also sets aside the argumentative concerns of reality and truth and accepts both positivist and interpretivist realities for solving practical real-world problem (Ivankova et al, 2006).

3.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology entails the framework for determination of deployment of research by our understandings of the nature of knowledge. The main epistemological perspectives comprise of objectivism, constructionism and subjectivism. Objectivism takes the view that

existence of reality is independent from conscious thought (Philpot & Smith, 2011). Objectivity 'exists' in real life and research undertaken with this view is said to explore an already prevailing 'truth'. Constructivism, on the other hand, takes the view that meaning and truth do not 'exist' in the real world in isolation from conscious thought or individual interactions and meaning-making. Subjectivism is aligned more closely with constructivism and revealed that knowledge meaning should not be perceived as the product of social interaction rather it involves the imposition of knowledge upon subjects (Creswell, 2013). The research project, with a pragmatist philosophy adopts a design that can incorporate qualitative and quantitative research approaches drawing from the concepts of interpretivism/constructivism and positivism/objectivism. The study leans more towards the interpretivism/constructivism paradigm as it upholds the notion of there being constructed and multiple realities of players and coaches and is based on inductive reasoning. The present research intends to make sense out of perception of athletes and coaches and provide the realization of complex phenomenon of social coaching. An interpretive research paradigm intends to uncover and explore values, meaning and rationalization of evolving concepts. This approach can provide the enriched insights in natural context for execution of professional coaching.

3.3 Research Design

In seeking to understand coach and player perceptions of coaching in elite volleyball in Iraq, the three focused research questions were:

1. What are the coaching philosophies that inform volleyball coaching approaches in Iraq?
2. What coaching approaches do the coaches and players value?
3. How and to what extent do coaching practices align with valued coaching approaches of men and women players of volleyball?

This research project explores a single case study using a mixed methods sequential explanatory approach, informed substantially from a pragmatic, interpretive paradigm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005; Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018). This approach enabled the researcher to gather perceptions, views and interpretations of experiences directly from coaches and players in order to understand the research problem. The researcher was able to draw on a range of research methods, quantitative and qualitative, within the mixed methods approach that were suitable for investigating the Iraqi team's views about effective volleyball coaching practices

(cf. Creswell & Poth, 2016). A pragmatic perspective underpinned the research effort, given that the study involved direct interaction with coaches and team players to examine a particular problem in practice (i.e., coaching). Clark, Creswell, Green and Shope (2008) stated that a pragmatic philosophical perspective is appropriate when dealing with issues of practice or where the study is concerned with practical issues or causes, reasons, and effects. It is concerned with linking theory and practice to inform future intelligent practice (Glasgow, 2013).

In the study to hand, the collection of data from players, coaches, and assistant coaches placed specific challenges on the researcher as alluded to in Chapter 1. This research used a mixed methods sequential explanatory qualitative design, explained in further detail in subsequent sections, to address the study's research questions (Maxwell, 2012) using a variety of data collection methods, including print documents, the PSPP video- and audio-recorded coaching sessions, and finally, semi-structured interviews, each data set was analysed separately using appropriate methods, detailed below, with a synthesis of findings reported in Chapter 7.

3.3.1 Quantitative Approaches to Research

Researchers have the option of choosing either qualitative, quantitative or, as is the case for this study, a combination of the two approaches during different phases of the research process (Clark, Garrett, & Leslie-Pelecky 2010). Quantitative research describes the relationship between variables and describes trends. Additionally, the researcher defines the questions to be asked and either develops or uses pre-existing instruments to gather the data in the form of numbers (Clark et al., 2010).

According to Tracy (2019), quantitative research is useful for testing objective theories by examination of association among different variables and to describe trends. In turn, these variables can be measured with the help of instruments where numbered data can be examined with the help of different statistical procedures. It is also based on the assumption of deductively testing theories or hypotheses. Quantitative research has the advantage of allowing the researcher to gather data from a large sample of participants, and, given certain conditions relating to the sample selection, to make inferences relating to larger populations.

Ziakas and Boukas (2014) associate quantitative research with a positivist paradigm. This position asserts that quantitative research is able to provide a conclusive answer to research questions (Wallace, & Sheldon, 2015). When information is gathered and examined with respect to reputable and standardised methodology, then trustworthy results are obtained.

However, a main drawback is that it takes no account of the perceptions and thoughts of people regarding the examined topics. In recent times, quantitative investigations have been supported by sophisticated statistical software and computer packages capable of managing and analysing extremely large data sets. Statistical analysis enables researchers to explore casual and complex relationships to determine the nature of the associations or the degree of influence one variable might have on another. For this study, quantitative data was collected from 4 teams of volleyball players comprising one male and one female team from each of two university clubs located in norther Iraq using the Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) scale (Fox & Corbin, 1989).

3.3.2 Qualitative Approaches to Research

Qualitative research is an inquiry approach useful for exploring and understanding a central phenomenon (Seawright & Gerring, 2008). The approach is aimed at gaining a deep understanding of a specific phenomenon or the participants, rather than a description of a theory or event (Yin, 2011). In order to learn about a phenomenon, the researcher investigates the perceptions, opinions or behaviours of participants using images or words. These words or images are analysed to provide descriptions and/or to identify themes. From this data, the researcher explains the meaning of the information based on personal reflections and past research (Yin, 2015).

Qualitative research is particularly appropriate for understanding behaviours, attitude, and views of participants relating to particular events, and how these might be shaped by different social forces. Moreover, qualitative methods are highly flexible and can be adapted in response to changes in the research environment. Qualitative techniques can also be deployed with little cost and with a relatively small sample of participants. The research scope of qualitative research can be quite limited, which is less useful for generalising, but highly useful for understanding the specifics of a unique group, such as elite volleyball coaches (Walliman, 2015).

Qualitative methods used in the current study include semi-structured interviews conducted online with coaches and assistant coaches and a sample of players from each of the 4 teams participating in the study plus analysis of the observable behaviours of participants in the audio- and video recorded coaching session conducted with each of the 4 teams. The resulting analysis aims to provide a deep understanding of how coaches and players perceive various aspects of volleyball coaching programs in Iraq. These insights may benefit coaches,

players and, ultimately, volleyball coaching education programs and, potentially, other sports in Iraq.

3.3.3 Case Study

Case study research is one of the most commonly used forms of qualitative inquiry (Lichtman, 2012). Yin (2011) suggests that case studies describe the nature of the participants who are being studied and their context. Case studies also distinguish themselves from other research designs because the researcher must proceed via a process of discovery and interpretation throughout the study as opposed to testing a pre-stated hypothesis. Mays and Pope (2007) argued that case studies also outline a process for acquiring and explaining in-depth understandings of situation-specific meanings or phenomena. Baxter and Jack (2008) and Stake (2005) also asserted that the case study design has clear advantages in answering how and why questions.

Though other qualitative research methods exist, such as ethnography, grounded theory, narrative inquiry, and phenomenology (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018), the case study method was chosen for this research based on the richness and thickness of the data that was potentially available for the study (Creswell & Miller, 2000). Moreover, ethnography and phenomenology would have required more extensive periods of fieldwork which was not possible for this study. To be considered a case, the entity being examined could be as small as one individual, as large as an entire school, or include sporting teams (Philpot & Smith, 2011). One advantage of using a case study approach is that the research can be completed in a relatively short, defined time frame, which is bounded by what the researcher determines as relevant to the case. The eclectic nature of data collection in case study research makes it one of the most widely used forms of qualitative inquiry (Philpot & Smith, 2011).

Stake (1995, 2005) described three types of qualitative case studies: intrinsic, instrumental, and collective. The intrinsic case study refers to a case as being of primary interest to the researcher, because of the researcher's background and interests, and may not necessarily be used to further or improve the case or a certain phenomenon. The instrumental case study serves to provide knowledge or insight on the actual subject, issue, organization, or entity being studied (Stake, 2005). The collective case study refers to a case study which is conducted at one place, for example, a school, college, clinic, or sporting club. This case study also can be described as instrumental, because of its potential to better understand and improve the coaching context of elite Iraqi volleyball teams. It is also intrinsic in that the interest in the

topic, the access to the teams and the desire to investigate this issue originates from my positioning as a former volleyball coach in a similar setting.

As this research is based on perception of players and coaches related to coaching approaches and practice, it requires a methodological approach which supports a pragmatic, interpretivist view. The relevant research methodology deployed is the case study. Case study research is suitable because it can consider positivist data collection methods such as survey instruments whilst emphasizing interpretivist dimensions of phenomena, such as naturalistic observation. Case study is therefore known as a comprehensive design for reporting and analysis (Yin, 2011). Case study reveals the situation that is prevalent to numerical and subjective analysis by investigation of dynamic, complex and unfolding event interaction, in relation with humans and other distinctive factors that are unique to particular situations (Stake 2005). Case study can account for social-political, material-economic and cultural-discursive phenomena or “arrangements” found in practice sites (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008), such as volleyball clubs in Iraq. The case study method persuades the researcher to reveal meaningful and contextual attributes that are pertinent for the current under-examination of coach and player perceptions of coaching approaches and practices in elite volleyball in Iraq.

In addition, case study also engenders the holistic realization of different relationships and events of individuals, coaches and overall sports teams. The case study research is effective for assessment of knowledge of coach and their practical deployment of varied skills of coaching. The analysis of different elements of coaching generates improved clarity relating to differences and similarities across volleyball coaches and the two Iraqi clubs, including between men’s and women’s teams. Case study allows for the identification of significant events – letting the situation and participations speak for themselves.

This case study then comprises players and coaches as participants in the study and investigates their perceptions, beliefs, interactions, and other phenomena. The case study framework incorporating a mixed methods sequential explanatory approach detailed below, will focus on understanding how and why coaches make certain coaching decisions and explore players’ perceptions of those decisions. Understanding how and why decisions, actions and perceptions occur may provide valuable insights for future coaches' programs.

3.3.4 Sequential Explanatory Mixed Methods Approach

Poucher, Tamminen, Caron, and Sweet (2019) noted that that qualitative studies in sport psychology have changed over time in terms of the emphasis on statistics as evidence to an increasing emphasis on interviews and addressing epistemological assumptions. They noted,

drawing on Culver et al. (2012), that between 1990 and 1999, 18% of published studies used participant interviews, 25% of studies used descriptive statistics and 57% used a combination. By 2000 to 2009, these ratios had shift to 39.8% of articles used interviews, 10% used descriptive statistics and 52% used a combination (p.163). Mixed methods are mostly done in order to overcome the limitations of a single design of research (Creswell, 2013). Interpreted data is often of more value and is more effective where mixed methods are utilised. This allows a single question to be addressed at different levels. The sequential research approach was considered a natural methodological framework for this research.

Creswell and Garrett (2008) noted that program evaluators have effectively integrated quantitative and qualitative methods over time, which Poucher et al. (2019) study confirms. The first phase of the study involved the collection of quantitative data from Iraqi volleyball player participants using the PSPP scale. The second phase of the research used video observational analysis followed by semi-structured interviews with coaching staff and players. Often research work needs have mixed or multiple methods of collecting data, converting it to information and analysing it. A sequential explanatory approach comprises two parts relating to the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study (Ivankova, Creswell, & Stick, 2006). While there are a number of ways to conduct sequential mixed-methods research, the design selected for this study is as follows: a) quantitative data is first collected and analysed; b) this is followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative data; c) the results of the quantitative analysis are then explained utilising results of qualitative study (Creswell, 2013).

Conducting research using sequential explanatory approach involves many challenges and decisions that confront the researcher. Decisions must be made concerning tasks such as choosing the best quantitative and qualitative measures for the study and identifying how the quantitative data relates to qualitative data so that the sequential explanatory synthesis can be achieved. In mixed methods sequential explanatory research designs, there are three major phases relating to researcher decision making. The first relates to *priority* in that the researcher needs to determine whether quantitative or qualitative data collection and analysis need to be given more attention with respect to answering the research questions. The second relates to *implementation*, or the order in which quantitative or qualitative approaches should be implemented or whether these can be conducted simultaneously or in overlapping time-frames. This was a consideration for this study as there were three types of qualitative data collected - audio-visual, interviews and documents. The third phase is *integration* which refers to the combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis. This is a critical aspect of mixed methods

approaches whereby the results of quantitative and qualitative research are combined to create a synthesis of research findings (Ivankova et al., 2006).

According to Yanow and Schwartz-Shea, (2015), using mixed methods research is useful when developing in-depth research as it can lead to a more meaningful elucidation of the examined phenomena. Other benefits relate to the dynamic interplay between quantitative and qualitative elements of the research whereby the collection of qualitative data is informed by the findings of the study's quantitative elements study (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). Mixed methods in this study have been employed to overcome some of the potential limitations of conducting the project from a distance, to produce multiple data sets, allowing for interpretation and to build what Cohen et al. (2018) describes as trustworthiness of the findings. Procedures for establishing trustworthiness echoed those noted by Poucher et al. (2019) including peer review and debriefing with Arabic speaking colleagues in Australia and Jordan, member checking and reliability checks of the data by the supervision team and details about the researcher and their role in data collection, which is discussed shortly.

3.4 Research Setting

The sites for this research were two volleyball clubs hosting Advanced Level male and female volleyball teams in a large city centres in northern Iraq. Data collection for this research was initiated in July 2017 at the start of the pre-season phase of northern Iraq's volleyball season. The four volleyball teams each had one head and one assistant coach, all of whom held at least a Bachelor's degree in Physical Education from an Iraqi University. The coaches informed the researcher that volleyball training sessions were conducted in the afternoons to early evenings, after school hours, on three days per week (Monday, Wednesday and Friday). Each session lasted for one hour and thirty minutes. All the coaches and assistant coaches from each team participated in the study.

As I have been a University sport science academic and volleyball coach in Iraq, as well as an experienced player, I have an existing professional relationship with the coaches of the participating teams. This existing coaching relationships with Iraqi coaches and players facilitated access to the research sites. These established relationships and sports-specific knowledge also assisted in establishing trust with the coaching staff, participant recruitment and entry to the research sites. Whilst I was not the coach of any of the player participants, I knew of some of their families, or had coached a relative. As discussed in Chapter 2, armed conflict with ISIS militia was taking place at and around the research site, and my inability to return to Iraq for personal security reasons, meant that it was not possible to conduct fieldwork

in person. Accordingly, data collection for all phases of the study was managed remotely from Brisbane, Australia.

3.4.1 Insider Researcher Status

By profession, I am a lecturer in Sport Science at a university close to the research site. I coached a local women's volleyball team at the university and one of the clubs in this study. In order to enhance my understanding of coaching and acquire high quality knowledge, I applied to complete my doctorate overseas with the intention of returning to both my university position and my club with newly acquired insights. My long-term aim is to contribute effectively toward sports coaching, sport education and volleyball in Iraq.

War had a tremendous impact on both my PhD journey and Iraqi volleyball. Iraq has been a war-torn country for many years. The destruction of Mosul, my city of origin, was devastating. ISIS destroyed the entire city, ruined the infrastructure and pushed the community back decades. As ISIS moved towards Mosul, we learnt that they were killing everyone belonging to the education sector, and specifically targeting university scholars. My life was being threatened in my own homeland, in the city where I grew up. I decided it was time to leave and applied for a Government sponsored scholarship. Higher education scholarship support in Baghdad was still available, as ISIS was attacking the north of the country.

Acquiring English was another complicating factor in completing a doctorate in Australia. I discussed the situation with my supervisors, before I passed my IELTS test. Taking and passing the test alone was a struggle, as I began the process as a non-English speaking (or writing) Iraqi national. My supervisors were aware that I was likely to lose my life if I returned to Iraq while ISIS remained in control. Consequently, my supervisors have been extraordinary in their support. They helped me with English tutorials, with teaching me how to write and improve my writing, assisting me throughout this journey. My words cannot capture what my supervisors have done for me.

In preparing my PhD proposal, I was not entirely sure how to draw together my previous coaching experiences, my teaching areas and the theoretical knowledge gained in my Master's degree in sports science to create a focus for study which could fascinate me and potentially make a difference to coaching practice when I return to Iraq. We discussed what Iraqi volleyball was like and had many early conversations about coaching approaches and coach learning. I explained the current coaching practices in Iraq and the lack of access that coaches have to professional coaching knowledge, coaches tend to draw on their past experiences as players. There are few specific and professional programs to assist the volleyball

coaches, especially given the warring climate and Iraq's exclusion from many international sporting competitions. The basis of this thesis began to take shape in those conversations.

Being a university lecturer and a local volleyball coach meant I could contact coaches, players, and other club staff. Although there was no possibility of my returning to collect data in person, I contacted them and explained my research and asked for their support, participation and help with the data collection. I discussed the benefits of taking part in the study and how it could help them to improve the future of sports in Iraq. They agreed to help, so I applied for ethics to conduct my study remotely in an international setting. All of them agreed to help in collecting data for my study.

However, there were several issues to resolve in the study design. Despite being in Australia, I was still an "insider researcher" (Humphrey, 2012) and had to take some steps to manage conflict of interest or research biases. An inside researcher is one who has a familiarity, or shares characteristics, with the group participating in the study, through such things as ethnicity, culture, gender, employment, social networks and/or political links. An insider researcher can be members of an organisation and will have deep knowledge of its workings (Humphrey, 2012). These reasons make an insider perspective useful rather than problematic. Substantive knowledge can be gained of any setting when utilising the insider researcher's subjective sense of their own experience through inquiry from the inside (Bartunek, & Reis Louis, 1996). I asked some university colleagues to oversee the data collection from participants, ensuring they were lecturers specialising in different sports - mainly swimming, soccer, and tennis. My English-speaking Iraqi colleagues in various universities around Western Asia and in Australia assisted me with translating data collection tools into Arabic for use with participants and then back into English for analysis. My colleagues in Mosul distributed and returned my data sets and conducted the filming. I have a debt of gratitude to my colleagues for facilitating data collection remotely while my personal safety in Iraq was under threat.

3.4.2 Ethical Considerations

The National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (NSECHR) (National Health and Medical Research Council [NHMRC], 2007) states that research merit and integrity, justice, beneficence, and respect constitute the four pillars for conducting ethical research. These considerations aim to protect the welfare of research participants for the duration of the study and beyond (Crow & Wiles, 2008). Ethics approval to conduct research at Griffith University is in accordance with NSECHR guidelines. This requires each researcher

planning to conduct a research project at Griffith University involving human participants to submit an application to the Griffith University Ethics Committee.

Ethical approval to conduct this study was applied for and granted by the Griffith University Human Research Ethics Committee (GU Ref No: 2017/243), (Refer Appendix 5). The following justifications of how the project complied with the National Statement Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007) by overviewing the specific way the researcher attended to each of the four NSECHR (2007) criteria.

The criteria for merit and integrity for this project have been research are met because the project will add to new knowledge in a previously under-research field in Iraq. The study has an appropriate design to achieve its aims and is based on a comprehensive review of existing research on the topic. Research integrity is protected through the rigorous application process for ethics approval overseen by the Griffith University Ethics Committee. The proposed project, including research ethics protocols was approved by Griffith University through a confirmation of candidature procedures where the project was defended by the researcher. The research was undertaken under the guidance of two senior academics at Griffith University.

The principles of justice and beneficence has been observed through measures including the inclusion of appropriate participants in the research including transparency in the manner participants were selected for the study. Care was taken to place as little burden or disruption on participants as possible during the study. Furthermore, all participants will have equal access to the findings of the research as dissemination of results will occur through publicly accessible research publications (see Appendix 6). Risk for individuals as a result of participating in this research was minimal, and the potential benefits to sporting organisations schools and community organisations may be significant. In addition, participation in the research could foreseeably result in potentially beneficial outcomes for individuals. For example, by participating in semi-structured interviews, coaches were provided with an opportunity for guided reflection on their own practice. Critical reflection on coaching approach and philosophy, as noted in Chapter 2, underpins coaches' ability to improve coaching practice.

Respect is described by NSECHR (NHMRC, 2007, p. 13) as "having due regard for the welfare, beliefs, perceptions, customs and cultural heritage, both individual and collective of those involved in research". A key aspect of ethical conduct of research is gaining informed consent from participants to participate in the research project. Informed consent procedures and guidelines attempt to ensure that participation was voluntary, and coercion has not occurred

(Miller, Birch, & Mauthner, 2012). Following NSECHR guidelines, all participants were informed of the aims of the study and what they would be asked to do in a research Information Package and Informed Consent form. This information clearly indicated that participation in the research was voluntary and that participants could withdraw from the study at any time. Electronic copies of Information Packages and Informed Consent forms (see Appendix 4) were emailed to club coaches who distributed paper copies to player-participants. Players and coaches then emailed scanned copies of the consent forms to the researcher prior to any data collection.

The study was conducted in such a way as to ensure that no harm would come to any participants (Josselson, 2006). Individuals who chose to be interviewed were not asked to provide any information that was personal or sensitive. Participants were also informed that all reasonable steps would be taken to ensure that their responses would remain anonymous (Simons, 2009). PSPP data was deidentified and results reported at a group level. Pseudonyms were assigned to participating clubs and players and coaching staff for purposes of reporting. In the case of interviews, transcripts were scrutinised for information that may have identified an individual and removed prior to analysis. Full transcripts of interviews were only available to the research team. Participants were informed that participation in the video-and audio-recorded volleyball training session was voluntary with attendance at the recorded session indicating consent to be filmed and for that material to be included in data collection. Screen shots of video-recordings used in the thesis were deidentified using a cartoonising software (www.cartoonize.net) to render the images.

In accordance with Griffith University's policies on the management and storage of research data, all electronic files were stored in a password encrypted electronic drive available only to the research team.

3.4.3 Participants

Iraqi volleyball has four levels of competition; Juniors, Youth, Advanced, and International. The Junior volleyball competition has 12 male teams and 6 female teams, in the northern parts of Iraq and in Baghdad. with players aged less than 12 years. The Youth volleyball competition has 12 male teams and 6 female teams, with players under 19 years. The Advanced volleyball competition has 12 male teams and 6 female teams, with the age range of players tending to be 21-25 years. The international Iraqi team has one male and one female team. The participants in this study were all drawn from advanced competition in the northern region of Iraq, from a network familiar to me as a coach in a similar region and competition.

The study's participants comprised coaching staff and players from four elite volleyball teams based at two different clubs located in major cities in Northern Iraq. Two teams, one male and one female, came from each club. Each team comprised 12 players, all of whom were university students and coached by a head coach and one assistant coach. All eight coaches were male. The total pool of participants for the study included: four head coaches, four assistant coaches, 24 male players and 24 female players ($n = 56$). While the study sample was relatively small in terms of the total volleyball player population in Iraq, the sample size was considered large enough to undertake a deep study of coaching practices in two clubs participating in the country's highest level of competition.

For the purposes of this study, the teams have been identified by the following pseudonyms Dejlal Club and Furat Club. The teams are further distinguished as male or female and are labelled Dejlal Men's, Dejlal Women's, Furat Men's and Furat Women's Teams. Participants were recruited via email invitations distributed by key points of contact known to the researcher at each of the clubs. These contacts then forwarded information and consent materials to potential participants. To minimise the chance that participants could be identified, all were given a pseudonym (Simons, 2009). Furthermore, any information that may have identified a participant was removed from the data prior to analysis. A summary of participants including their role in the research is provided in Section 3.5 below.

3.5 Data Collection and Instruments

The mixed-methods sequential explanatory design used for this study enabled the collection and combination of three distinct data sets. These data sets and the instruments used for their collection are indicated below in order of their administration during the study.

1. Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) (Quantitative data gathered from survey of all player participants and analysed statistically) ($n = 48$)
2. Video – and audio-recordings of 4 volleyball training sessions; one session per team (Analysed using video observational and notational analysis) ($n = 4$)
3. Semi-structured interviews conducted with all coaching staff ($n = 8$) and four players from each team. ($n = 16$).

Additional data that was sought to supplement the main sources of data for this study include secondary sources such as coaching plans (verbal), competition schedules, government policy documents, official reports and documents from the professional volleyball association.

These were sourced through internet pages and archives, books and newspapers. Secondary sources of data may lack the participant engagement inherent in the other methods of data collection, but they provide insight into socio-political, cultural-discursive and material-economic contextual aspects of the study. Some of these documents, particularly the Government reports, have already been discussed to provide context to the study in Iraq in Chapter 1.

Different types of data were collected from different sets of participants in the study. All participants (coaching staff and players) took part in the video-recordings of training sessions and all players from the four teams completed the PSPP ($n = 48$). All coaching staff ($n = 8$) and only four players from each team ($n = 16$) took part in semi-structured interviews. The following table lists the participants by club indicating their participation in either the PSPP or interviews or both. All of the coaches and assistant coaches have degrees in sports science and specifically in volleyball, which is considered to be a superior form of qualification for coaching. There is no equivalent national coach education or training system (like the Australian Level 1, Level 2 Coaching offered by National Sporting Organisations and/or Sport Australia).

Table 4

PSPP and Interview Participant Data Table

Dejlah Men			
Participant (age)	Role	PSPP	Interview
Zack (18-25)	Player / Captain	Yes	Yes
Philip (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Milo (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Ollie (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Players 5-12	Player	Yes	No
Max	Coach	No	Yes
Michael	Assistant Coach	No	Yes
Dejlah Women			
Participant (age)	Role	PSPP	Interview
Amy (18-25)	Player / Captain	Yes	Yes
Matilda (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Tayla (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Olivia (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Players 5-12	Player	Yes	No
Daniel	Coach	No	Yes
Victor	Assistant Coach	No	Yes
Furat Men			
Participant (age)	Role	PSPP	Interview
Mathew (18-25)	Player / Captain	Yes	Yes
Murray (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Stephen (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Arthur (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Players 5-12	Player	Yes	No
Adam	Coach	No	Yes
Mark	Assistant Coach	No	Yes
Furat Women			
Participant (age)	Role	PSPP	Interview
Hannah (18-25)	Player / Captain	Yes	Yes
Daisy (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Sophia (18-25)	Player	Yes	Yes
Megan (18-25)	Player	Yes	No
Players 5-12	Player	Yes	No
Samuel	Coach	No	Yes
Edward	Assistant Coach	No	Yes

3.5.1 Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP)

The role and importance of physical self-perception for athlete performance has been explored in multiple ways, such as exploring exercise as a way to reduce trait anxiety in female participants (Asci, 2003) and to measure the effect of exercise on self-esteem and physical self-

worth (Moore, Mitchell, Bibeau, & Bartholomew, 2011). Scrabis-Fletcher and Silverman (2010) examined the Perception of Competence on athletes' performance of physical activity finding statistical significance among all of the sub-domains of the PSPP (mentioned below). In particular, they found that competence in motor skills and perceived knowledge and skills can lead to an individual's improvement and effective participation in different kinds of physical activities for prolonged periods with greater level of intensity. As discussed in Chapter 2, self-worth, and particularly physical self-perception have been linked to increased motivation to engage in physical activity and improve performance (Ebbeck & Gibbons, 1998; Moore et al., 2011).

The PSPP was first developed by Fox and Corbin (1989) and validated in a study of the self-perceptions of college-age students in the US based on Shavelson, Hubner and Stanton's (1979) ideas around self-concept and Harter's (1985) measurement of self-worth. The PSPP is a sophisticated scale with four robust subdomains — *Sports Competence, Attractive Body, Physical Strength and Physical Condition* — comprising the domain level construct of *physical self-worth* (Fox & Corbin, 1989, p. 414). The following table summarises the subdomains and domain level constructs measured by the PSPP and their associated explanations and gives insight into why this tool was chosen to explore physical self-worth with the elite volleyball players in this study.

Table 5

Summary of Physical Self-Perception Profile Subdomains and Domain-Level Constructs with Their Associated Explanations (adapted from Fox, 1990)

Sports competence	Some people feel that they are not very good when it comes to playing sport, but others feel that they are good at just about every sport.
Physical Condition	Some people do not usually have a high level of stamina and fitness, but others always maintain a high level of stamina and fitness.
Body Attractiveness	Some people are extremely confident about the appearance of their bodies, but others are a little self-conscious about the appearance of their bodies.
Physical Strength	Some people feel that they are physically stronger than most people of their sex, but others feel that they lack physical strength compared to most others of their sex.
Physical Self-Worth (Domain level)	Some people feel extremely satisfied with the kind of person they are physically, but others sometimes feel a little dissatisfied with their physical selves.

Fox (1990) subsequently incorporated the instrument into the PSPP Manual, an expanded guide on how to use and interpret the data generated by the profile with athletes. The full PSPP profile which is given to the athletes is shown in Appendix 1. The PSPP was chosen for this study with elite university level volleyball students in Iraq because of its proven validity with college-age students (Zason Chian & John Wang, 2008; Wang, Liu, Chatzisarantis, & Lim, 2010; Marsh, Richards, Johnson, Roche, & Tremayne, 1994; Eklund, Whitehead, & Welk, 1997). Morgan, Graser, and Pangrazi (2008) adapted the CY-PSPP to examine physical self-perception among children and youth showing that physical self-perception was correlated with changes (i.e., increases) in daily steps taken by children.

Surveys typically ask people about their perceptions, beliefs, characteristics or behaviours (Tharenou, Donohue, & Cooper, 2007). Furthermore, surveys can provide valid data, particularly if the survey has been shown to be valid and reliable across multiple studies (Walliman, 2015). In addition, surveys are usually easy to administer and can be completed by study participants in a short period of time. As such, surveys provide a convenient means for collecting a large amount of data in a relatively short period of time (Kraska & Neuman, 2011). For this study, the PSPP provided quantitative data for the study. Following the mixed-methods sequential explanatory approach described above, the PSPP data was analysed. The results were then used to inform the questions developed for the semi-structured interviews.

The PSPP was used in this study in order to compare athlete physical self-perception with different approaches to coaching, and hypothesised gender differences associated with this relationship. As a validated profile, the PSPP can produce statistical evaluations of sample populations, such as college athletes and in this case, elite volleyball players located in Iraq. The PSPP enables exploration of patterns across data sets can be used to measure differences between data sets (Asçi, 2003). The PSPP has been translated and utilised in studies with athletes in cultures as diverse in Turkey (Asci, Eklund, Whitehead, Kirazci, & Koca, 2005), England (Lindwall, Asci, & Hagger, 2011) and Sweden (Sonstroem, 1997, 1998).

Following a sequential mixed methods approach (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2008), player participants were invited to complete the PSPP survey first. Prior to the PSPP's administration in this study, the instrument was translated into Arabic by the first author and peer checked by Arabic speaking academic colleagues, following a modified back translation process first outlined by Hambleton and Kanjee (1995) and adapted by Asci et al. (2005) for their PSPP study in Turkey. Figure 3.1 below shows how the translation was produced and distributed for peer checking with the original English version of the cover page of the PSPP in the left panel and the Arabic translation in the Right panel.

During the PSPP completion phase, the researcher sent the translated PSPP via email from Brisbane, Australia to coaching contacts at the clubs on 19 July 2017. The researcher then arranged for those contacts to distribute the translated PSPP questionnaires to individual players as documents attached to email. Players completed their responses in their own time away from coaching sessions and returned identifiable documents to the lead author over email by the middle of August. All 48 players completed the PSPP survey. The responses, written in Arabic, were entered into a Microsoft Excel file and then imported into IBM SPSS Statistics 22. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics and Single factor ANOVA.

3.5.2 Video Recordings of Coaching Sessions

The timing of ethical clearance from the university aligned with the approaching volleyball season. Video-recordings of coaching sessions for all four participating teams (one video-recorded session per team lasting around 1.5 hours) were conducted in late August 2017. This equated to about 6 hours of footage. Lecturers from a University in Ninewa Governorate were coordinated from Australia to organise necessary recording equipment and to liaise with the coaching staff from each team to schedule times for recording recordings of sessions. There were ever-present risks of conflict through 2017 and many difficulties in scheduling sessions for filming were encountered. It was usual for training sessions and in games to be cancelled due to heightened tensions. There was also the risk to be mitigated of over-burdening coaches who already run these sessions on very little resourcing. Hence, the decision was made to only film one session per team with the most convenient timing.

My four colleagues from the university used two Sony digital cameras to video- and audio-record the coaching sessions. One camera positioned in the centre-side of the court provided the primary footage that was coded using notational analysis, which is explained further in section 3.6.5. A second camera was positioned usually at the end of the court and sometimes moved closer to the players to capture certain activities and side-court behaviours and conversations. Video-recordings for all four teams were transferred to a CD and sent to the researcher in Brisbane for analysis (discussed further in section 3.8.2.).

3.5.3 Semi-Structured Interviews

The final data collection step was to conduct semi-structured interviews lasting between 30 to 40 minutes with all coaching staff ($n = 8$) and selected players ($n = 16$). Using open ended questions, enabled the researcher to “to interact with research participants in such a way that they generate rich and complex insights” Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 101). The interview

format allowed participants to explain their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in as much depth as they wanted. In addition, the researcher was able to flexibly explore interesting lines of investigation that became apparent during the interview or prompt the participant to elaborate on a particular response (Cohen et al., 2018).

For this study, some questions were based on content from Christophel and Gorham (1995) to investigate the influences on player motivation. These can include negative things that a teacher (or coach) does that de-motivates them, such as derision. These questions were aimed at exploring some of the responses to the PSPP survey, such as identity support derived from physical fitness. Additionally, the researcher designed some questions to elicit responses from players on coaching behaviours and attributes that support or hinder their own motivation and performance that were identified in the research literature. Finally, some questions were specifically related to the model of TGfU to gauge player and coach understanding of this approach to coaching. The full list of questions for the players and coaches can be found in Appendices 2 and 3.

All interviews were conducted remotely from October to December 2017, using Viber or Skype and audio-recorded using the record function within these platforms. Audio-recordings were then, transcribed by hand into Arabic into a Microsoft Word document. The transcriptions were returned to each participant by email for verification and further comment and then translated into English into a separate Microsoft Word document by the researcher for thematic analysis, which is detailed shortly. As such, the English transcripts and the excerpts presented in Chapter 5 are not verbatim as grammatical corrections had to be made to improve readability. This part of this phase of the research was to establish connections between player and coach preferences towards the approaches to volleyball coaching enacted by their coaches and the players' perceptions of that coaching. As this outcome did not require fine-grained analysis of the transcripts, it was decided by the researcher and the supervision team that verbatim transcripts were not required: they are translated summaries of the interviews, which means that they have fewer words than typical 30-minute interviews. Nevertheless, every effort was made by the researcher to translate as accurately as possible what was reported by the participant.

Player participants for the interview phase were selected using a purposeful sampling approach. Patton (2002) stated that purposeful sampling allows the selection of information-rich cases for study in depth. Information-rich cases are those from which one can learn a great deal about issues relevant to the research. The captains of the four teams were selected be interviewed because they occupied a leadership role and routinely led parts of the training

sessions (e.g., warm-up and warm-down). They tended to be the longest playing and most experienced players, have experience of other coaches in representative teams, and therefore with the potential to have more exposure and greater insights into differences in coaching approaches. Other participants were selected based on their pattern of responses to the PSPP in accordance with protocols enabled by the study's mixed methods sequential explanatory design. For example, most players reported strong identity support from the sub-domains of physical condition and physical strength, but only some players, particularly female players, reported pride in themselves for being able to play sport. This warranted further questioning.

Each interviewee was asked to share a little bit about their background at the commencement of the interview. For the player participants, the interview was conducted using 13 semi-structured interview questions. These canvassed player's favourite parts of coaching, their preferences for coaches' approaches, their views on what makes them a successful individual player, a successful team, what builds team cohesion and what role the head coach and assistant coach plays in these concepts. The coaches were asked a similar but not identical set of 12 questions, probing their planning habits, how they believed they helped their players achieve their goals, what approaches to tactics and strategy they foregrounded in training and ultimately what they believed made them an effective coach. Coach participants from each team were invited to share season program planning documents and other relevant documents and talk to these if they so desired.

3.6 Data Analysis

3.6.1 PSPP Data Analysis

Completed PSPP forms written in Arabic were returned by each participant to the researcher via email. The researcher then manually entered the data into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The spreadsheet was then imported into IBM SPSS 22 which was used to analyse the data using descriptive statistics including means and standard deviations. Following this, the data was analysed using single factor ANOVA. This test is used to understand how different groups respond. It works by setting a null hypothesis for the test that the means of the different groups are equal. If there is a statistically significant result, then the groups are unequal (qualtrics.com). Ultimately, with different groups, such as two different clubs, or between men's and women's teams, you would hypothesise or expect that they would show at least slight or significant differences in their responses.

The predetermined significance level of $p < 0.05$ was selected for this project. In the case where p-value was below 0.05, the group mean was considered to be divergent. In the case where p-value was greater than 0.05, then it infers that there was assumed to be not divergent. The survey based on PSPP involves the utilization and analysis of self-administered questionnaire. It is designed for collection of particular data based on self-reporting system. This method provides significant information about physical self-worth, conditioning, sport competence, attractive body and strength. The drawback of survey data analysis method are based on restriction of self-system reporting and probability for misinterpretation of questions and choices of responses.

Anova is useful for hypothesis testing. Based on mean differences, Anova involves the comparison of means of two different group by evaluation of different estimation of variance comparison. Anova comprises of two models that are random effect model and fixed effect model. The parametric test of Anova is useful for acceptance and rejection of null hypothesis. The rejection of null hypothesis leads to the conclusion that means of population are not equal. The main assumption considered for one-way Anova are independency of cases, normal distribution, and homogenous variance of data within groups. The main benefits of Anova test entails that it is feasible for multidimensional analysis of variables, analysis of multiple factors at single time, and economical method (Ivankova et al., 2006).

3.6.2 Video Observational Analysis

Observation in research can be understood as systematically watching and coding people, behaviours and practices, events, activities and routines (Marshall and Rallis, 2016; Denscombe, 2014). Video observation and notational analysis techniques were employed in this study due to their ability to enable remote, international data collection. Video recordings enable enormous amounts of verbal and non-verbal data to be captured (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018, p.523), which is why a researcher's attention needs to be directed towards certain types of data to "note" with an observation schedule. This method, known as "structured observation", requires a form or schedule with pre-determined categories, which typically produces a kind of frequency table (Cohen et al., 2018, p. 546).

Observational analysis in coaching is known as well-known technique that persuades coaches to become effective observers themselves, enabling identification of weaknesses and strengths of performance (Cushion et al., 2012). It provides micro level analytical opportunities to see where improvement is required. Coaches are not required to be effective mentors rather than they need to become observer and analyst. It also required critical thinking, perception

and scrutiny on higher level. Coaches are required to thoroughly observe and watch different techniques of athletes for evaluation of their relevant performance. By recording video over the time period and development of content library, coaches can offer their help for how to improve performance. The feedback can be useful for motivation of players. The video analysis is subjected to manifold benefits for athletes and staff coaching. The abilities for providing visual and instant feedback, tracking progress in long terms and prevention of serious injuries will enhance the effectiveness of video analysis. In handling hours of video footage, an observation schedule helps the observer to stay focused on the reasons for obtaining the footage – coaching behaviour, player behaviour, verbal and non-verbal communication and coaching practices and practice architectures – the way things “hang together” in a coaching session (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008).

Video footage provides a means to notate additional information with multiple viewings that may not have been captured and/or recorded in the moment or, as in this study, upon first viewing. Recorded observations enable researchers to look for things they may have missed had they taken notes on the side-line. Structured observation combined with sport-specific notational analysis permits the researcher to collect quantitative and qualitative data, via generating statistics and providing a language to describe coach and player behaviours generated from the categories of behaviour listed in the observation schedule. For example, in the schedule used in this study, a number of coach behaviours are itemised, such as ‘direct management’, ‘indirect management’, ‘praise’ and so on. Hughes and Franks (2004) defined notational analysis as a procedure used in any discipline requiring assessment and analysis of performance. This means that the observer needs to understand the game or behaviour under view in order to make accurate notations of what is occurring. It is typically used in analysing sports matches, such as number of spikes, blocks and accurate serves in a game like volleyball. This is what distinguishes notational analysis from other forms of naturalistic observation. Miles and Huberman (1994) define naturalistic observation as that which a lay observer can make sense and form meaning of from what he or she is watching and tends to happen over longer periods of time and on multiple occasions. In this study, an observation schedule can generate the frequency of certain types of coach behaviours, such as direct instruction, corrective feedback and praise, and player behaviours, such as waiting, resting, exercising and so on. This provides a quantitative account of the frequency of coaching behaviours that comprise and shape elite volleyball coaching practices in Iraq, which is of central importance to this investigation.

Notational analysis is used for analysis of player movement and of coaching performance, often combined with video analysis software. Lees, Cabello and Torres (2009) qualitative biomechanical analysis research indicates that notational analysis sits comfortably alongside quantitative methods in mixed methods, combining descriptive narrative with statistical frequencies of behaviours and, when required, equations derived from video analysis software in determining human performance. Hughes and Franks (2004) argued that notating video footage, despite creating a new problem of treating enormous amounts of data, can enable the viewer to recover more than 30% of events that are lost through memory recall alone.

As mentioned in the data collection section, recorded video footage in this study was captured via two cameras. The main camera, positioned in the centre-side of the court provided the primary footage that was coded using two Coach Analysis and Intervention System (CAIS) tools (adapted from Cushion et al., 2012). A second camera, positioned usually at the end of the court and sometimes moved to be closer to the players, enabled narrative descriptive data of side-court behaviours and conversations to be generated. These four coaching sessions (two men's and two women's teams) were observed in full, from the primary camera, four times over several months (once for *intra-rater* reliability calibration with the supervision team, once by the researcher and twice for *inter-rater* reliability with two Arabic speaking colleagues). The first tool identified primary coach behaviours during instruction (see the full schedule in Appendix 7) and the second tool, ‘phase of training’ behaviours (refer to Figure 8).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1	Furat Women's Team	00-29	6:59	1-1:29	1:30-1:59	2:0-2:29	2:30-2:59	3-3:29	3:30-3:59	4-4:29	4:30-4:59	5-5:29	5:30-5:59	6-6:29	6:30-6:59
2	Confer with assistant coach														
3	Corrective Feedback														
4	Feedback - General Negative														
5	Feedback - General Positive														
6	Feedback - Specific Negative														
7	Feedback - Specific Positive														
8	Humour														
9	Hustle														
10	Instruction	1	1	1											
11	Management - Direct	1	1												
12	Management-Criticizing														
13	Management-Indirect			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
14	Modelling - Positive														
15	Modelling- Negative														
16	Physical Assistance														
17	Praise														
18	Punishment														
19	Question - From player														
20	Question - Response (Coach)														
21	Scold														
22	silence			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	Uncodable														
24	VPA - Thinking Aloud														

Figure 8. Inter-rater reliability calibration of coaching behaviour variables from CAIS tool (adapted from Cushion et al., 2012).

The tool was adapted because there were many more behaviours listed in CAIS than were evident in the video. Rather than code “nil” for the many extra categories, the team only coded those items that appeared in the footage at least once. Additionally, Cushion et al. (2012) reported that the tool was designed to quantify changes in coaching behaviour over a season, whereas this was implemented to capture evident coaching behaviours in one sitting.

Key observable coaching behaviours derived from Cushion et al. (2012) were itemised into an excel spreadsheet. The videos were watched at natural speed and stopped at each 30 second interval at which point the supervision team (for intra-rater reliability) would discuss and confirm that they agreed on the observed behaviour, for example, direct instruction and/or include any other variable. In addition to the CAIS coding, narrative descriptions were made to correspond with the 30 second time codes (refer to Figure 9).

Narrative for Furat Women’s video observation

00:00-00:29: Coaches are in front the team and the head coach has just told the Captain to be in front the team and stand beside the coaches

30-59: Team starts running around the court. Warm up is under the captain’s responsibility. Head coach and assistant coach are not interested in the warm-up for the team. They are setting up drill stations.

1-1:29: Running around the court.

1:30-1:59: Running around the court.

2-2:29: Running and moving the arms in a circle. The coaches are far from the team.

2:30-2:59: Running and doing arm circles. Some players have no idea how to do it. Coaches have not noticed that. They are still setting up the court.

3-3:29 Assistant Coach now watches the players running but does not correct the players in their warm up technique. He has said nothing to the players.

3:30-3:59: Head coach is far from the team and the assistant coach is now near the team but still doing nothing. No feedback is given, no motivational talk. The captain is doing all of the warm-up and no coach and assistant coach support is given to her.

4-4:29: The captain is with the team in warm-up and coaches appear satisfied that the team is getting a good warm-up without their input.

4:30-4:59: Captain and players are now doing stretches (legs) and the coaches are not interested in watching the team.

5-5:29: More stretches from the captain and the players.

5:30-5:59: Players are doing more stretches and then moving into some different positions. Some players are doing these well, but another player has no idea how to do it and is not interested.

6-6:29: Captain is still with the players doing more stretches and some players have no idea how to do it. They don’t appear interested in that.

6:30-6:59 The captain is now doing static quad stretches.

Figure 9. Narrative for Furat Women’s team for CAIS tool notation (up to 7 minutes).

In the above narrative, the first 7 minutes of the Furat women's coaching session, also notated in Figure 11, describes that the coaches handed responsibility for the nature and quality of the warm up to the Captain while they set up the court for future activities. This example of researcher narrative was repeated for all four videos to accompany each excel data spreadsheet.

Photographs were also generated from screen shots of selected video segments to illustrate the narrative commentary. This method of data collection, enabling multiple viewings and interpretations from inter-raters, creates a larger data set than would be possible with once-off, real-time observation. It also permits the observers to keep 'arm's length' from the action, watching the footage on screen rather than courtside (refer to Figure 10).

Figure 10. Screen shot of Furat Women's team warm up (6.15 minutes into session)

The "analysis" part of observational and or notational analysis comes with how the data sets are treated to address the research problem. For example, individual item constructs from the observation schedule – derived from coaching behaviours such as "corrective feedback" (Lyle, 2002) – can be compared across different parts of the same training session (e.g., warm up, drills, game), across different clubs, and between male and female teams, as an example. The difference in means for each behaviour can be compared and contrasted in ways that answer the research questions around coach and player perceptions of coaching approaches and practices. For example, to look at how frequent the coaching behaviours are that players also identify in interview data as valued, or that coaches identify as valued. Notated video footage is a vital element to this mixed methods study. It enabled data collection to occur whilst the researcher was studying overseas on a humanitarian visa, but also permitted the conduct of a study in Iraq of potential beneficence to Iraqi Volleyball and the wider coaching community.

3.6.3 Thematic Analysis of Interview Data

Qualitative data can be analysed in a wide variety of ways, however the key consideration is that interpretations made from data are the methods used to derive them are rigorous and defensible (Nowell, Norris, White & Moules, 2017). Thematic analysis was the method chosen to analyse the interview data generated for this study ($n = 24$) as it was particularly suitable for reporting the findings in a way that specifically addressed the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2013). TA can be described as a collection of related approaches that enable the researcher to identify and analyse patterns of meaning in qualitative data (Braun, Clarke, & Weate, 2016, p. 1.). Moreover, Braun and Clarke (2013) suggest that TA is particularly useful when searching across data sets such as focus group discussions, a set of documents, or multiple one-one-one semi-structured interviews, to find “repeated patterns of meanings” (p. 86). In alignment with pragmatic dualism philosophical view thematic analysis adopted a descriptive and qualitative method. The thematic analysis entails the freedom for permitting the analysis of enrich and accurate data. This approach enabled the experience of coaching for determination of information devoid of constriction and limitation, and lead to maximisation of worth of reality and experiences. It is useful for generalisation of feeling as much as possible with respect to guideline in broader context.

TA has been used as a method for analysing qualitative data in the fields of sports psychology (Braun & Clarke, 2019; Braun et al., 2016; Murphy, Dionigi & Litchfield, 2014), nursing (Crawford, Brown & Majomi, 2008), psychology (Braun & Clarke, 2006) and education (Xu & Zammit, 2020) among others other social science fields. Braun et al. (2016) study used TA to investigate women’s perspectives on, and experiences of physical exercise, whilst Murphy et al. (2014) investigated secondary physical education teachers’ knowledge of the factors impacting female participation in physical education and strategies they adopted to engage female students. As female participation in sport in Iraq is already a complex and constrained phenomenon, using TA to understand what enables and constrains their participation is particularly useful for this investigation.

While formalised approaches to TA have been developed reflecting a positivist research epistemological orientation (cf. Guest, MacQueen & Namey, 2012), more flexible approaches have been proposed in line with interpretivist paradigms that treat meaning in social science research as context dependent, negotiated and provisional (Creswell, 2009). Drawing on previous work in TA (e.g., Boyatzis, 1998; Patton, 2002), Braun and Clarke (2006, 2013) proposed an approach involving six steps, to bring some structure to what they regarded as

poorly defined approach to qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2013). They reflected that many qualitative researchers “claim to have used, analytically, ‘a combination of discourse analysis and grounded theory’. We’d shake our heads in confusion, thinking ‘these orientations are (typically) philosophically incompatible’, and usually (saw) an analysis that really was not one or the other” (Braun & Clarke, 2019, p.591). The steps they proposed to bring rigour to qualitative research are: 1) familiarising yourself with the data; 2) generating initial codes; 3) searching for themes; 4) reviewing themes; 5) defining and naming themes; and 6) producing the report. Braun and Clarke (2006) note that TA is not aligned to any particular research paradigm or theory and as such, can be incorporated into a wide range of research contexts and methodological approaches. TA was identified as particularly suitable for this study in light of the pragmatic approach typically adopted in mixed methods research that prioritises developing a deep understanding of the research problem and selecting the most appropriate research tools to achieve that aim (Creswell, 2013).

Braun et al. (2016) emphasise that conducting TA requires active decision making on the part of the researcher during all six phases, noting that qualitative data can be analysed in a number of ways depending on such factors as the research focus and theories informing the investigation. Underscoring the active role played by the researcher, Tyler and Ussher (2001) stated that “themes do not just lie about waiting to be discovered, they do not simply emerge, but must be actively sought out” (p. 319).

Braun et al. (2016) point to a number of methodological considerations and researcher decisions that will influence the ways in which TA is conducted. The first of these decisions relate to the researcher’s level of engagement with the data and whether the intention is to find patterns in it using a semantic or latent focus (Braun et al., 2016). A semantic focus is one that attempts to identify patterns that relate to explicitly stated ideas concepts or reported experiences. For example, in this study part of the coding related to the experiences of players and assistant coaches who reported that they were required to “follow the [Head] Coach's plan” which was identified as a theme in early coding of the data. Alternatively, a latent focus requires the researcher to code for *concepts that underpin* the literal descriptions or statements in the data (Braun & Clark, 2006). Taking up the previous example, the requirement of players and assistant coaches to “follow the coach's plan” was thought to point to the existence of particular coaching philosophy, in this case guiding the preference for an autocratic or command style of coaching, which had been previously identified in the literature. Accordingly, several extracts of interviews were coded under “Autocratic style” in the early phases of coding. This study used both approaches to coding.

A second consideration relates to whether the data analysis will involve a bottom-up inductive or a top-down deductive approach. An inductive approach is used to progressively built up codes and themes from concepts identified in the data extracts. A deductive approach uses pre-existing themes associated with theories or models that exists outside of the data or concepts identified in reviewed literature related to the topic (Braun et al., 2016; Nowell et al., 2017). Interview analysis for this study involved an iterative approach to code and theme identification using both inductive and deductive approaches. Coding of interview data began using a set of broad themes relating to volleyball coaching practices that the interview questions were designed specifically to probe. Other themes and sub-themes that existed prior to the data analysis were latently coded from the review of literature and were included based on the reasonable belief that interviewees would address these in some way. In addition, because the semi-structured interview questions were formulated, in part, to investigate issues raised by the quantitative analysis of the PSPP data video observation analysis, it was therefore reasonable to assume that participants would address concepts interrogated by those questions in some aspects. Accordingly, interview data coding began with a limited set of themes (improving fitness, sport skills, coaching strategies, player preferences in training, player motivation), which were elaborated, refined and expanded throughout the coding process.

Coding proceeded via a process of constant comparison and revision (Charmaz, 2006) which involved moving backwards and forwards between the data and coding structure comparing extracts with extracts, extracts with codes, codes with codes. This correlates with steps 4 and 5 of Braun and Clarke's (2006) TA, which is discussed shortly. Through this detailed iterative process codes were progressively refined and relabelled to better reflect the text they represented and to better reflect the meanings found across the data set as a whole.

3.6.3.1 Coding data using NVivo software

NVivo software was used to support the analysis of interview data. NVivo is a software package that enables computer assisted qualitative data analysis. It supports the research in the tasks of data storage and management, and data analysis (Richards, 2009). An NVivo project was created as the workspace to store all interview transcripts, create codes for analysing the data and the project journal. This journal served the purpose of an electronic diary which was used to record emerging ideas concerning the data and key decisions relating to the creation of new codes and the relationships identified between individual codes and emerging themes. NVivo enables the creation of codes or data storage points where related data extracts can be stored and reviewed and labelled. This provides the researcher with a flexible workspace which

enables codes to be merged in cases where it is determined that codes contain conceptually similar extracts or deleted if they are judged to be no longer relevant (Bazeley, 2007).

NVivo also afford the researcher the flexibility to adapt the coding structure, for example, gathering related codes together under a “parent” codes or themes. This enables the researcher to logically structure themes and codes to act like headings in a report to reflect the story the researcher wants to tell about the data as a whole. Screen shots of the NVivo workspace show how the coding structure evolved over the six phases of interview data analysis discussed below.

Following transcription into English, all 26 interview transcripts were imported into NVivo as Microsoft Word files. Preliminary codes based on the research literature and analysis of the PSPP data and Video observational analysis were created in the coding window in NVivo and given provisional labels. Interviews were then examined line by line and extracts coded to one or more codes (Bazeley, 2007).

3.6.3.2 Conducting the thematic analysis

Braun and Clarke (2006) caution that their six-step model should not be regarded as constituting a rigid or formulaic “staircase” approach to data analysis, but rather as guideposts to assist researchers to navigate the often messy and convoluted path towards extracting meaning from qualitative data (see also Braun et al., 2016). The following sections describe each of the six steps in Braun and Clarke’s (2006) model and how these steps were used to conduct the interview data collected for this study.

3.6.3.3 Becoming familiar with the data

Familiarity with the interview data came as a result of some of the unique aspects of data collection associated with this study. First, the author conducted all interviews with coaching staff and players from the two volleyball clubs via Viber or Skype. Second, the study required that all interviews be conducted in the participants first language, Arabic. This required the audio-recordings to be manually translated into English by the researcher. In addition, immediately following each interview, the researcher reviewed the audio-recording to construct a detailed summary of the interview. These summaries included impressions of the interviewee’s responses which were accessible to the researcher as an insider who had an intimate knowledge of the coaching staff and players and the social and cultural context of elite volleyball coaching in northern Iraq.

In addition, a preliminary list of codes that were either identified from the literature or generated intentionally as a result of prior data analysis (PSPP and Video-recordings of volleyball coaching sessions) were created in NVivo's code list, along with provisional descriptions of each code. An electronic project journal was also created for recording critical decisions concerning changes made to existing codes, the identification of new codes, and interesting insights that became apparent to the researcher during the coding phase. The coding process described below was assisted by NVivo Software.

3.6.3.4 Creating initial codes

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that following the familiarisation process, the next step is to identify initial codes from the data. Codes are aspects of interest in the data that can be identified from the most basic segment of raw data or information that can be evaluated for meaning. For this study, interview transcripts were structured to some degree by the questions to which participants were asked to respond. As such, meaningful segments usually accorded to the length of responses that were typically one to several sentences in length. Short responses of one or two sentences were usually associated with a single idea and coded accordingly. However, several codes were frequently identified in longer responses or longer exchanges between the researcher and interviewee on the same topic. The coding approach is illustrated in the example below that in an interview with Max, the Head coach of the Dejlah men's team.

Table 6

Example of Coding of Raw Transcript Data to Codes

Raw transcript data	Codes identified
<p>Researcher: Do you allow the assistant coach to contribute to the volleyball program?</p> <p>Max: No, it's my work and I know what I need in the session for the players. The assistant coach has to follow me and help the players to improve in volleyball.</p> <p>Researcher: Do you ask your players about the volleyball program?</p> <p>Max: No way. All the program in volleyball is under my control and nobody can do it except me.</p> <p>Researcher: How do you plan your program in volleyball?</p>	<p>Follow Coach's plan Coaching hierarchy</p> <p>Autocratic Democratic Coaching</p> <p>Coaches' knowledge Experience</p>

<p>Max: It depends about my experiences as I was playing volleyball in long time ago.</p> <p>Researcher: Is it your experiences important more than the knowledge?</p> <p>Max: I know the knowledge is important but the practical skills in volleyball depends on my experiences more than the theory. I transfer my experiences when I played volleyball from a long time ago to my players recently.</p>	
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Several measures were used to reduce researcher bias in the identification of codes and to ensure that the TA analysis focused on coding that addressed the original research questions. Several transcripts from the coaching staff and players were initially coded by the researcher and supervisors independently. Then, the supervision team sat together as a form of member or “peer checking” (Cohen et al., 2018) to discuss the codes, looking back at original interview transcripts, especially those that were coded more than once, to see where they fitted best. The results of this coding exercise were then discussed to achieve agreement around the meaning of codes and to assess alignment between data extracts and initial codes. This process resulted in a common understanding of the meanings of particular codes which were then recorded against the name of the code for future reference. In addition, periodic meetings were held as coding progressed to ensure the consistency of coding and to the explanatory power of new codes identified by the researcher. The following screen shot in Figure 11 illustrates the preliminary set of codes from the first phase of analysis, in which 20 initial codes, drawn from both semantic (literal statements) and latent coding procedures (related to underpinning literature) were named.

Name	Files	References
Autocratic coaching	20	37
Coaching hierarchy	7	13
Coaching strategies and planning	17	32
Coachs' knowledge_experience	20	35
Cultural issues_Female players_Impact of war	11	14
Democratic coaching	6	6
Feedback	17	29
Fitness and skills	24	76
Follow coach's plan	6	11
Good results	9	11
Iraq Volleyball Federation	6	9
Motivation_Team spirit	15	27
Player perception of coaching quality	15	42
Player self-coaching	6	7
Player_coach relationships	21	38
Players' opportunity to learn	11	17
Resources	8	10
Sport psychology as aspect of coaching	6	6
Tactical aspects of coaching (TGFU)	16	34
What players enjoy about training	16	17

Figure 11. Preliminary codes identified from initial coding phase

3.6.3.5 Searching for themes

Once all the data was coded, the next phase of data analysis involved the critical step of searching for themes from the created codes. This phase of analysis requires the researcher collating and reorganise the coded data extracts into broader categories or themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2013; Nowell et al., 2017, Xu & Zammit, 2020). Desantis and Ugarriza (2000) described a theme as “an abstract entity that brings meaning and identity to recurrent experience and its various manifestations. As such, a theme captures and unifies the nature or basis of the experience into a meaningful whole” (p. 362).

Braun and Clarke (2006) proposed a number of different ways that researchers might go about identifying themes including visually representing codes using mind-maps or organising them into tables including descriptions of each code, to identify relationships and patterns. Braun and Clarke (2006) note that throughout this stage of analysis, some codes merged with others, some discarded and others identified as potential themes. For this project, the final set of themes which are listed shortly in Figure 12 were placed into a table. They were then colour coded using a highlighter when codes were believed to relate to a common theme. The coded extracts for each code were then re-read by the researcher and supervisory team to discuss and confirm the apparent relationships. In a few instances, text extracts were recoded

if it was agreed that particular extracts either belonged with another code or required representation in a separate code. For example, it was decided by the researchers that one code originally identified as “Cultural Issues_Female players_Impact of war” be recoded to Social issues_Funding_Impact of war” to sharpen the focus of the code. Extracts focusing on Female players was then recoded to its own code: “Women’s opportunities” reflecting the concepts related to women’s opportunities to develop as players in elite volleyball.

This activity is consistent with Braun et al. (2016) contention that the researcher should not approach the six TA steps as a strictly linear process, but feel free to work forwards and backwards between them, revisiting steps in the coding process to obtain a more authentic representation of the data. The following screen shot shows the second set of 20 amended codes derived from all 24 interview transcripts following the review described above.

Name	Files	References
Autocratic style	20	41
Coaching hierarchy	7	13
Coaching strategies and planning	17	32
Coachs' knowledge_experience	20	35
Feedback	17	29
Fitness and skills	24	76
Follow coach's plan	6	11
Good results	9	11
Iraq Volleyball Federation	6	9
Motivation_Team coherence	15	27
Player perception of coaching quality	15	42
Player self-coaching	6	7
Player-coach relationships	21	38
Players' opportunity to learn	11	17
Resources	8	10
Social issues_Funding_Impact of war	11	14
Sport psychology aspect of coaching	6	6
Tactical aspects of coaching (TGFU)	16	34
What players enjoy about training	16	17
Women's opportunities	3	4

Figure 12. Final coding labels following coding of all interview data

Table 7 illustrates the initial identification of themes and amended codes that resulted from this phase of analysis. Significant aspects of the coding structure that occurred in this

phase included identifying themes that appeared to represent coherent sets of codes including Participant context, Coaching approach, Holistic coaching and Player development. In addition, a number of codes were promoted to the level of themes including Autocratic style, Coach's knowledge_experience. The themes that were identified in the reviewing step were: Participant context, Coaching style, Coaching approach, Coach's knowledge_experience, Player development.

Table 7

Initial Themes Derived from "Searching for Themes" Phase

Initial themes and codes (sub-themes)
Participants' context Resources Iraq Volleyball Federation
Autocratic style Autocratic coaching Follow coach's plan Coaching hierarchy
Coaching approach Fitness and skills Feedback Coaching strategies and planning Sporting psychology as aspect of coaching Tactical aspects of coaching (TGfU) Good result
Holistic Coaching Player-Coach relationships Motivation/Team spirit
Coach's knowledge experience Social issues impact of war Player perception of coaching quality
Player development Player's opportunity to learn Player self-coaching What players enjoy about training Women's opportunities

3.6.3.6 Reviewing themes

The search for themes resulted in a coding structure or grouping for all identified codes with preliminary labels assigned to themes that were thought to capture the recurrent experiences of participants or concepts represented by the codes. The next phase of analysis according to Braun and Clarke (2006) involves reviewing the preliminary set of themes to ensure they are supported by the data (Xu and Zammit, 2020). At this stage, Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that some themes might be merged, while others separated using Patton's (1990) criteria of internal homogeneity and external heterogeneity as a guide (p. 91). This requires the researcher to review the coding structure on two levels (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The first involves re-reading the extracts contained in the relevant codes to ensure that they coherently reflect the theme. If there are inconsistencies at this level, the authors suggest investigating whether the theme itself is problematic or whether the data contained within the code set is consistent with the theme itself. At this stage, Braun and Clarke (2013) suggest a number of questions that can be asked to assist with the refinement process including:

- Is this a theme or just a code and what are its' boundaries?
- If it is a theme, does it tell me something useful about the data and my research questions?
- Are the data too diverse and wide ranging that the theme lacks coherence? (Adapted from Braun and Clarke, 2013, p. 65).

When it has been established that the underlying extracts coherently align with the theme, the researcher can then move on to the second level of refinement that involves examining the coherence of themes across the data set. The key consideration at this level is the extent the themes, considered together, reflect the meanings identified across the entire data set.

When reviewing the themes for this study, the researcher and supervision team reviewed the extracts contained within each code to check for coherence. It was at this level that a small number of extracts, originally appearing under "Player-coach relations" and "Coaches knowledge_experience" were identified as related to participants' experiences (or desire for) more democratic behaviours from coaching settings. While small in number, it was felt that these were significant with respect to the overall story relating to players' experiences as told through the data. Accordingly, these extracts were recoded under the label, Democratic coaching.

When agreement was reached that coherence had been achieved, attention was focused on the extent to which the themes faithfully represented the data overall and aligned to the research questions. It was at this second level of analysis that some reorganisation of themes and codes took place. For example, it was felt that codes collected under the original themes of “Autocratic style”, “Coaching Approach” and Coaches knowledge did not appear to produce the best fit when considering the data overall. Table 8 shows the original coding to these themes.

Table 8

Example of Preliminary Coding to Themes “Autocratic Style” and “Coaching Approach”

Codes	Theme
Coaching hierarchy Fitness and skills Follow coaches’ plan Coaching strategies and planning Achievement of good results	Autocratic style
Focus on skills and fitness Tactical aspects of coaching (TGfU) Sport psychology	Coaching approach
Social issues impact of war Player perception of coaching quality	Coach’s knowledge experience

Following a careful examination of the relationships between codes and themes, reorganisation resulted in the following resolution represented in Table 9.

Table 9

Example of Reorganisation of Codes to Themes

Codes	Theme
Autocratic approach to coaching Follow coach’s plan Coaching hierarchy Democratic coaching behaviour	Coaching style
Focus on fitness and skills Coaching strategies and planning Achievement of good results	Coaching approach
Player perception of coaching quality Sport psychology aspect of coaching Tactical aspect of coaching (TGfU)	Coach’s knowledge experience

In this iteration of themes, it was determined that the term “coaching style” should be used to represent a broader range of phenomena than those captured by the narrower notion of “Autocratic style”. Furthermore, it was determined that “Autocratic coaching” was related to a strong (apparently socially and administratively mandated) hierarchy of authority and responsibility among the coaching team and players indicated by the code, “Coaching hierarchy”. Also, it was determined that while “Sport psychology aspects of coaching” and “Tactical aspects of coaching” appeared to be related closely to “Coaching approach”, a review of the data showed that the extracts often pointed to the absence of these dimensions in the overall coaching plan. Accordingly, it was determined that these codes were more related to the extent of the Coach’s knowledge base for coaching and were therefore relocated under “Coach’s knowledge_experience”.

3.6.3.7 Defining and naming themes

The fifth and final phase of data analysis requires the researcher to identify the aspects of each theme that make it unique and to label each theme in a way that captures its essence (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Xu & Zammit, 2020). Also, it is critical at this stage that themes are organised into a logical sequence that reflects a coherent story that can be told about the data overall (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Analysis during this phase required the researcher to return to the literature to compare the initial set of codes and themes established prior to the interview data analysis to compare these with themes generated in the course of TA. This led to refinements of the thematic structure that better reflected the conceptual distinctiveness of each theme, and a closer alignment of theme labels to reflect specific terminology used in the research literature.

During this phase of analysis, a number of key realisations were emerging concerning the connections between themes that eventually led to a number of revisions made to theme names. For example, it was becoming evident that much of the specific coaching behaviour that had been observed in video recordings of coaching sessions, and the ways coaches spoke about their coaching practises, derived from a complex set of associations that comprised, for each coach, a specific (but never explicitly stated) coaching philosophy. Accordingly, the theme that had originally been labelled “coaching style” was renamed “Coaching philosophy” to fulsomely capture the theme’s conceptual significance.

In addition, the relocation of the codes “Sport psychology aspect of coaching” and “Tactical aspects of coaching (TGfU)” prompted a reconsideration of the theme “Coach’s knowledge experience”. It was noted that some of the extracts under this theme pointed to a

deficit in coaching knowledge and indicated areas where coaching practice could be strengthened by exposure to current knowledge. Accordingly, to better capture the essence of the data, the theme “Coach’s knowledge experience” was renamed “Coach professional learning”. The following screen shot illustrates the final coding structure of six key themes that included: Participant Context, Coaching Philosophy, Coaching Approach, Holistic Coaching, Coach Professional Learning, and Player Development. These six themes and their associated subthemes comprise the structure for the interview data analysis presented in Chapter 6.

Name	Files	References
Participant Context	0	0
Coaching Philosophy	0	0
Autocratic_democratic coaching	20	41
Coaching hierarchy	7	13
Follow coach's plan	6	11
Coaching Approach	0	0
Fitness and skills	24	76
Coaching strategies and planning	17	32
Sport psychology aspect of coaching	6	6
Good results	9	11
Holistic Coaching	0	0
Player-coach relationships	21	38
Motivation_Team cohesion	15	27
Coach professional learning	0	0
Coaches' Knowledge_Experience	20	35
Player perception of coaching quality	15	42
Tactical aspects of coaching (TGfU)	16	34
Player Development	0	0
Players' opportunity to learn	11	17
Feedback	17	29
Player self-coaching	6	7
What players enjoy about training	16	17
Women's opportunities	3	3
Key quotes	17	29

Figure 13. Final themes and coding structure.

Note. The theme “Participant Context” has been collapsed in this summary to better illustrate the key themes and sub-themes.

3.6.4 Producing the Report

The final stage of TA is writing up the results. Braun and Clarke (2006) stress that reporting the data needs to go beyond providing simple extracts of text. It should, they argue,

produce a logical, coherent and interesting story that can be told about the data and presented in a way that convinces the reader of the authenticity and merit of the analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that the researcher should provide vivid examples of supporting evidence that capture the essence of the idea that the example is meant to illustrate.

Braun and Clarke's (2006) insistence that reporting the results must go beyond superficial description of the data is an important consideration given the mixed methods sequential explanatory approach adopted for this study. Within this design, the interviews were purposefully constructed to elicit responses from participants to explain aspects of the PSPP data collected from players, and the analysis of video-recordings of coaching sessions conducted at each club. The thematic analysis of the interview data is presented in Chapter 6. Beyond this, the interpretation of the interview data played a crucial role in framing the critical synthesis of findings as they related to all three data sets collected for this study which is presented in Chapter 7.

3.7 Conclusion

This chapter has overviewed the methodology adopted for this study. It has described aspects of case study approach relevant to the study the incorporation of the mixed methods sequential explanatory approach within that overarching design. The chapter overviewed the relationship between the quantitative and qualitative approaches with mixed methods designs discussing their specific application within this research. The chapter discussed the data collection phases and the instruments used in each phase including PSPP, video-recordings of coaching sessions in the semi-structured interviews. It detailed quantitative techniques used to analyse the PSPP data and video-recordings and discussed the use of TA for analysing the semi-structured interviews conducted with players and coaches. The chapter concluded by overviewing ethical considerations relevant to the study. Chapter 4 presents the PSPP data analysis.

4 PHYSICAL SELF- PERCEPTION (PSPP) FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This research focused on coaches', assistant coaches' and players' perceptions of volleyball coaching and coaching practices to understand how and why they are valued, seeking to identify if there were differences in the way in which men and women are coached and what they value in terms of coaching philosophies, approaches and practices. A sequential mixed methods research approach was chosen, comprising both quantitative techniques such as the completion and analysis of a validated questionnaire presented in this chapter, and qualitative techniques such as observations and interviews, which are presented in Chapter 5. The qualitative phase involved the video recording of coach behaviours, player behaviours and coaching practices in the same four elite teams during one coaching session. The coaching sessions (2 men's and 2 women's teams) were observed in full via video four times (once for intra-rater reliability, once by the researcher and twice for inter-rater reliability with two Arabic speaking colleagues). The observations were notated with an adaptation of the Coach Assessment and Information System (CAIS) template designed by Cushion et al. (2012). Lastly, coach (n = 8) and player (n = 16) perspectives were sought via individual interviews conducted over Skype and Viber, thematically analysed with the assistance of NVivo and also via the theoretical lens of practice architectures (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008; Kemmis et al., 2014).

This chapter reports on the findings concerning players' sense of physical self-perception using Fox and Corbin's (1989) and Fox's (1990) Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP) for College Athletes. As discussed in Chapter 2, the PSPP adapted Shavelson, Hubner and Stanton's (1976) ideas around self-concept and Harter's (1985) measurement of self-worth

to develop a sophisticated measure, with complex and differential weighting of subdomains and constructs to determine physical self-worth. Originally developed for use with USA college students, the PSPP has been comprehensively validated with this age group (Zason Chian & John Wang, 2008; Wang et al., 2010; Marsh, Richards, Johnson, Roche, & Tremayne, 1994; Eklund, Whitehead, & Welk, 1997). More recently, Morgan et al. (2008) adapted the CY-PSPP to examine physical self-perception among children and youth. The PSPP was selected for use in this study in order to identify constructs that enhanced athlete physical self-perception and compare these with coach and player ideas about and preferences for effective coaching. As a validated profile, it can produce statistical evaluation of sample populations, such as college athletes and elite volleyball players. The PSPP enables exploration of patterns across data sets and highlights differences within data sets (Asçi et al, 2005). The PSPP has been translated and utilised with athletes in Turkey (Asci, 2011) and Sweden (Sonstroem, 1997, 1998; Lindwall, 2004) before and this study has now translated the profile into Arabic (see Chapter 3).

The participants were elite volleyball players from the top men's and women's teams at two clubs in Northern Iraq, hereafter described as Dejlal Men and Dejlal Women and Furat Men and Furat Women ($n = 48 [4 \times 12]$). The coaches, who were known to the researcher, were contacted at the two clubs to distribute the translated PSPP questionnaires to individual players as documents attached to email. Players completed their responses in their own time away from coaching sessions and returned identifiable documents to the researcher via email. These responses written in Arabic were entered into SPSS and analysed by applying descriptive and inferential statistical tools and single factor ANOVA with the help of Microsoft Excel. The results have been presented as combined team responses (Dejlal Men, Dejlal Women, Furat Men, Furat Women), and individually de-identified for reporting. The sections forthcoming present the summary results of the PSPP and the single factor ANOVA for each team. Individual results have been combined into team reports and reports by gender. A discussion of the results is presented before concluding this component of the study's findings.

In the tables that follow, the 30 item constructs of the PSPP are presented in the order in which they appear in the questionnaire. The items are grouped into four subdomain subscales: Sport, Condition, Body and Strength, and a Physical Self Worth subscale, adapted from Harter's (1985, 1987) physical self-perception methodology, where all items comprise of matched statements that contains one positive and one negative sentence. For each contrasted description, the male and female players across the four teams were asked to indicate which statement is most like them, for instance 'Really true for me' or 'Sort of true for me' (Refer to Figure 14). Respondent's scores are rated on a scale of one to four. These four

subdomains and their differential and complex relationship to Physical Self Worth (Fox & Corbin, 1989, p. 410) have been measured via the deliberate systematic separation of individual item constructs throughout the questionnaire. Participant perceptions of ‘Sport’ are rated via six questions - 1, 6, 11, 16, 21, and 26. Participant ratings of ‘Condition’ are captured in questions 2, 7, 12, 17, 22 and 27. Participant ratings of ‘Body’ are measured via their response to questions 3, 8, 13, 18, 23 and 28. ‘Strength’ as a subdomain is calculated by responses to questions 4, 9, 14, 19, 24 and 29. Finally, questions concerned with participant’s Physical Self Worth include 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30.

THE PHYSICAL SELF PERCEPTION PROFILE (PSPP)			
AGE : _____			
WHAT AM I LIKE?			
These are statements which allow people to describe themselves. There are no right or wrong answers since people differ a lot.			
First, decide which one of the two statements best describes you.			
Then, go to that side of the statement and check if it is just "sort of true" or "really true" FOR YOU.			
Really True for Me <input type="checkbox"/>	Sort of True for Me <input type="checkbox"/>	EXAMPLE Some people are very competitive BUT Others are not quite so competitive	Sort of True for Me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
REMEMBER to check only ONE of the four boxes			
1.	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are not very good when it comes to playing sports	<input type="checkbox"/>
		BUT	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Others feel that they are really good at just about every sport	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are not very confident about their level of physical conditioning and fitness	<input type="checkbox"/>
		BUT	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Others always feel confident that they maintain excellent conditioning and fitness	<input type="checkbox"/>

ارجو التفضل بالإجابة الصحيحة والمعبرة عن الحالات التي يمر بها الرياضي في الفترة الظاهرة عن طريق أسئلة الاستبيان وذلك جزءاً من دراسة الدكتوراه بعنوانها "دراسة تصورات أبحاث المدربين واللاعبين للظاهرة الأكثر فاعلية للتدريب الكرة الطائرة مع لاعبين الشباب في العراق". سيوفر الاستبيان لاطمئني وإجابات القوة الظاهرة الصالحة التي أن هناك مقاييس شخصية لبعض اللاعبين والصفات والشخصيات التدريبية وتختلف برامج المدربين وتختلف الجوانب العقلية والتي سيتم فيها تصوير لوحة تدريبية.

الفرق بين هذا البحث أو البصاح في تصورات لاعبي وإصابات الكرة الطائرة ومدربيهوم تصورات نتائج التدريب الفعول والتربوية في لعبة القوى الكرة الطائرة للنادي الفرق العراقية. النتائج التي سيتم استخدامها دراسة الحالة وطريقة جمع البيانات هو ملاحظة وثيقة تجميع والمراقبة الميدانية عبر الفيديو لتفسير العمارسات والمعتقدات التي طقت من قبل اللاعبين والمدربين حول اللعبة التربوية للتدريب الكرة الطائرة.

هذا ويستمر التوصل لتحقيق عملية التي تهدف للبحوث العلمية الرياضية بشكلها العام والتربويين والشكر والتقدير والبرامج الرياضية بشكل خاص

طلب الدكتوراه
العلم ابراهيم

استبيان عن التصور الذاتي الذاتي:

الاسم:
الجنس:
اسم الفريق:
عنا ابنا:
ماهي اقبالي الرياضية?
هناك بعض الاستبيانات التي تسمح للناس بوصف أنفسهم والتي غالبا ما تكون اجاباتهم مخطئة وتلك ليس هناك جواب مطلق صحيح أو خطأ
أولا: قرر أي من العبارتين هي التي تصفك بشكل أفضل. ومن ثم اذهب إلى الاستبيان وحدد في ما إذا كنت (ب) (د) (ج) (أ) ما صحيحه أو صحيحه (ج) بالشعبه لك.

الدرجة 1	صحيح جدا	بعض ما	الدرجة 2	بعض ما	صحيح جدا
بعض ما	صحيح جدا	بعض ما	بعض ما	صحيح جدا	بعض ما

ملاحظة: التأكيد من الإجابة الواحدة لكل سؤال ضمن الخيارات الأربعة.

Figure 14. Instruction page for completing the English language PSPP on the left and as translated into Arabic language PSPP for player participants on the right (adapted from Fox, 1990).

As shown in Figure 14, the Arabic version of the PSPP preserved the original formatting of the English version. The scale of 1-4 is produced by giving the lowest score (1) to the strongest negative expression of the statement e.g., “really true for me” that “some people are not very good at playing sports”. The highest score (4) is awarded for the strongest positive expression of the statement e.g., “really true for me” that “others feel that they are really good at just about every sport”. Unanimous agreement around the rating or importance given to any one construct across a group would rate closer to 4.

4.2 Rationale for ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) Test to PSPP

This section explains the use of the ANOVA test. The scale used in the Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) is applied in descriptive statistics. The main purpose of using ANOVA is to examine the analysis of variance between constructs and/or groups and can be used to compare the means between two or more groups of values. In this section, Single factor or one-way ANOVA is applied with the help of Microsoft Excel. It enables a comparison of all factors across the teams involved. The test is based on null hypothesis which presumes that the average from the entire population is equivalent:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 \dots \dots \mu_x$$

H₁: Minimum One Mean is Different

The following criteria are considered during hypothesis testing:

If test Statistic is greater than Critical Value $F > F_{crit}$, then Null Hypothesis will be rejected. If p-value is lesser than 0.05 (level of significance) then Null Hypothesis will be rejected.

The ANOVA test is based on certain assumptions, such as expected error values are zero, variance of entire error is equivalent to each other, error is independent, and it is normally distributed. This test is considered an omnibus test statistic, used to reveal which specific groups are divergent from each other. The summary output reveals that with the extent of freedom, mean square, sum of square and mean square for predictor variable (variation across treatment level) along with residual based on variation within level, p-values and F-statistic values are considered. The Mean Square and Sum of Square are considered as the variation measures. The F-statistics is computed with the help of mean square within and among the data. The P-value is considered as the probability of observed F value from the F- distribution table.

For the predetermined significance level, 5% was selected for this study. If the p-value is below 5% (level of significance < 0.05), then it affirms that the group mean is divergent. In the case where a greater than 5% significance (p-value > 0.05), then it infers that there is no divergence between mean of groups (i.e., null hypothesis). In the following section, the Single Factor ANOVA is applied on four separate teams of volleyball where two teams are male-oriented and remaining teams are female-oriented.

4.3 PSPP Sub-Domains Summary Results and ANOVA for four Teams

Table 10

Sub-Domains and Self-Worth Sum, Means, $F(\text{crit.})$ and Significance for the Four Teams

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Competence	Between Groups	.144	1	.144	1.162	.287
	Within Groups	5.684	46	.124		
	Total	5.828	47			
Conditioning	Between Groups	.021	1	.021	.197	.659
	Within Groups	4.854	46	.106		
	Total	4.875	47			
Attractiveness	Between Groups	.354	1	.354	2.331	.134
	Within Groups	6.997	46	.152		
	Total	7.351	47			
Strength	Between Groups	.158	1	.158	1.528	.223
	Within Groups	4.743	46	.103		
	Total	4.901	47			
Self-worth	Between Groups	.098	1	.098	.608	.440
	Within Groups	7.402	46	.161		
	Total	7.499	47			

As seen in Table 10, no significant difference between groups was found on Sporting competence - $F(1,46) = 1.162, p = .29$. For physical conditioning, - $F(1, 46) = .197, p = .66$. For Body Attractiveness, no significant difference between males and females with $F(1, 46) = 2.331, p = .13$. For Physical Strength, $F(1, 46) = 1.528, p = .22$ and lastly, for Physical Self-Worth, no significant differences were found with $(F1. 46) = .608, p = .44$.

No significant differences were found within or between teams for the sub-domains of sports competence, body attractiveness and the overall domain of physical self-worth. Slight differences, or significance, was found for conditioning and strength. With these mixed results, the individual item constructs of each sub-domain were then examined more closely. The following section presents PSPP summary results and ANOVA by team at item level.

4.4 PSPP Construct Summary Results and ANOVA by Team

4.4.1 Dejlal Men's Volleyball Team

The first team consists of 12 member ANOVAs of Dejlal Men's Volleyball Team, which was the top men's team at this club. The results of one-way ANOVA show that the

maximum average was observed for the *Importance of maintaining physical conditioning* with value of 3.083333333 whereas minimum value is observed for *Importance of Being Good at Sports* with a value of 1.333. The maximum variations are observed in *Stamina and Fitness* with value of 1.515151515 whereas minimum variations are observed for *Physical Side of Themselves* with value of 0.0833. The ANOVA table for Dejlal Men's Team reveals that p-value is found to be 0.000199 ($P < 0.05$) and F-statistic $> F_{crit}$ ($2.136073 > 1.4394$). Based on these results, using the criteria of F statistic and p-value, it can be confirmed that null hypothesis is accordingly rejected, and that minimum one Mean is different (Refer to Table 11).

The Dejlal men's team rated highly physical conditioning, stamina and fitness and had least variation between the importance of the physical side of themselves. This implies that time and practices spent on developing fitness and stamina would be a source of identity support for these players. A coach who is aware of the high importance placed upon fitness and conditioning by the players themselves would be expected to include opportunities to develop fitness in coaching sessions.

Table 11

ANOVA Single Factor for Dejlah Men's Team

SUMMARY

Constructs	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Good at Sports	12	24	2	1.454545
Confidence in Physical Fitness	12	29	2.416667	0.810606
Attractive Body	12	27	2.25	0.931818
Physically Stronger	12	24	2	1.454545
Proud of Themselves	12	27	2.25	0.386364
Athletic Ability	12	26	2.166667	1.060606
Vigorous Physical Exercise	12	28	2.333333	0.969697
Maintaining Attractive Body	12	31	2.583333	1.356061
Muscles	12	23	1.916667	0.628788
Happy with Physical Acts	12	31	2.583333	1.174242
Participation in Sports Activities	12	31	2.583333	1.356061
Stamina and Fitness	12	28	2.333333	1.515152
Clothing Embarrassment	12	22	1.833333	1.242424
Situation to Require Strength	12	33	2.75	0.568182
Physical Side of Themselves	12	35	2.916667	0.083333
Joining in Sports Activities	12	17	1.416667	0.628788
Fitness and exercise setting	12	33	2.75	0.75
Admiration for body looks	12	32	2.666667	1.151515
Physical Strength	12	26	2.166667	0.333333
Feeling About Physical Side	12	22	1.833333	0.333333
Learning New Sports Skills	12	22	1.833333	0.333333
Maintain Regular Exercise and Physical Conditions	12	32	2.666667	0.242424
Physical Shape of Body	12	31	2.583333	0.628788
Strong and Well-Developed Muscles	12	23	1.916667	0.992424
Respect for Physical Selves	12	22	1.833333	0.333333
First to Join in Sports Activities	12	28	2.333333	0.787879
Maintain a Higher Level of Physical Conditioning	12	25	2.083333	0.44697
Conscious of Body Appearance	12	28	2.333333	0.787879
Deal with situation for physical strength	12	29	2.416667	0.810606
Satisfaction with physical kind of person.	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Importance of Being Good at Sports	12	16	1.333333	0.787879
Importance of maintaining physical conditions	12	37	3.083333	0.265152
Importance of having attractive figure	12	30	2.5	0.818182
importance of physically strong	12	26	2.166667	0.878788
Importance of good sports ability	12	30	2.5	1.181818
Importance of regular and vigorous exercise	12	26	2.166667	0.878788
Importance of spending time and money to maintain attractive body	12	29	2.416667	1.174242
Importance of well-developed Muscles and being Strong	12	27	2.25	0.386364

Anova

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	63.54605	37	1.717461	2.136073	0.000199	1.439462
Within Groups	336.0833	418	0.804027			
Total	399.6294	455				

4.4.2 Dejlah Women's Volleyball Team

The second group reported in Table 12 consists of 12 members from Dejlah Women's volleyball team. The results of summary of one way or single factor ANOVA show that maximum average was observed for the *Physical Side of Themselves* with value of 3.416666667 whereas minimum value was observed for the *Importance of Being Good at Sports* with value of 1.416666667. The maximum variations were observed in *Good at Sports* with value of 1.878787879 whereas minimum variations were observed for *Proud of Themselves* with value of 0.265151515.

The ANOVA table for second team revealed that P-value was found to be 0.000 ($P < 0.05$) and F-statistic $> F_{crit}$ ($2.192302 > 1.4394$). The obtained results based on criteria of F statistic and p- value confirms that null hypothesis is consequently rejected thus, it is confirmed that minimum one mean among entire variables is different (Refer to Table 12).

Table 12

ANOVA Single Factor for Dejlah Women's Team

Summary

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Good at Sports	12	28	2.333333	1.878788
Confidence on Physical Fitness	12	27	2.25	0.75
Attractive Body	12	27	2.25	0.931818
Physically Stronger	12	19	1.583333	0.810606
Proudness	12	25	2.083333	0.265152
Athletic Ability	12	30	2.5	1
Vigorous Physical Exercise	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Maintaining Attractive Body	12	24	2	1.454545
Muscles	12	21	1.75	0.386364
Happy with Physical Acts	12	34	2.833333	1.242424
Participation in Sports Activities	12	30	2.5	1
Stamina and Fitness	12	34	2.833333	0.515152
Clothing Embarrassment	12	22	1.833333	1.424242
Situations Requiring Strength	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Physical Side of Themselves	12	41	3.416667	1.356061
Joining in Sports Activities	12	26	2.166667	1.787879
Fitness and exercise setting	12	26	2.166667	1.242424
Admiration for body looks	12	31	2.583333	1.174242
Physical Strength	12	27	2.25	0.386364
Feeling About Physical Side	12	27	2.25	0.931818
Learning New Sports Skills	12	27	2.25	1.113636
Maintain Regular Exercise and Physical Conditions	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Physical Shape of Body	12	31	2.583333	1.356061
Strong and Well-Developed Muscles	12	30	2.5	1
Respect for Physical Selves	12	34	2.833333	0.878788
First to Join in Sports Activities	12	23	1.916667	0.44697
Maintain a Higher Level of Physical Conditioning	12	27	2.25	0.931818
Conscious of Body Appearance	12	23	1.916667	0.628788
Deal with situation for physical strength	12	27	2.25	1.295455
Satisfaction with physical kind of person.	12	27	2.25	0.386364
Importance of Being Good at Sports	12	17	1.416667	0.44697
Importance of maintaining physical conditions	12	35	2.916667	0.44697
Importance of having attractive figure	12	24	2	0.727273
importance of physically strong	12	34	2.833333	0.69697
Importance of good sports ability	12	30	2.5	1.363636
Importance of regular and vigorous exercise	12	26	2.166667	1.424242
Importance of spending time and money to maintain attractive body	12	36	3	0.545455
Importance of well-developed Muscles and being Strong	12	22	1.833333	0.878788

Anova

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	74.69518	37	2.018789	2.192302	0.000119	1.439462
Within Groups	384.9167	418	0.920853			
Total	459.6118	455				

4.4.3 Furat Men's Volleyball Team

The third group consists of 12 members of the Furat Men's volleyball team. The results of summary of one-way ANOVA show that maximum average was observed for *Physical Side of Themselves* with value of 3.0 whereas minimum value was observed for *Good at Sports* with value of 1.3333. The maximum variation was observed in *Participation in Sports Activities* with value of 1.659090909 whereas minimum variation was observed for *Satisfaction with physical kind of person* with value of 0.272727273.

The ANOVA table for Furat Men's Team reveals that P-value is found to be 0.00456 ($P < 0.05$) and F-statistic $> F_{crit}$ ($1.767988 > 1.4394$). The obtained results based on criteria of F statistic and p-value confirms that null hypothesis is consequently rejected thus, it is confirmed that minimum one mean among entire variables is different (Refer to Table 13).

Table 13

ANOVA Single Factor for Furat Men's Team

Summary

Constructs	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Good at Sports	12	16	1.333333	0.424242
Confidence in Physical Fitness	12	18	1.5	0.636364
Attractive Body	12	27	2.25	0.931818
Physically Stronger	12	20	1.666667	0.606061
Proud of Themselves	12	28	2.333333	0.424242
Athletic Ability	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Vigorous Physical Exercise	12	31	2.583333	0.810606
Maintaining Attractive Body	12	26	2.166667	0.333333
Muscles	12	27	2.25	0.386364
Happy with Physical Acts	12	27	2.25	0.75
Participation in Sports Activities	12	27	2.25	1.659091
Stamina and Fitness	12	25	2.083333	1.174242
Clothing Embarrassment	12	24	2	0.909091
Situation to Require Strength	12	27	2.25	0.75
Physical Side of Themselves	12	36	3	0.727273
Joining in Sports Activities	12	21	1.75	0.931818
Fitness and exercise setting	12	28	2.333333	0.969697
Admiration for body looks	12	27	2.25	1.113636
Physical Strength	12	25	2.083333	0.810606
Feeling About Physical Side	12	22	1.833333	0.69697
Learning New Sports Skills	12	25	2.083333	0.810606
Maintain Regular Exercise and Physical Conditions	12	29	2.416667	0.628788
Physical Shape of Body	12	30	2.5	0.818182
Strong and Well-Developed Muscles	12	29	2.416667	0.810606
Respect for Physical Selves	12	32	2.666667	0.787879
First to Join in Sports Activities	12	30	2.5	0.272727
Maintain a Higher Level of Physical Conditioning	12	24	2	0.545455
Conscious of Body Appearance	12	25	2.083333	0.810606
Deal with situation for physical strength	12	23	1.916667	0.810606
Satisfaction with physical kind of person.	12	30	2.5	0.272727
Importance of Being Good at Sports	12	28	2.333333	1.151515
Importance of maintaining physical conditions	12	32	2.666667	1.151515
Importance of having attractive figure	12	28	2.333333	1.151515
importance of physically strong	12	34	2.833333	1.424242
Importance of good sports ability	12	23	1.916667	0.810606
Importance of regular and vigorous exercise	12	27	2.25	0.75
Importance of spending time and money to maintain attractive body	12	26	2.166667	0.878788
Importance of well-developed Muscles and being Strong	12	23	1.916667	0.810606

Anova

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	52.28289	37	1.413051	1.767988	0.00456	1.439462
Within Groups	334.0833	418	0.799242			
Total	386.3662	455				

4.4.4 Furat Women's Volleyball Team

The fourth team consists of 12 members from the Furat Women's volleyball team. The results of summary of one-way ANOVA shows that maximum average was observed for the ***Importance of physically strong*** with value of 3.4166 whereas minimum value was observed for ***Clothing Embarrassment*** with value of 1.166666667. The maximum variation was observed in *Participation in Sports Activities* with value of 2.022727273 whereas minimum variation was observed for ***Learning New Sports Skills*** with value of 0.083333333.

The ANOVA table for Furat Women's team reveals that P-value was found to be 7.29E-17 whereas ($P < 0.05$) and F-statistic $> F_{crit}$ ($4.942633 > 1.4394$). The obtained results based on criteria of F statistic and p- value confirms that null hypothesis is consequently rejected thus, it is confirmed that minimum one mean among entire variables is different (Refer to Table 14).

Table 14

ANOVA Single Factor for Furat Women's Team

Summary

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Good at Sports	12	30	2.5	1
Confidence on Physical Fitness	12	29	2.416667	0.810606
Attractive Body	12	31	2.583333	0.992424
Physically Stronger	12	22	1.833333	1.242424
Proudness	12	23	1.916667	0.265152
Athletic Ability	12	28	2.333333	1.333333
Vigorous Physical Exercise	12	27	2.25	0.75
Maintaining Attractive Body	12	27	2.25	0.568182
Muscles	12	27	2.25	0.386364
Happy with Physical Acts	12	33	2.75	1.295455
Participation in Sports Activities	12	33	2.75	2.022727
Stamina and Fitness	12	32	2.666667	0.969697
Clothing Embarrassment	12	14	1.166667	0.151515
Situations Requiring Strength	12	31	2.583333	0.44697
Physical Side of Themselves	12	34	2.833333	0.515152
Joining in Sports Activities	12	19	1.583333	0.628788
Fitness and exercise setting	12	26	2.166667	0.515152
Admiration for body looks	12	22	1.833333	0.333333
Physical Strength	12	30	2.5	1
Feeling About Physical Side	12	25	2.083333	0.265152
Learning New Sports Skills	12	23	1.916667	0.083333
Maintain Regular Exercise and Physical Conditions	12	32	2.666667	0.606061
Physical Shape of Body	12	26	2.166667	0.878788
Strong and Well-Developed Muscles	12	26	2.166667	1.060606
Respect for Physical Selves	12	25	2.083333	0.44697
First to Join in Sports Activities	12	22	1.833333	0.333333
Maintain a Higher Level of Physical Conditioning	12	25	2.083333	0.265152
Conscious of Body Appearance	12	21	1.75	0.931818
Deal with situation for physical strength	12	32	2.666667	0.424242
Satisfaction with physical kind of person.	12	26	2.166667	1.060606
Importance of Being Good at Sports	12	15	1.25	0.204545
Importance of maintaining physical conditions	12	39	3.25	0.386364
Importance of having attractive figure	12	17	1.416667	0.265152
importance of physically strong	12	41	3.416667	0.44697
Importance of good sports ability	12	37	3.083333	0.810606
Importance of regular and vigorous exercise	12	17	1.416667	0.44697
Importance of spending time and money to maintain attractive body	12	34	2.833333	1.424242
Importance of well-developed Muscles and being Strong	12	23	1.916667	0.265152

Anova

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	124.3246	37	3.360123	4.942633	7.29E-17	1.439462
Within Groups	284.1667	418	0.679825			
Total	408.4912	455				

4.5 Discussion of PSPP Results

At sub-domain level, there were no significant differences found between males and females on total PSPP score $F(1,46) = .671, p = .42$. As discussed earlier, there was significance (difference) in the sub-domains of conditioning and strength, but not sports competence, body attractiveness or total physical self-worth. The following table shows the comparison of average score and variance by sub-domain of each team.

Table 15

Average and Variance by Sub-Domain of Four Teams

Team	Dejlah Men's		Dejlah Women;s		Furat Men's		Furat Women's	
Average of sub-Domains	Average	Variance	Average	Variance	Average	Variance	Average	Variance
Sport	2.0208325	0.948865	2.0208325	0.948865	2.072916625	0.836174125	2.156249875	0.802083125
Condition	2.4305555	0.7891415	2.388889	0.7828283333	2.152777667	0.794192	2.375000167	0.652778
Body	2.374999833	1.016414167	2.194444333	1.161616	2.208333333	0.8194443333	1.958333333	0.6426766667
Strength	2.194444667	0.7979796667	2.125	0.7512628333	2.097222333	0.6957071667	2.333333333	0.760101
Self-Worth	2.3055555	0.4898988333	2.611111	0.8434345	2.4305555	0.6098485	2.3055555	0.6414145

Table 16 shows the results by gender across all 4 teams combined and compares these results to previous studies by Whitehead (1995) and Fox and Corbin's original study (1989).

Table 16

Means and Standard Deviation of Males and Females in Iraqi Volleyball Clubs (Dejlal & Furat), Whitehead (1995), and Fox and Corbin (1989)

	Current study sample						Whitehead (1995)		Fox & Corbin (1989)			
	Males n = 24		Females n = 24		Total n = 48		Total n = 1153		Males n = 180		Females n = 175	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Sport competence	2.07	0.38	2.18	0.33	2.12	0.35	2.85	0.70	2.87	0.64	2.42	0.71
Physical condition adequacy	2.35	0.33	2.40	0.32	2.38	0.32	2.90	0.67	2.74	0.63	2.49	0.68
Attractive body adequacy	2.30	0.36	2.14	0.42	2.22	0.40	2.59	0.72	2.49	0.59	2.30	0.69
Strength competence	2.18	0.28	2.30	0.36	2.24	0.32	2.73	0.64	2.60	0.63	2.47	0.60
Physical self-worth	2.37	0.36	2.46	0.43	2.41	0.40	2.96	0.65	2.64	0.67	2.96	0.76
PSPP Total	2.25	0.13	2.28	0.15	2.28	0.14	-	-	-	-	-	-

However, particular variables (PSPP item constructs) are noteworthy in terms of the differences in maximum and minimum averages and variations between teams and genders. A comparison of the differences in ANOVA results at item level for all four teams are summarized in Table 17 (below).

Table 17

Comparison of Differences in ANOVA Results Among All Four Teams

Construct average and variation	Dejlal Men's Team	Dejlal Women's Team	Furat Men's Team	Furat Women's Team
Maximum Average	Importance of maintaining physical conditions	Physical Side of themselves	Physical Side of themselves	Importance of physically strong
Minimum Average	Importance of being good at sports	Importance of being good at sports	Good at Sports	Clothing embarrassment
Maximum Variation	Stamina and Fitness	Good at Sports	Participation in sports activities	Participation in sports activities
Minimum Variation	Physical Side of themselves	Proud of themselves	Satisfaction with physically kind of person	Learning new sports skills

There are some limitations to these results which should be noted. Firstly, the small sample size ($n = 48$) should not be considered representative of volleyball in Iraq, but rather a point in time depiction of physical self-perception of the athletes involved in this case study. Sample size can also be linked to Type II error and may affect the ability to identify even smaller differences within and between the groups. As can be seen in Table 16, Whitehead (1995) and Fox and Corbin's (1989) studies had larger sample sizes. Additional unknown variables, such as actual fitness and ability levels of athletes and their experiences of coaching to date, might reveal significant opportunities to positively influence physical self-perception in future assessments.

The maximum averages were derived from the sub-domains of 'condition' and 'strength', with one female team valuing strength (Furat Women), and the other female team (Dejlah Women), and both male teams (Dejlah Men, Furat Men), valuing condition. The minimum averages were derived from the sub-domain of 'sport' for one women's team (Dejlah Women), and 'body' for the other women's team (Furat Women). The lowest averages for the two men's teams were from the sub-domain of 'sport'. 'Sport' as a sub-domain also showed the maximum variation in rating for three out of four teams, with one men's team (Dejlah Men's) dissenting over stamina and fitness.

Dejlah Men's team rated the importance of maintaining physical fitness and conditioning most highly and had least disagreement that the physical side of themselves was important. Being fit brought more consensus amongst the team than being good at sports. For the Dejlah Women's team, being good at sport was a polarising construct. It rated both as the lowest average, but also highest variation (disagreement) amongst team players. What was clear was that the high rating given to *being proud of themselves* proved least controversial – that is, there was consensus that, as a team, Dejlah Women were individually proud of themselves for their achievements. The Furat Men's team had similar contestation over how important being good at sport or participating in sport was to them as individuals. With high variation for participation in sports, and low weighting given to being good at sports, it appeared to be less important than the physical side of themselves ('condition'). Lastly, Furat Women's team also valued being physically strong ('strength') and were not overly concerned about their appearance ('body'). They rated the opportunity to participate in sports highly, which is a right still to be guaranteed to women in many Gulf States (Hamdia et al., 2020) but were less concerned about extending their repertoire of sports skills.

The PSPP results indicated that players' physical capacities played an important part in identifying as an elite volleyballer, serving as a strong source of identity support and avenue to

enhance self-esteem. Consistent across both male and female teams (all four teams) was high rating of physical conditioning, physical strength and satisfaction with the physical side of themselves, serving as a powerful marker of their athlete identity, a finding similar to Loland's study (1999). Both mens' and women's teams placed greater value on physical strength. In volleyball, strength of players is highly significant and is a distinguishing marker of elite players. It is useful for maximisation of performance and provides the base for improvement in jumping abilities of male and female players as well as their capacity for directional change. As the volleyball game requires maximum repeated efforts, players must possess physical strength, aerobic as well as anaerobic capacities, for repeating hard and fast movements. In addition, the physical training of volleyball players is highly critical for better realisation of player performance and game economy. The ranking of players as elite or 'national standard' is mainly achieved and distinguished by their level of physical fitness. The role of physical training for elite volleyball performance is ubiquitous and highly significant and it should be emphasised more than motor skill development, specifically development of specific and maximal strength.

Shannon (2011) similarly found that physical capacities and appearance can play a vital role in how elite athletes identify themselves. Physical performance as a primary driver of identity is therefore an avenue for enhancing self-esteem. Shannon's research examined self-concept (Physical), identity of athletes and self-esteem (global) among (n = 308) former college athletes. The results confirmed that self-worth (physical) revealed the positive association with global self-esteem (Shannon, 2011). The identity of athletes was suggested to be the mediator self-concept (physical) and self-esteem. It also worked as the mediator for physical self-concept and physical activity (Shannon, 2011). This finding points to a need for coaching experiences in elite Iraqi volleyball that meet athletes' preferences around physical conditioning and strength in order to affirm their elite athlete identities and physical self-worth.

Unlike Anderson (2004) and Loland (1999), who posited that both body appearance and physical performance are useful for reinforcement and strengthening of athlete identity, the athletes in this study placed little emphasis on body appearance. This does contrast to a number of American college athlete surveys where body image was important for physical self-perception (cf. Zason Chian & John Wang, 2008; Wang et al., 2010; Marsh, Richards, Johnson, Roche, & Tremayne, 1994; Eklund, Whitehead, & Welk, 1997). These studies found that female athletes reported low body image and lower physical self-worth and were less involved in physical activity as compared to males. Moreover, male athletes reported higher physical

self-concept as compared to female athletes and characteristically placed greater emphasis on physical capabilities as compared to body image.

In Iraq, there are quite different ideals about standards of dress for men and women, such as often-required hijab headwear for female players and long, loose playing shirts. Regardless, sporting uniforms did not appear to be a source of body or clothing embarrassment, nor being concerned about what they looked like engaging in their sport. Omiya et al. (2014) suggested that cultural influences on physical appearance could lead to higher dissatisfaction with women around the sub-domain of 'body' in contrast to men, contributing the lower physical self-worth in women. The results implied that religion imposes different restriction on female volleyball players in Iraq. In spite of cultural and religious constraints, female Muslim volleyball players shows a positive behavioural attitude. The PSPP results show that the women's teams are not overly concerned with body image or clothing appearance. Similarly, there was no clear gender divide either around 'strength' or 'sport' amongst the Iraqi players.

The results revealed differences at the item level in the importance to Iraqi volleyballers of sports competence to physical self-perception. Al-Husseini and Elbeltagi (2016) found that sport competence was a powerful predictor for both female and male athletes. In this study, two out of four teams rated *Importance of being good at sports* with the lowest average (Dejlah Men and Dejlah Women), which indicates that being good at sports was not as vital and important to the players' physical self-perception and global self-worth as conditioning and strength. Furat Men, by way of example, rated *Being good at sports* as the lowest average

4.6 Conclusion

The results revealed small differences at item level of physical self-perception between males and females and between clubs. It should be noted here that a small sample size of 48 might be considered a limitation and can explain why no significant differences at sub-domain level were found. Volleyball is a demanding competitive sport for players requiring high physical conditioning. The PSPP results show that higher emphasis was placed upon the individual constructs of physical conditioning and strength (for all teams) as well as sports competence (for Dejlah women).

It could be suggested from these results that physical self-perception, athlete identity and physical self-esteem could be enhanced when coaching practices focus on enhancing physical conditioning and strength. Gillham et al. (2016) reported that physical strength is considered as the vital domain for an explanation of self-perception. Physical self-esteem is often linked with societal expectations of body attractiveness, rather than enhancement in

overall sports capability, health or wellbeing. Eather, Morgan and Lubans (2016) asserted that regular exercise can boost confidence through enhancement of body image. The results of the PSPP with the four Iraqi teams did not support the finding that concerns about body image was strongly correlated with physical conditioning, unlike Western applications of the PSPP.

Overall, it appears that high physical self-perception reported by players and strongly associated with physical conditioning and strength is a clear driver of engagement in elite volleyball at these two clubs. Player physical self-perception can be particularly supported by time and effort spent on physical conditioning and strength development in coaching. The findings also suggest that physical strength and conditioning as a primary coaching approach and motivator or source of athlete identity support might be pursued at the expense of more holistic coaching practices for supporting the physical self-perception of players, such as sport competence and/or pride in themselves. These are important cultural-discursive arrangements underpinning the primacy of coaching behaviours that focus on fitness.

There may also be material-economic arrangements underpinning the emphasis on strength and conditioning in coaching, mainly that coaches can implement fitness regimes with very little specialist equipment and resourcing. It does not require resourcing from the Government to ensure that players at the national level have elite levels of fitness and strength to play the game. What is clear though is that it does require a shift in the arrangements or practice architectures of Iraqi coaching to introduce new coaching practices which move away from what coaches and players have always done.

5 OBSERVATIONAL ANALYSIS OF COACHING SESSIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents an analysis of the observational data gathered during coaching sessions, where the focus was upon coaching behaviours, player behaviours, communication and practices. Sections 5.2 through 5.5 provide a detailed analysis of four coaching sessions (one per team), using the researcher's narrative of the sessions in conjunction with two adapted observational tools from Cushion et al. (2012) Coach Analysis and Intervention system (CAIS), as described in Chapter 3. The first tool was the Phase of Coaching/Training States checklist (ibid., p. 212), which was adapted for video recorded observation of the four Iraqi teams in one coaching session. The second tool (Appendix 2) was the Primary Coaching Behaviours checklist (Cushion et al., 2012, p. 211), also adapted for use with video recordings (see Appendix 7). These tools focused attention upon the 'what', the 'how' and the 'when' of coaching behaviours, providing useful ways of distinguishing 'physical conditioning', 'technical' and 'game-based' instruction. It also enabled the frequency and nature of player behaviours to be notated and analysed with multiple viewings by the researcher, the supervision team (as intra-raters) and external coaching colleagues as inter-raters.

The four coaching sessions were recorded in mid-August 2017, at the end of their pre-season training just prior to the onset of competition. These were afternoon sessions scheduled from 5 pm onwards, generally lasting two hours. Each team used their volleyball club venue for practice. In terms of the data collection sequence, the video recordings were made between the 7th and 25th of August, one month after the PSPP questionnaires were completed and returned (in July). Interviews with players and coaches commenced whilst filming was scheduled over August, and the interviews, presented in the Chapter 6, continued into October.

The first tool discussed here is Phase of Coaching/Training States, the phases and sub-categories of which can be summarised in Table 11. The three phases which dominated these sessions were training, playing and management. The sub-categories included warm-up, warm-down, fitness and conditioning, technical skills practice and full game play (refer to Table 18).

Table 18

Phase of Coaching/Training States, from Cushion et al. (2012, p. 212)

Coaching phase sub-category	Description of observed coach and player behaviours
Training Warm-up	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as warm-up. e.g., running laps of the court, stretching.
Training Fitness training	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as physical conditioning. e.g., shuttle runs, weight bearing exercises.
Training Technical practice	Individual or group activity covering isolated technical skills under limited or no pressure. May involve coaches in the drill.
Playing Full sided game	Full court in play, all players on court, regulation rules with both teams scoring in the same way. Coaches on court side.
Training Warm-down	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as warm-down. e.g., Stretching.
Management Rest	When players are taking a break from practice. e.g., water break, waiting for their turn in the technical drills.

Cushion et al. (2012) included more sub-categories in their original checklist than those indicated above, coding different types of technical practice with constraints or under pressure, as well as conditional and small-sided games. None of these sub-categories were observed across the four teams, hence the observation tool was adapted to reflect the identifiable phases and sub-categories listed above.

The second observation tool utilised from the CAIS tool (Cushion et al., 2012) was that of Primary Coaching Behaviours. A much larger checklist of behaviours, as shown in Appendix 7 was available but only the following behaviours were identified and coded: 'corrective feedback', 'general positive feedback', 'instruction', 'direct management', 'indirect management' and 'silence'. These coaching behaviours were concentrated within the sub-category of training, substantially within technical skills and full match practice phases of coaching. This is because the coaches did not lead the warm-up or warm-down, or, in the case of one of the women's teams, the fitness component of the session. The Furat Women's team was led by the Team Captain in what appeared to be a "less important" phase of coaching

whereas, in both men's teams, the coaches either directed the fitness, or the players led it themselves, in what seemed to be well-rehearsed fitness routines.

Table 19

Explanation of Primary Coaching Behaviours, from Cushion et al., (2012, p. 212)

Behaviour	Explanation
Hustle	Verbal statements or gestures linked to effort to activate or intensify previously directed behaviour – “come on, faster”
Instruction	Coaches explaining the point of an activity, points of technique, cue words e.g., “push forward”
Corrective Feedback	Corrective statements that contain information that specifically aim to improve the player(s) performance at the next skill attempt (can be delivered concurrently or post).
Indirect Management	Management that is practice related, not contributing directly to practice. e.g., collecting all the balls, placing markers around the court, getting ready for the net activity.
Direct Management	Management that is practice/match competition related coach behaviour, contributing directly to practice or explaining how to execute the skill, drill or game. e.g., “I need you in three groups of four” or behaviours such as target setting, or coach performing the task.
Silence	No verbal communication. Coach is silent. This can be on or off task.

The following sections of the chapter present findings from each team. A researcher narrative of the recorded video is presented first, which includes the selection of some images from the video recordings as screen shots where relevant. These are followed by the analyses of Phases of Coaching, then Primary Coaching Behaviours derived from the coding of the videos. A comparative analysis of men's and women's teams in terms of phases of coaching and primary coaching behaviours is also presented.

5.2 Dejlal Men's Team

5.2.1 Researcher Narrative

Dejlal Men's team is one of the top sides in their competition in Northern Iraq. Dejlal is the home club for several current Iraqi international players. The Head Coach, Max, is an ex-international player. The Assistant Coach, Michael, is a teacher and ex-player. At the beginning of the session, Max, Michael and the players greet each other before the Team Captain, Zack, takes the players for a routine warm-up around and within the court (players n = 12). The coaches seemed to prioritise giving the players' time to warm up so that they could be physically and mentally prepared for the physical activities, but it was observed that they

probably need additional warm-up time as this session, running laps around the court, only lasted approximately 6 minutes, accounting for 5.76% of the total coaching session.

Figure 15. Dejlah team fitness exercises –beat the ball—directly managed by the coach, Max.

Max then directed the players to perform different fitness exercises, which, for example, involved running to keep a ball in play. In Figure 10 you can see Max directly managing the fitness activity – beat the ball – where he sets the ball forward in the court for players running from the base line to dig or set back from the opposite side of the court before the ball hits the ground. This was an individual activity – all players lined up at the end of the court and waited for their turn. Michael said nothing, standing to the side, waiting for Max to allocate him a task. During subsequent fitness activities, it was observed that some of the players were exercising according to Max’s instructions while others were not. The coaches did not appear to worry that not all players were complying, for example, they did not give redirection to any player to get back on task. This seemed to indicate that they were not particularly concerned about the intensity or specificity of the warm-up.

After the warm-up and fitness component, the players had time to practice technical skills. Max explained and demonstrated a setting activity that the players would be doing next. However, some players were asked to continue exercising, as this activity funnelled down to just one player at a time, while Max himself performed each and every set. A few players seemed to be confused as to whether they should continue exercising or not. When some players began the setting practice, they appeared to be making some mistakes. Neither Max nor Michael provided any instruction, guidance or feedback to explain the right way to do it. Max was silent, letting his facial expression convey his displeasure at incorrect or unsuccessful

attempts. As this activity progressed, players continued making mistakes in their drill. Only some players were actively engaged in the drills and others were resting to the side of the court. This accounts for 10.57% of the entire session being coded as “rest”. Some players were directed to dig pass in pairs while they were waiting, but only some pairs diligently persisted with this ‘waiting-for-my-turn activity’.

During this setting activity, it was observed that Max was directly managing the activities, not as a skilled observer ready to provide feedback, but as a player. Max had the most touches on the ball, the most sets, while Michael either fetched the balls to keep the drill going or handed Max the balls to use. Michael still said nothing. His role was to support Max in the execution of each drill. Max was performing like a skilled player and, at this point, giving no teaching cues, no corrective feedback and no praise. In the next two technical activities, at the net (blocking and spiking in pairs), Max finally stood back and allowed players to perform all the touches. Feedback was minimal.

Max did not bring any paperwork with him nor make any notes during the session. He was running the practice from memory and making no written records of, or reflections upon, player learning. Neither Max nor Michael provided any motivating comments to the players and did not discuss any strategies or plans to motivate and influence the players in their decision-making. As illustrated in the following section on coaching behaviours, “silence” accounted for 25% of the total coaching time. Player disengagement was moderate, particularly as there were lengthy waiting periods for active practice.

Figure 16. Max setting the ball to start the technical drill with two players. Two other players can be seen waiting for their turn, doing a dig/set partner passing drill.

When the coaching session moved into game play, the players were unable to complete the play and made a mistake with the net. Max was unhappy with the players, by the look on his face, but he did not take this moment to provide guidance related to the correct technique or strategy. He spent a short amount of time talking with the players about how unhappy he was with their performance and fitness, which was coded as corrective feedback (3.17% of total coaching time). However, it was observed that the coach did not provide positive feedback or model positive performance to the players.

Figure 17. Players appear confused during match practice. They talk among themselves.

The Dejlah men's team finished the sessions with full match practice, while the coaches watched from the side lines. A full match was the only time that the Head coach did not insert himself into the drill. On conclusion of the session, players executed some warm down stretches and chatted. There was no debrief by Max or Michael before the players left for the evening.

5.2.2 Phases of Coaching

Figure 18. Dejlah Men's team percentage time in phase of coaching session.

As discussed earlier, the warm-up was short, only 5.76% of the training session. The dominant phases of coaching were fitness (35.07%) and technical skills with little to no pressure (26.98%). The Dejlah men's team had a low percentage of full match practice, accounting for 15.92%.

5.2.3 Primary Coaching Behaviours

Figure 19. Dejlah Men's Team - Primary Coaching Behaviours as percentage of coaching session.

The Dejlah men's team spent the most amount of time in a "training" phase of coaching, with game play comprising the smallest proportion. So, it is not surprising that "direct management", as indicated in Figure 17, accounted for more than half of the approximately 70-minute training session. Direct management was debated and selected as the primary code during rater and inter-rater phases of data collection because Max was not "teaching" the players – he was directing them where to stand, when to start, telling them when their effort was not good enough and so on. He also controlled the pacing of each drill by being a performer. The intra-raters (researcher and supervision team) debated whether or not this could be considered 'positive modelling', according to Cushion et al. (2012) definition, but decided it was not. This is because Max was not stepping into and demonstrating the role/skill that the players would be taking, such as defending with a dig, and then stepped out to allow a player to perform the role. Instead, Max, performed the spike as he wanted to control the quality and intensity of the play that initiated the drill, but not once did he physically model or describe in key cues what the defensive dig, as an example, should look like to the players.

Max appeared to coach as though he believed he was the best or more technically proficient player. Michael stood by waiting for instruction as the apprentice coach in waiting. Players did not ask questions and accepted that the technical drills revolved around Max's performance as a playing coach.

5.3 Dejlah Women's Team

5.3.1 Researcher Narrative

Dejlah women's team trained for 99 minutes on one afternoon in the August pre-season. Their session was the longest in duration of the four teams. Their coaches were Head Coach, Daniel and Assistant Coach, Victor. Dejlah women's team is one of the top teams in their northern Iraq competition and feature current international players. Daniel is a lecturer and Victor is a local schoolteacher. Both joined the club as coaches after international playing experience.

Figure 20. Dejlah Women's team fitness activity – was meant to be shuttle runs but some players misunderstood and ran through the court.

Figure 20 shows an activity from the fitness phase of the coaching sessions and indicates a degree of confusion within the team as some are running through the court, some are bending down to touch the line and returning to the start in a standard shuttle run. Some are looking at other players to see if they are doing the drill correctly. The coaches have not provided any guidance. The players corrected themselves.

After 25 minutes of warm-up and fitness activities, the players moved into low or no pressure technical drills. The intra-raters discussed whether or not these could be considered “pressure” drills, or even small-sided games, as described by Cushion et al. (2012), as they were performed with opponents. But it was decided that they were low pressure technical drills because opponents quite simply were required to make the drill work. The players could not practice blocking without someone spiking the ball over the net.

Figure 21. Technical drill – spiking-blocking. Two players showing incorrect technique.

In Figure 21, this spiking and blocking drill potentially involved 3 players on each side of the court, with the remaining 6 players occupying themselves with another ‘waiting-for-my-turn’ drill somewhere else. Effectively, only two players – one each side of the net – were actively involved at any one time – the spiker and the blocker. Both of these players are showing incorrect footwork and body positioning for spiking and blocking respectively as indicated by their lack of balance. No feedback was provided to the players at the time of this activity. Daniel just watched and said nothing. His body language showed displeasure at what he saw but he created no opportunity to explain how the players were off balance, and attempted to play, unsuccessfully, with poor body positioning. The players were left to figure it out for themselves.

The most noticeable jump in time allocation for phases of coaching is the transition from low or no pressure technical progression from drills (which accounted for 17.11% of the session) to game play. Cushion et al. (2012) proposed that a coach may work up to a full sided, competition rules game through conditional or small sided games, as would be expected in games sense or TGfU approaches to coaching (Stolz & Pill, 2016). This did not occur, and a full match was instigated, taking up 39.41% of the training time (refer to Figure 19).

Figure 22. Full sided game with Dejlal Women's team. Note the location of the coaches.

During this game phase of the coaching session, all players were finally and simultaneously involved. The coaches are sitting down to the side. Victor is watching intently from near the service line but says nothing, as it is not his role to give advice over the Head Coach. Daniel is sitting near the base line with a parent. He is deep in conversation with the parent but provides no team feedback. This accounts for the large amount of coaching time spent in silence.

Daniel is observed spending a lot of time speaking with family members who start come into the sports hall while the women are still playing. The family members are here to escort their daughters and sisters home as they should not travel unaccompanied. The time and energy that Daniel puts into greeting and communicating with each family member gives an insight into a coaching role that is not really captured by the checklist –a form of coaching care. Each one of these family members need to be satisfied that the young women are safe, in good care and not at risk of any harm in order for them to be allowed to play. Daniel has to make sure the family members are happy and willing for the players to remain in the team, week after week. This is where he puts his energy as he has said little to nothing during the match to the players themselves.

5.3.2 Phases of Coaching

Figure 23. Percentage time in phases of coaching for Dejlah women's team.

As can be seen in Figure 23, the Dejlah women's coaching session devoted similar amounts of time to the warm-up (7.02%) and warm-down (5.01%). Almost equal amounts of time were allocated to fitness and conditioning exercises (17.35%) and technical drills (17.11%). They had a very large component of just under 40% of the whole session for full match practice, which was a point of difference to the men's coaching sessions. Dejlah women's session was approximately 33 minutes longer in duration than the other teams, lasting 99 minutes in total. As the pre-season training was drawing to a close, and competition was looming, Head Coach Daniel wanted the team to spend extra time in full match practice.

Given that Dejlah had more time for the coaches to watch from the side-line and offer their feedback on the practice match, it is surprising that the proportion of silence that characterised the session was so high – 35.51% (refer to Figure 21). This huge proportion of time spent in silence represents lost learning opportunities for the players.

5.3.3 Primary Coaching Behaviours

Figure 24. Dejlal women's team – Primary coaching behaviours.

As with the Dejlal Men's team, the proportion of primary coaching behaviours observed as "direct management" can be attributed to the coach performing the drills with the players – as a player himself – not as a coach offering feedback from the side. Similar to the Dejlal men's coach, Daniel had the most touches on the ball during the technical drills as he would take the role as setter or spiker. Victor would take on the role as "ball handler" – often feeding the ball to Daniel to keep a drill going. Victor would not offer his perspective on how well the players were performing. His role was clearly to support the Head Coach, often as a "gopher". It would have reduced the amount of time that players who were waiting around for their turn with the main drill with Daniel had they worked with Victor on an alternative drill instead. This did not occur during the coaching session.

5.4 Furat Men's Team

5.4.1 Researcher Narrative

Adam is the Head Coach and Mark is the Assistant Coach of Furat Men's team. This team is a top performing club in the northern Iraq competition and features current international players. Adam is an ex-international player and has a PhD in Sport Education, specialising in

Volleyball. He is a lecturer working at the university. Mark is a teacher from a local school and has a major in Sport Education – Volleyball. He was a high-level club player, but not to international level. The elite ex-player to coach pathway was also evident at this club. At the beginning of the session, the coach and players greeted each other. The coach spent a short amount of time instructing the players as to the session’s format. The players listened to their coach carefully and no questions were asked.

In the warm-up session, the coach asked the players to run their own warm-up activities. This was a contrast to Dejlal Men’s and Women’s teams as the head coaches at Dejlal club preferred to specify how the players should warm-up. Different players chose different warm-up exercises, and the coach was far away from them during this phase of the coaching session.

Figure 25. Furat Men’s team during fitness and conditioning training, but unsure of what they are supposed to be doing.

After the warm-up, Adam gave additional instructions regarding particular fitness and conditioning exercises. Adam was not recording any information about the players – no achievements, fitness statistics or similar, as he did not have a notebook. At this time, the players did not talk or discuss anything – silence dominated. The coach was involved in the exercise session, demonstrating different exercises for the players to follow. As intra-raters, the researcher and supervision team again debated if this could be considered “physical modelling”, according to Cushion et al.’s (2012) definition but decided that it was non-verbal instruction. Physical modelling includes helping the player to get into the correct position and

can include physically moving their bodies. Adam was only quickly showing the players what he wanted in lieu of complicated verbal instruction and it appeared that he was joining in conditionally, perhaps to improve his own fitness, or perhaps as showing off just a little. As the players continued exercising, Adam and Mark monitored the players. Adam expressed unhappiness with some players and pointed out areas for improvement as part of corrective feedback. Some players appeared to be less serious and made mistakes. Most of the corrective feedback observed across the coaches of three teams related to fitness exercises, rather than technical skills and game play.

Some players took rest time without informing Adam or Mark or asking permission. Other players continued to do their conditioning activities while Adam turned his back on the court to answer the phone. While he was not watching, even though Mark was, the players relaxed and paid less attention to their practices and exercises.

Figure 26. Coach is not watching and is on the phone.

While it was not clear who phoned, as with Dejlah female players, it is possible that a player's family member was phoning to double check on the player's movements. Coaches in Iraq spend many hours on the phone to extended family members, confirming training and playing times, pick up and drop off times and who will be present. The concept of coaching care in Iraq clearly extended to taking training time to nurture relationships with families. The coaches did not turn off their phones to concentrate on coaching – being available on the phone at any time during training was standard coaching practice. After the phone call, Adam returned

to the group and started to lead the first technical drill. As with the previously discussed head coaches, Adam directly managed the activity by performing as a player.

Figure 27. Adam coaching via a playing role.

Figure 28. Head Coach Adam controls the spike – defensive dig practice drill – with only one third of the team.

In Figure 28, the two screenshots show Adam controlling the spike. Two thirds of the team can be seen waiting around to the side of the court. Assistant Coach Mark could take them for an alternative drill, but he does not. His job, like the Assistant coaches already observed, is to support Adam as Head Coach.

5.4.2 Phases of Coaching

Figure 29. Furat Men's team percentage phases of coaching.

Of the three teams observed thus far, Furat Men's team had the highest proportion of fitness time (25.85%) and the least amount of game play (12.05%). Their coaching session was the most evenly distributed amongst each sub-category, but still heavily biased towards "training states" rather than coaching.

5.4.3 Primary Coaching Behaviours

Figure 30. Furat Men's – Primary coaching behaviours as a percentage.

Furat Men's team was the only team with "hustle" coded. According to Cushion et al. (2012, p.211), hustle means "verbal statements or gestures linked to effort to activate or intensify previously directed behaviour". It could mean "come on, faster, faster", "pick up the pace" and so on. Furat male players spent more than half of their coaching session being directly managed, with Adam controlling and performing as a lead player in the technical drills. Again, silence was the second greatest coaching behaviour – relative to the amount of time spent on warm-up, game time and warm-down.

Adam (and Mark, to some extent) crafted a session somewhat different to the other coaches and teams. Fitness and conditioning were prioritised, and game time appeared to be less important. Adam's past history as an elite player appeared to be an important part of his coaching identity as he participated in both the fitness activities as well as all of the technical drills. Intra-raters (researcher and supervision team) also discussed whether or not his participation in fitness could be considered physical modelling, but decided it was a form of instruction – "do as I do".

5.5 Furat Women's Team

5.5.1 Researcher Narrative

Figure 31. Furat women's team – commencement of the coaching session.

Furat's women's team is the last to be discussed in this chapter. Furat is a top club in the northern Iraq competition, with current international players, where Samuel is the Head Coach and Edward is the Assistant Coach. They are also on the Iraqi International Women's volleyball coaching team. Samuel is a local high school teacher and Edward is university lecturer– which is unusual given that the Head Coaches in the other teams tended to be the university academic.

At the start of the session, Samuel explained that the Team Captain, Hannah, was separated from the rest of the team, and asked to lead the warm-up. As the team captain, Hannah appeared to be assigned higher status than other team members. Edward, the Assistant Coach, was standing further away, a deferential step behind the Head Coach and Captain. The team has been told to line up on the side-line by Samuel. Note many of the players were standing with their hands behind their backs as they listened, as did Edward. There is a clear hierarchy of authority with this team.

Hannah led the team as they ran laps around the court. Samuel and Edward appeared to take little interest in the intensity or nature of the warm-up – it was the Captain's responsibility to lead the group and they appear to know the routine. In the first 3 minutes, Samuel and Edward were busy setting up markers on the court. Hannah modelled arm circling to warm up the shoulder joint and mimic actions required in practice but there appeared to be no quality

control from either Hannah or the pre-occupied coaches. Some players were doing arm circles with correct technique, but 5 out of 12 players were not arm circling correctly. Coaches still had no interest in intervening in this part of the lesson. Suddenly, Hannah loudly clapped her hands to signal that the team were to change to a new activity. She repeated the hand clapping every time the team was to change what they were doing.

As the players continued to perform sometimes effective, sometimes ineffective warm-up actions, Edward just watched, but did not intervene or correct them. As Assistant Coach, he, like the other assistant coaches observed, would not intervene unless directed to by the Head Coach. Samuel did not appear concerned about this part of the session, as he was busy setting up for a later activity. Edward was seemingly in charge, except that Hannah was leading the activities. There was no feedback given or hustle or positive modelling. Edward could give feedback, hustle or praise in place of the pre-occupied Samuel. Hannah is leading the team from the front, so she could not see the rest of the team or manage their activities. It would be reasonable to assume that she does not share the same technical knowledge as the coaches. As the person leading this phase of the coaching session, Hannah did not really have the capability (or positioning) to improve player learning. The coaches' lack of engagement seemed to indicate that they saw the warm-up as a way to raise heart rate, warm up the muscle groups and prevent injury, not as an opportunity for learning.

Less than 5 minutes into the session, Hannah switched to leading stretches (calf) standing in the centre of the court. The other players found their spot on the court for stretching – still appearing routinized. Up to this point, there had been no direct instruction or management from the coaches since the warm-up commenced. Stretching continued, with perhaps only 2 players demonstrating good form. No input was provided by coaches or intervention to correct performance.

Well into the eighth minute of the session, players are standing still, doing static stretches, lower body, upper body, arms. After the tenth minute, they segue into fitness and conditioning activities. About 12 minutes into the session, Samuel moved over to the team. He looked as though he was preparing for the warm-up to end. He gave instructions about the next drill, which was a spike-dig drill on the same side of the net.

Figure 32. Head Coach Samuel is controlling the spike-dig drill. Assistant Coach Edward is standing beside him to hand him the balls out of the basket.

In Figure 32, Samuel adopted a player's role in the drill, controlling the pace and direction of the spikes. He struck the ball with ferocious intensity from a short distance towards the receiver, with his only comment being "again", "not good", "again". Only 1 player was actively involved, with 2 more players engaged should the dig make it over the net. The remaining 9 players were standing on the other side of the court, watching. No feedback was provided regarding body positioning, or why some digs were successful, and others weren't. Samuel did not confer with Edward, who was right beside him, handing out the next ball from a trolley. The non-engaged players occasionally fetched the balls from around the court. The dominant coaching behaviours in this phase were direct management (47.05%) and silence (34.01%).

Figure 33. Furat Women's team match play – the coach was not watching much of the game and was talking to a member of one player's family.

Once the team commenced full match practice, Samuel removed himself from active play and stood to the side (in top left of picture), as can be seen in Figure 31. He stood near a family member who had arrived early to watch the women's team train. Samuel appeared more focussed on conversation than on the game. Once again, it appeared that the Iraqi coaches put time and energy into building relationships with extended family members to ensure the continuing participation of female players in the sport.

Throughout the match, there were instances when nothing went right. Not one good serve, not one good return. There were plenty of opportunities for specific performance feedback from either coach. Match play was characterised by silence and indirect management. A few minutes later, one rally was actually very good. Again, the coaches said nothing - no positive feedback or praise was uttered. Samuel finally stopped talking with family members and was now watching the game with hands on hips. With another poor serve, Samuel speaks up and says, "your serving is terrible". Intra-raters decided that this was an example of general negative feedback. Samuel shortly reiterates to the team – "just focus on your serve", which was coded as corrective feedback.

Figure 34. Furat Women's team stretching in warm-down. Some were stretching, some were reading or talking.

As the Furat women's team moved into a warm-down, it appeared to show the social side of their team training, which was indicated in the PSPP findings in Chapter 4 – that participating in sport, being good at sport and being part of a team was important to female players. Only at the end of the training session, while Samuel was still greeting and talking with more family members who arrived to collect their sisters and daughters, did Edward lead a phase. He asked the girls to stop stretching, to lie down, close their eyes and then he said “just relax, imagine you are at the beach and relax” – seemingly practicing mindfulness. Samuel appeared to have delegated the warm down to Edward while he continued to chat to family members constantly arriving and to pack away the equipment so the next group (Basketball players) could use the same gym. He had elected to “pack up”, keep family members and other sports hall users happy rather than deliver any key, take-away messages to the team. A player finally asked a question of Edward – but it was “Can I go get some water?”. He responded “Ok, ok”. The players were a captive audience at this point of the coaching session. It was a perfect opportunity to reiterate key coaching points, remind players of areas to focus upon and any other key messages between now and next time. No such opportunity was taken. As the group started to disperse, Edward came back to the players still in the circle and asked team captain Hannah to come back, as she had started to leave the gym with a relative. Family members were now intermingling with players. They appeared to be operating on the assumption that the session was over. Some people had started to leave. Some were still stretching. After speaking with Edward, Hannah asked the remaining players to line up once again on the side-

line. “Everybody on the line”, she said. They came back together and said “Sport, hey!!!”, which was a team cheer. After this cheer, everyone was permitted to leave.

5.5.2 Phases of Coaching

Figure 35. Furat Women’s team – Phase of coaching as percentage of coaching session.

As with other teams in this competition, Furat’s coaches spent a lot of time in “training” states rather than “playing” states. No form of questioning – either from the coaches or the players – was observed or coded. Asking questions appeared to be completely off limits. Asking questions to check for player understanding, or to invite input, was not part of Furat women’s coaching experience. While it is arguable that the 33.96% of technical practice may have included a type of “functional practice”, where “re-enactment of isolated simulated game incidents might occur” (Cushion et al, 2012, p211), there were simply not enough team members involved for these practice drills to be considered “game-like”.

5.5.3 Primary Coaching Behaviours

Figure 36. Primary coaching behaviours for the Furat Women's team as a percentage of coaching session.

Furat's coaches spent almost half the session directly managing the players in the technical activities, while silent more than one third of the session. Knowing that Hannah led the warm-up and the fitness activities accounted for the higher proportion of time where the players were not interacting with the coaches. Samuel, as a former elite player and a current Iraqi international coaching staff member, inserted himself as a skilled player into every technical practice drill. As with other clubs, this funnelled players 1, 2 or 3 at a time into the task with him, causing others to wait. Furat women's players didn't have as much rest as other teams (3.36%) because they assisted Edward in retrieving balls from around the gym.

5.6 Discussion of Observational Analysis Findings

Volleyball is a sport that requires supreme physical fitness and technical proficiency. A player must have anaerobic and aerobic capacities and consequent capacity for making hard and fast movements in defensive and offensive plays. The players' physical strength and conditioning has a significant impact on the team's ability to apply tactics during play. The evidence collected in the video recorded analysis of coaching sessions shows that developing

player fitness and physical conditioning is a priority in both men's and women's teams, but slightly more so in the men's teams.

Dejlah Men's team had almost 62% of the coaching session spent on fitness and technical training which was characterised by more direct management. During the session, the head coach maintained an angry face, pointed his finger in gestures of disappointment and used feedback such as "not good" with the players. Their warm-up was 5.76% while the warm down was 5.7% of the total coaching time. In contrast, the Dejlah women's team had a lower proportion of time - 57% - of coaching session spent on fitness and technical training which was characterised by more direct management. During the session, especially when the players made mistakes, the head coach again provided negative feedback – like "not good enough" - with angry facial and hand gestures. The warm-up was 7.02% of total coaching time and comprised running and stretching, while the warm down was 5.01% of mostly stretching.

Furat Man's team had almost 51% of the coaching session spent in fitness and technical training, which was characterised by more direct management. During the session, 35.03% had minimal coach feedback, occasionally a word like "not good" was directed toward the players, especially when they made a mistake in the skills. Warm up comprised 16.46% of the session whilst the warm down comprised 9.75%. In contrast, the Furat women's team had almost 50% of the coaching session spent in fitness and technical training, which was characterised by more direct management. During the fitness and technical training, the coach's feedback was limited to "not good" when the players made mistakes. 50% of the coaching session was performed in silence and utilised indirect management. The warm-up totalled 11.39% of the coaching session and comprised of running and stretching while the warm down was mostly stretching, taking 3.36% of the total coaching time.

The overwhelming statistic for all four teams was the total time spent in silence or receiving negative general feedback on performance (such as "not good enough"). Hustle only appeared in technical drills, if at all and again it was mostly negative. There was no coach hustle in warm-up at all. Coaches left the content and quality of the warm-up to the Captain in most cases and had little input. With the exception of the Furat women's team coach, Samuel, who asked the team to "just focus on your serve", no additional performance feedback was given in game time. Western coaching literature has established the primary importance of providing general positive praise, specific performance feedback and encouragement to players in order to develop their knowledge and sport-specific skills (Cushion et al., 2012; Lyle and Cushion, 2016). The analysis of all four teams showed that questioning and providing answers, giving feedback and providing verbal cues was not part of any team's coaching practice,

regardless of gender. The coaches have the potential to improve player's knowledge through detailed and specific feedback designed to address player weaknesses. Written planning and reflection upon sessions could help address existing problems and challenges so that coaches could motivate players, encouraging effective and efficient responses (Cassidy et al., 2018). Video analysis indicated that the coaches did not use planning documents during sessions, write notes or reflect on the sessions. The coaching practices in these Iraqi teams could become more effective if coaches were to keep track of players' needs and performances and develop clear strategies to address areas requiring improvement.

Westrheim and Manger (2014) stated that forming a positive and effective player-coach relationship can help to effectively manage coaching sessions. The strategies and approaches adopted by the coaches can have a profound impact on the players' skills and potential. This helps to keep players motivated to continue attending training in order to enhance their capabilities. The lack of coach conversation with players was contrasted with the time spent talking with family members who arrived in the hall to watch, often during game time. The video analysis indicated that coaching practices in Iraq entail developing and maintaining strong relationships with players' families, a *strong coach – family relationship*, to ensure the wider family supports the players' involvement, particularly for the women's teams. There was direct evidence that family was extremely important to the coaching staff as they diverted their attention from the players in session to address the needs of family members in attendance. This suggests that there may also be socio-political and cultural-discursive reasons as to why the coaches, particularly the male coaches of women's teams, did not provide much spoken feedback – even negative - as there could be a high possibility of embarrassing the players in front of their families and embarrassing their families by appearing to disappoint the coach. Such embarrassment may end the female player's involvement in the sport.

Chapter 6 presents the findings from interviews with the eight coaches and 16 players (four from each team), in which their coaching philosophies, preferences for coaching, rationale for particular approaches and perceptions of their value are analysed.

6 INTERVIEW ANALYSIS

This investigation was concerned with coaches', assistant coaches' and players' perceptions of volleyball coaching and coaching practices to understand how and why they are *valued*, seeking to identify if there were differences in the way in which men and women are coached and what they value in terms of coaching philosophies, approaches and practices. This chapter analyses the interviews conducted with coaches and players of four Iraqi volleyball teams. These findings are presented according to identified themes, drawing upon concepts elicited from the review of sports coaching literature and the theoretical framework drawn from practice theory. The findings demonstrate both cohesion and disjuncture between player and coach perceptions of coaching quality and practice.

Using Nvivo, a total 20 codes were initially identified from player interviews and coach interviews. The player/coach codes were proposed, combined, reviewed and reassembled and interpreted into parent and child codes according to Braun and Clarke's (2006) six steps of thematic analysis (TA). These codes generated from the entire participant group were ultimately refined and presented here as six themes. These include the 1) Iraqi participant context, 2) coaching philosophy, 3) holistic coaching, 4) coaches' knowledge and experience, 5) coaching approaches and 6) player development. Recall that the full list of sub-themes were presented in Figure 13 from Chapter 3 is repeated here for convenience.

Name	Files	References
Participant Context	0	0
Coaching Philosophy	0	0
Autocratic_democratic coaching	20	41
Coaching hierarchy	7	13
Follow coach's plan	6	11
Coaching Approach	0	0
Fitness and skills	24	76
Coaching strategies and planning	17	32
Sport psychology aspect of coaching	6	6
Good results	9	11
Holistic Coaching	0	0
Player-coach relationships	21	38
Motivation_Team cohesion	15	27
Coach professional learning	0	0
Coaches' Knowledge_Experience	20	35
Player perception of coaching quality	15	42
Tactical aspects of coaching (TGFU)	16	34
Player Development	0	0
Players' opportunity to learn	11	17
Feedback	17	29
Player self-coaching	6	7
What players enjoy about training	16	17
Women's opportunities	3	3
Key quotes	17	29

6.1 The Participant Context

As recalled from Chapter 3, the interview participants were the four head coaches, four assistant coaches (n = 8) and four players from each team (n = 16), summarised as follows in Table 20. The coaches had a minimum of six years of coaching at this level and the players would have been playing for approximately 5 years. This seems short, compared to Western countries, but juniors do not have access to continuous club sport from young ages. Their opportunities to play at a competitive level are generally in secondary school and university.

Table 20

Player and Coach Interview Participants

Dejlah Men	Role	Dejlah Women
Zack	Player	Amy
Philip	Player	Matilda
Milo	Player	Tayla
Ollie	Player	Olivia
Max	Coach	Daniel
Michael	Assistant Coach	Victor
Furat Men	Role	Furat Women
Mathew	Player	Hannah
Murray	Player	Daisy
Stephen	Player	Sophia
Arthur	Player	Megan
Adam	Coach	Samuel
Mark	Assistant Coach	Edward

The interviews were conducted with the players and coaches between October and December during the main playing season. This followed the PSPP questionnaires (July) and pre-season filming (August) of all teams. This final phase of mixed method data collection used the interview schedule as shown in Appendices 2 and 3 and conducted and audio recorded over Viber (internet phone). The interviews were conducted in Arabic, transcribed into Arabic, then translated by the researcher into English.

Each player was asked to share background information at the interview's commencement to establish demographic data. All of the players were aged between 18 and 25 years and were concurrently university students. As explained earlier, elite sporting clubs are often resourced by educational institutions or coached by teachers and/or lecturers because of the understandably low levels of Iraqi Government funding for community sport, particularly outside of Baghdad. Elite players are most often young adults or university students. Playing sport in Iraq is more socially acceptable for students, especially for women. The players identified as having Shia or Sunni Muslim or Christian religion, with Iraqi or Kurdish ethnic identity. The coaches had Christian and Shia Muslim religious backgrounds and identified as Iraqi or Kurdish. The religious and ethnic backgrounds of the combined participant group impacted upon coach-player relationships and team cohesion. As will become evident in the following sections, vignettes from players in particular identified how not being from the right city or background impacted upon their relationship with their team and coaches. These aspects are not identified within particular teams to protect confidentiality and anonymity.

There were 13 semi-structured interview questions for players, canvassing their coaching preferences, their views on what makes them a successful individual player or a successful team, what builds team cohesion and what role the head coach and assistant coach plays in all of these concepts. The coaches were asked 12 similar, but not identical, questions. They were also asked about their planning habits, how they helped players achieve personal goals, what tactical and strategic approaches they foregrounded in training and what they believed made them an effective coach.

6.1.1 Resources for Volleyball

This section presents sub-themes around resources for volleyball, social issue and impact of war and the Iraqi volleyball federation. A defining feature of the participant context was the impact that war and widespread poverty had in undermining player participation. These teams were among the best national and regional clubs, yet coaches and players were all unpaid volunteers. The players noted resourcing, or material-economic, issues as barriers to success: they were short of equipment, the court surfaces could be better, and they lacked team uniforms other than a competition shirt.

We do not have enough equipment in the club. I told the union in volleyball and my club (about) the equipment, but they do not have it. (Matilda, interview).

If we have a championship, the club will give me only one T-shirt. (Olivia, interview)

RESEARCHER: Does your club provide you with team uniforms?

MEGAN: No (*embarrassed*) (interview).

Daniel, the Dejlah women's coach, explained:

We do not have enough equipment in the club. I told the union in volleyball (IVF) and my club that we need the equipment, but they do not have any (coach interview).

Daniel also noted that while championship experience is valuable for player experience, teams from northern Iraq often missed out because of the war and the lack of player income:

You know the championship is very important to the players to get more experience. My team did not go to another city because of the war in Iraq and, in some circumstances, the players (cannot go) without additional money from the club (Daniel, interview).

My training is not good because of the war in Iraq. In addition, we do not have financial money to go to another city too (Daisy, interview)

Tayla from Daniel's team also pointed to another issue besides money to travel:

Because Iraq has some issues, that's why it's very hard to get to the court. In addition, my team cannot go to Baghdad because it's scared (Tayla, interview).

The teams play and practice in northern Iraq, where the population is predominantly Kurdish and Sunni Muslim. Baghdad in southern Iraq has a mainly Shia Muslim population. The players' religious and ethnic identities are a factor in whether or not they feel safe in another region.

When asked whether the clubs could pay the players' transport fees, or any kind of stipend to support their playing careers, Daisy, from Furat Women's team, noted "we do not have money to go to another city" (Daisy, interview). Phillip, from Dejlah Men's team, stated that "players have no salary, and the coaches have to volunteer with the team" (Philip, interview). No-one got paid, not players, not coaches. Everyone is a volunteer. Volunteer sport succeeds all over the world, often with cash and in-kind donations from participating families but, in highly impoverished locations, such community financial underwriting of sport is difficult.

The findings here suggest that there is lack of money to support elite team sport competition. This could point to a lower position on government priority lists and a lack of available funding in the playing community. Edward, Assistant coach with Furat women's team explained "I like volleyball, that's why I help my team even as a volunteer for a long time because the government has no funding for the coaches" (Edward, coach - interview). As indicated in Chapter 2 and Chapter 5, coaching in Iraq is supported by Physical Education teachers in high schools and Sport Education lecturers in universities – these coaches are financially supported by their "day job" and gift their time and expertise to elite sport. Harkness (2012) asserted that financial support and management is a key factor for the successful execution of sport programs. Proper financial support for volleyball would be consistent with

the Iraq 2030 rebuilding program. Seeking and managing funds to support team budgets appears to be an ongoing financial concern. An adequate strategic planning process, risk management and clear accountability is required for improving the overall situation of the Iraqi volleyball federation.

6.1.2 Social Issues, Funding, and the Impact of War

The second sub-theme relating to Iraq's internal conflict and the resulting social issues and lack of funding, had a significant impact on players and coaches alike. A number of players indicated that they could not get enough matches, because "the war in Iraq is a big problem" (Daisy, player interview). These interviews were conducted in late 2017, before Mosul had been liberated from ISIS so there were many times that the players could not train at their own court, let alone travel to other clubs: "because of the war in Iraq, we were not allowed to go to the club for months" (Hannah, player interview).

The women players were most generous in their praise of their coaches, acknowledging that coaches were doing as much as they could under the circumstances. When Megan was asked if she trusted her head coach at Furat, Samuel, and thought their team was successful, she replied "yes, he is a good coach in my city, and yes, although the circumstances in Iraq ... (*voice trails off*)" (Megan, player interview).

Male players were more vocal in their criticism of the lack of Government funding for volleyball – the sport and the coaches. Murray, from Furat men's team, said "the government does not support the coaches in Iraq". He added "coaches have to go overseas to get more knowledge about volleyball" (Murray, interview). Stephen, also from Furat men's team, conceded that it would be very difficult to resource the sport in these times, "I guess to get new knowledge is not easy at the moment in Iraq" (Stephen, interview).

In just one case, there appeared to be some evidence of cultural division, that the player involved was very hesitant to talk about – differential treatment by the coach depending on ethnicity. For this extract, the player and team will be anonymised:

RESEARCHER: Do you trust your coach in his coaching talents?

PLAYER: (Silent, then laughing). Yes. (but not convincing)

RESEARCHER: Can you give me an example?

PLAYER: (embarrassed laughing) Hmmmmm

RESEARCHER: Believe me, nobody will hear your voice. What do you say about your coach?

PLAYER: My coach likes some players and does not care about others.

RESEARCHER: Why does your coach only help one or two players and not others?

PLAYER: It depends, I am not similar to my coach's group (*city, religion and ethnicity*). The coach tends to help the players who live in his city. I don't understand why the coach does not want to help more players.

RESEARCHER: Have you told your coach about this?

PLAYER: Yes, yes, I told him, and the coach's answer was "ok, just wait".

RESEARCHER: Are you sure that the coach helps some players while he doesn't care about others?

PLAYER: Yes, yes.

The player seemed to indicate that attempts to ask questions, ask for help or feedback would be "put off" by the coach, never to be actioned. This team, without revealing any specifics of the ethnicities, had just a few players whose culture, city, language and religion were different to the majority of the team and the coaches. The fact that the player was a long-time member of the team, despite describing marginalisation, points to the value of their playing skills and the willingness of the coaches and other team members to suspend broader cultural tensions to keep the team together.

Despite the war and its complications for team sport, remaining involved with volleyball was very important to all the participants. Everyone persisted, despite the safety risks and the hardship compounded by low levels of income. In Chapter 4, players across the four teams reported maximum average value for the importance of maintaining physical conditioning and physical strength and valued the physical side of themselves. The women's teams also had least variation in being proud of themselves (Dejlah women's) and Learning new sports skills (Furat women's). Being part of the club, despite the war, was an important part of their identity and provided the opportunity to acquire those things they value – new skills. For the men, least variation in the PSPP was recorded for the physical side of themselves and being satisfied with being a physical kind of person. Maintaining their connection with the clubs in times of conflict enabled them to continue to train, to work out, to draw identity support from the nature of the training that prioritised physiological training states and physical fitness.

6.1.3 Iraq Volleyball Federation

The sub-theme of war and the related budgetary restrictions appeared to have consequences for the Iraq Volleyball Federation (IVF). They were not able to host many in-country tournaments nor prepare Iraqi teams for international events. Players did not see this as a resourcing issue but one of lowered priority. Olivia said, “the federation does not have enough interest to do a championship between teams” (player interview). Such capability would require a solid deployment of monetary and non-monetary resources (such as political support and interest): these are not currently available. Murray noted that “the Iraqi volleyball union (IVF) is not good with volleyball players”. Several players noted that the federation organised ‘friendly matches’ for international representative players within Iraq but could not host championship tournaments that would bring international teams to Iraq. The federation is responsible for funding international players and coaches and handling the issues facing national representatives. However, the coaches and players thought the federation budget was insufficient to address these constraining issues. Murray also made the point that “the government does not support the coaches in Iraq” (player interview).

As discussed in Chapter 5, the coaching sessions were filmed towards the end of the pre-season, just before main competition started. This following exchange pointed to a concern about the communication between these top clubs, who fielded international players and coaching staff, and the Federation:

Yes, I cannot do a good program for the players because I do not know what the timing is for the Iraqi championship tournament... Iraq does not have a good union (Federation) in volleyball (Daniel, Dejlal women’s team).

The volleyball federation in Iraq does not support the coaches too (Adam, Head coach Furat Men’s team)

The federation was perceived as unable to support development within the sport. Phillip, from Dejlal men’s team, stated that “the Iraqi volleyball federation does not help coaches to improve in their knowledge, for example, during training courses overseas” (interview). Phillip also said that the IVF did not do enough to “look after volleyball in schools” (Phillip, interview), which he seemed to imply was necessary to improve the pipeline of players into elite volleyball.

Olivia, from Dejlah women's team stated, "the Iraqi volleyball federation does not engage in planning for teams in Iraq" (interview). She attributed much of her team's success to her coaches and was forthcoming in her opinion about the lack of support from the IVF in terms of resourcing and opportunities to compete:

My coach is good and supports the players, but the volleyball union (IVF) is not good with us...The union do not have enough interest to do a championship between teams (Olivia, player interview).

The players and coaches agreed that the IVF was in need of an adequate budget increase to ease financial restraints. This was crucial if national athletes and elite teams were to obtain adequate exposure either in-country or at external international events. A broadening of the IVF's focus, extended support for all stakeholders (current coaches and players, future players), resources (club facilities and funding) and competition opportunities were all specifically identified as essential.

6.2 Coaching Philosophy

A coaching philosophy is the basis upon which coaching decisions are made. Juariyah and Adi (2017) defined it as the principles, values and beliefs that guide characteristics and behaviour related to the individual's coaching practice: what to coach, how to coach and why they coach in that way. A coaching philosophy is also something that players possess - even if they are not aware of it – driving what they expect to see their coaches doing in their coaching relationship. This section presents sub-themes around autocratic and democratic coaching, coaching hierarchy and following the coaches' plan.

6.2.1 Autocratic and/or Democratic Coaching

When asked about whether or not he had autocratic or democratic coaches, Murray from Furat men's team replied "No, not democratic" (Murray interview, *with emphasis*). When pressed as to why, he replied "nobody can talk with the coaches about the skills or the programs in volleyball" (Murray, interview). Similarly, Amy from Dejlah women's team was embarrassed to admit that Daniel is autocratic: "He believes all the time that his own opinion is right" (Amy, interview). Players were also asked if they had any input into coaching sessions or the overall program:

RESEARCHER: Does your coach ask you about the volleyball program?

OLIVIA: No, no way!

RESEARCHER: How about input into the skills you do?

OLIVIA: No! (Dejlah women's player, interview).

Not every player, or coach, shared the opinion that the coaches “never” asked for their opinion or input into training. Daniel, coach of Dejlah Women's team, said that if they were all up to his expected standard – “if all of them have good skills, I will spend time talking about tactics.” (Daniel- coach, interview). For Daniel, being proficient in skills appeared to be more important than player input into the sessions.

Milo, from Dejlah men's team, thought that perhaps 5% of the time, his coach Michael would invite player input, but “it will be around nothing important” (Milo, interview). Phillip agreed that input “depends, maybe, yes” (Phillip, interview). Zack, gave an example “once, a long time ago, I told him (Michael), that we should play a game during training” (Zack, interview).

In Furat women's team, Hannah expressed a view that Samuel (and Edward) did invite player contributions:

My coaches are very good, and my coaches respect the players and help us. Sometimes, my coaches ask me for some ideas in training and around the program. (Hannah, player, interview).

From the video analysis in Chapter 5, there was evidence that Hannah led the team for warm up, fitness and warm down. Hannah led a well-known routine and determined things such as timing. But as discussed previously, the coaches were completely disinterested in these physiological training phases and her input appeared to be valued for freeing them up from team supervision to enable set up of the next activity or to talk to family members watching. Her position as team captain elevated her in status from just another player but also may not reflect the experiences of the rest of the team. The fact that Hannah is leading the warm-up is not evidence of democratic coaching. She is repeating what she has been drilled before and this is not an example of player input being invited into the design of each coaching session.

6.2.2 Coaching Hierarchy

The majority of players and assistant coaches agreed that autocratic coaching was the dominant coaching style. A related characteristic was that the Assistant coaches, like the players, also had little input into the coaching sessions.

Hmmm, I have to tell the truth, In Iraq the main coach does not ask the assistant coach about the volleyball program. The main coach is in charge of the program in the session and the assistant coach must follow the program (Victor, Assistant coach, Dejlal women's team, interview).

Daniel was asked: "Do you ask your players about the volleyball program?", to which he replied: "No way!". And then he was asked if he asks his assistant coach to contribute to the program, to which he replied: "No, sometimes I ask my assistant coach in general a question about volleyball but not about the program (Daniel, Head Coach, Dejlal women's team, interview). Amy reported a similar observation:

Our assistant coach was talking few weeks ago with the head coach, but he does not listen to the assistant coach, not to anybody (Amy, interview).

Victor from Dejlal Women's team also suggested that the assistant coach's role included collecting match statistics during competition:

...during the match, I have to check the points awarded to my team and if there is something important to tell the main coach to win. I have to check statistics for the hitter, setter, passes, everything! (Victor - assistant coach, interview).

The dominance of these practices around hierarchical relations and the resultant autocratic way of coaching suggests the teams did not know anything different: that these were normal and taken-for-granted practices. However, there was evidence to suggest that some assistant coaches and players held onto contrasting beliefs about the way coaching *could* transpire:

Hmmm, the main coach should have an open mind (to a new model), that involves talking with the assistant coach and with players too. The main coach should ask the assistant coach and the players for input into the volleyball

program, move far away from using this classic (traditional, autocratic) session”
(Mark, Assistant coach, interview).

Ammar, Chtourou, Abdelkarim, Parish, and Hoekelmann (2016) argued that the main aim of coaching is to provide athletes and other coaching staff with adequate tools for coping with change. They argued that effective coaches are responsible for meeting the needs of individual athletes and shifting the focus of coaching sessions when differences are evident in the performance of team – such as reaching pre-season fitness and conditioning expectations. Assistant coaching staff can do so much more in supporting the delivery of effective coaching sessions.

Different factors that caused the frustration among assistant coaches and players regarding the practices of head coaches are hierarchy’s issues, absence of proper and clear planning as well as style of communication. The relation between athlete and coach is considered as highly critical and badly effected by poor coaching practices. The different issues also resulted in emergence of some professional and ethical dilemmas.

6.2.3 Follow Coach’s Plan

The analysis of coaching sessions in Chapter 5 indicated that players are required to follow the coach's instruction. The coaches are all former elite players and were captured on video performing excellent volleyball skills. Their primary approach in sessions was to perform the skills for players to observe and then imitate. Coaches rarely spoke to the players at length, nor did players or assistant coaches talk about the skills during coaching sessions.

In these interviews, coaches did not contradict the video evidence. They were asked about planning responsibilities and the division of labour within the coaching team. This exchange between the researcher and Max, head coach of Dejlal men’s team, gives a clear insight into how the coaches perceived these aspects:

MAX: I have to prepare everything! I have to get the players fit. I have to coach their skills. I have to do everything for the team to achieve its goal ... I have to create the plan so that the players can improve step by step in volleyball.

RESEARCHER: Do you ask the assistant coach to contribute to the volleyball program?

MAX: No, it's my work and I know what I need in each session for the players. The assistant coach has to follow me and help the players to improve in volleyball.

RESEARCHER: Do you ask your players to have input into the volleyball program?

MAX: No way! All of the program is under my control and nobody can do it except me (Max - coach interview).

Michael, the Dejlah Men's assistant coach, agreed:

It is not my work. The main coach is the only one who can make plans for the players ... I just have to give a hand to the players to help them improve in volleyball" (Michael - coach interview).

When asked if he had input into adapting skills and drills to help the players during a coaching session, Michael added "it depends on the session and the part of the program (we are up to). It's not my work. It is for the main coach". When pressed further, with another example of ways in which he could possibly debrief or make suggestions to a program underway, Michael insisted: "it is not my work! It is only the main coach who can do it". The suggestion that Michael might have knowledge to contribute or a responsibility to co-design a program with Max appeared to make him nervous and resistant. When asked what he would do if he acquired some new knowledge about coaching volleyball – from overseas or his own research - Michael replied in apparent exasperation: "even if I get new knowledge, the main coach will not allow me to design a plan for the players." When asked if he thought he should be allowed to, Michael said: "no, it is not the right idea" (coach interview). To usurp the role of the head coach was not something he would support in this interview.

Edward, the assistant coach with Furat women's team also replied that he would follow Samuel's plan. However, he seemed able to act with some agency, providing his coaching opinion when sessions were in play. Edward took a role in the Furat women's warm down, and the team captain was responsible for leading the warmup and fitness exercises (which included modelling and speaking to the team in place of the coach). Edwards said: "it is my job to support the players and follow the main coach's program". When asked if he thought he assisted the players to meet their goals, he replied:

It is not my job. I am following the main coach. I support the players with their skills and talking with the players. I also help my players if they need transport (i.e., Edward pays for it) (Edward - coach interview).

Mark, the assistant coach with Furat men's team, stated that his role was "... to help the coach, look after the players and support them" (Mark - coach interview). The assistant coaches' responses seemed to indicate that a holistic care component was part of their role but designing the season plan and the coaching sessions was off limits. Giving feedback to the main coach about a plan's success seemed difficult and unacceptable.

Coaches are required to do more than just get players fit and teach technical skills. Coaches have a responsibility for athlete development and to assist them to attain their goals. The coaching teams appeared to share responsibility for holistic care, but everyone- players and assistant coaches alike - must follow the coach's plan.

6.3 Coaching Approach

A coaching approach could entail a great many things. From the interview data, the codes aligning with the theme of coaching approach included fitness and skills, coaching strategies and planning, sport psychology as an aspect of coaching and good results.

6.3.1 Fitness and Skills

The coaches generally viewed themselves responsible for teaching technical skills and developing player fitness and conditioning. Their comments about the focus and priority given to player fitness appears consistent with the proportion of time spent in physiological training states. Shulman (1986) argued that traditional training methods, such as fitness and drills, are highly valuable. Traditional training methods often begin with a warm-up period followed by fitness development, continuing into different drill activities related to individual or group-based performance. This type of training is useful for the coaching of proficient technical skills.

Daniel responded to a range of questions how he helps players to achieve their goals for improvement and team success with: "I have to teach my players fitness, and skills, and then play volleyball" (Daniel - coach interview). To him, the importance of fitness was clear.

When asked how he prioritized areas of fitness and conditioning, Max replied: "it depends on the players. If they need speed, or endurance for the session" (Max - coach interview). He dismissed the possibility of achieving speed and endurance through game play

as well as exercises, saying, “I do not think so. I develop fitness so we can play the game” (Max - coach interview).

Most coaches believed fitness was an integral part of the weekly coaching session. Ironically, Victor, assistant coach with Daniel from Dejlal women’s team, stated

In my opinion, players in volleyball should improve in fitness (by themselves), far away from the coaches. Coaching should be for the tactics; the coaches should **teach** the players. (coach interview, emphasis added).

Victor was the only coach to air this view, but several players argued the same. Tayla said: “my coaches have good strategies for improving fitness” (Tayla - player interview). Stephen felt coaches could be more effective by: “just spending more time with the team to improve skills and fitness” (Stephen - player interview). Matilda, from Dejlal, thought her coaches did a good job with fitness:

MATILDA: My coach is good, especially when we have good skills and fitness exercises.

RESEARCHER: I watched your video and noticed that your coaches seemed more interested in technical drills than fitness.

MATILDA: Well, it depends. (But) I think my coaches are more interested in drills than fitness (player interview).

Megan, from Furat women’s team, also thought that drills were important and that “my coaches have good skills in volleyball and have different tactics in volleyball”, which she also indicated she valued when asked what was her favourite part of coaching: “the warm-up and the exercises with the ball that’s important” (player interview).

Tayla thought her coaches were happier when the team appeared to be getting fitter, as they linked fitness with good team results. This was interesting given the thread above, as the training phases results (Figure 18) indicated Dejlal women’s team spent the last time on fitness. Phillip from Dejlal Men’s team said

Fitness is very important for me. My coach spends a long time in fitness (35% of training) because it is very important for volleyball players...Volleyball needs more fitness than football (Phillip - player interview).

The development of fitness, comprising physical strength and conditioning for volleyball, is critical for success and proficient game playing. The players seem to realize the

value of fitness and enjoy participating in these training activities. Improving fitness also supported their elite athlete identity, contributing to the all-important physical strength and conditioning sub-domains of physical self-worth. Ollie, another player from Dejlal Men's, emphasised the importance of fitness when asked about his favourite part of coaching:

RESEARCHER: What is your favourite part about coaching sessions?

OLLIE: Fitness part which is very important in the volleyball. fitness is important to everybody.

Some players suggested that technical drills were either more important or of equal value to fitness. Olivia from Dejlal women said, "I prefer drills with the ball. Doing the skills is very important to me" (Olivia - player interview). When asked what was something specific that the coaches had done to make her a successful player, Olivia replied "the first thing they taught me was how to move (i.e., positioning). They helped me with this a long time ago" (player interview).

Fitness was a clear priority for coaches, as evidenced by the amount of time allocated to physiological phases of training in the video analyses, and it was also a player favourite. This is returned to later in Section 6.6.4.

As the coaches and players are giving preferences to strength, conditioning and fitness. In addition to tactical and technical volleyball requirement, speed, power and strength are considered as critical factors responsible for determination of competitive performance. It is essential to develop concurrent power, strength and fitness to underpin the performance of sports. Nonetheless, it is difficult to execute effective practices of strength and conditioning because of absence of relevant expertise, facilities, equipment and time. Even though, opportunities for professional development of strength and conditioning and fitness are limited in Iraq. Hence, players and coaches are required to embrace relevant training for up skilling of players. A well-structured program of training can enhance the stamina and agility of players. It is useful for development of physical trait for playing the full potential of volleyball.

6.3.2 Coaching Strategies and Planning

Although players felt that the coaches were autocratic and did not seek their input, this does not mean coaches did not consider their athlete's needs when designing sessions. Daniel, from Dejlal women's team, was asked how he planned sessions as the video analysis indicated that he did not consult written plan or take notes:

I don't need to – it's all in here (pointing to his head)...it all depends upon the players, what my team needs in order to meet its goals. I think (this) female team need more skills especially serving and defence” (Daniel- coach interview).

Dejlah women's team was the one with the unusually high proportion of game time, compared to the other three teams, and their technical drills phase also prioritized serving and defence. When asked if he thought that the team could meet its priorities in fitness and particular skills through small-sided games, or combined together, he replied: “I am focusing on fitness and ball skills”. Daniel shared Max's view that match play was the place to learn tactics – not coaching sessions: “the championship is more important for the player to get experience” (Daniel - coach interview).

Hannah, from Furat women's team, noticed that Samuel nor Edward tended not to use written notes:

RESEARCHER: do your coaches use a notebook in the session?

HANNAH: Not really, but sometimes my coaches have one for the matches.

Milo, a Dejlah men's team player, commented that: “each of the coaches have their own private style. It's actually impossible to have the same style all the time. They shouldn't be using the same strategy with every player” (Milo - player interview). His comments suggested that the coaches did not alter their strategies for different purposes, or different players and were driven by routine:

It's not right, because it's routine without improving us as volleyball players...The volleyball players get some fitness and skills, but the coach must change a bit in training...The coaches stay with the traditional program and strategy...All coaches believe they are a good coach and understanding everything. Also, they believe their opinion is true all the time. That's why the coaches alone decide what we do (Milo, player interview).

Max confirmed that it was his job (alone) to plan training and that his approach was to work with the players “step by step to improve in volleyball” (Max - coach interview). Max was unequivocal in his view that neither assistant coaches nor players could co-design the training sessions or season plan. He alone would decide what player should achieve and how

they would get there. Some players were happy with this situation. Stephen, from Furat men's team said:

My coaches support players to reach their goals. That's a good idea from the coaches. It's a very important thing for coaches to do, for example, they told me to come over to the training earlier to improve in my fitness and skills (Stephen - player interview).

Each head coach mentioned that part of their remit was to help players reach their goals, but strategic collaboration and co-design were absolutely refuted, as Ollie confirmed:

RESEARCHER: How does your coach use *your* feedback to improve *his* coaching?

OLLIE: I do not think he does. My coach does not use feedback from the players.

6.3.3 Sport Psychology as an Aspect of Coaching

Fox and Corbin (1989) defined sport psychology as the impact of the mind on the athlete's performance. Kuhlmann (2016) argued that building psychology into coaching is useful when enhancing motivation, self-confidence and relaxation under high pressure. As discussed in Chapter 2, psychological training can begin with an educative phase, during which athletes can learn about the impact and benefit of different psychological skills on the team's overall performance. Players then need to acquire and develop strategies through simulation, repetition and application in competition. Psychological training can also be used for developing greater self-awareness. The interview findings related to sport psychology as an aspect of coaching indicated that for Iraqi volleyball teams, psychology sessions were generally absent.

Adam (Furat men's team), Assistant Coach Edward (Furat women's team) and Assistant Coach Victor (Dejlah women's team) agreed that "we do not have psychology in our coaching sessions" (various - coach interviews). Amy from Dejlah women's team confirmed that "we do not have any training with the coach in psychology" (Amy - player interview). Similarly, Milo from Dejlah men's team said, "players don't have a session in psychology in coaching, but a lot of coaches talk about psychology during the championship" (Milo - player interview).

Some players recognised the importance of developing psychological skills and sought outside means of learning. Hannah from Furat women's team reported watching seminars on YouTube: "I watched YouTube about some training in psychology with my friends in the

volleyball team” (Hannah - player interview). Matthew from Furat men’s team agreed that “psychology is very important for the players and the team” (Matthew - player interview).

Miller and Levy (1996) asserted that sport psychology is useful for athletes in diverse settings. Some relaxation and mental strategies can enhance performance. Psychological strategies can enable players to overcome challenges, such as coping with competition pressure, staying motivated with ongoing exercise programs and enabling them to enjoy their sports, particularly under trying circumstances such as pursuing high level competition in a war-torn country. Edward’s attempt at mindfulness in the Furat women’s warm-down could be regarded as an example of psychological skill training but the players seemed perplexed by his request and not many players actually did what was asked – suggesting it was a “one off” for the video recording. There appeared to be more scope to enhance the extent to which sport psychology was used in coaching. Sport psychology allows the development of volleyball players who can utilise different psychological tools required to become proficient to reach the top of the sport.

6.3.4 Good Results

‘Good results’ was a theme that was interlinked with codes concerning coach strategies and planning, fitness and skills, and autocratic coaching/ follow coach’s plan. According to Doozan and Bae (2016), the coach has a direct influence on the performance of players, improving their ability to perform as well as their competition attitudes (which should also comprise psychological training). The interview findings thus far show that teams were expected to have a high level of fitness (strength and conditioning) and excellent technical skills. The video analysis pointed to the majority of players having excellent techniques and working hard in significant proportions of their coaching sessions in fitness activities.

Several coaches justified their coaching approaches and planning around “the team needs it to get a good result” (Max, Dejlal men’s team coach, interview). Mark, assistant coach from Dejlal women’s team thought that his team: “achieved good outcomes” (Mark - coach interview). Megan, from Furat women’s team, thought that “my coaches have good results in volleyball” (player interview).

Samuel pointed to “good results” as the basis of his coaching approach. When he was asked how he helped his players meet their goals, instead of revealing insights into his coaching approaches, he said: “I started work with the volleyball club in 1994 and now I have got 6 times the best team in Iraq, 7 times the second best (runner-up) team and twice the third best team”

(coach interview). Samuel put forward that his record as a coach stood for itself and good results justified his program design.

Matilda from Dejlah women's team also appeared prepared to accept her coach Daniel's approaches to coaching, including "being angry" because of their achievements as a team:

MATILDA: my coach is angry person, especially when we have a game or some serious exercises.

RESEARCHER: is it good idea from the coaches to get angry with the players?

MATILDA: sometimes, yes.

RESEARCHER: Do you believe your team is a good team?

MALNILDA: yes. Especially, after beating many teams.

Vollmer and Curtner-Smith (2016) suggested that perceptions of the effectiveness of the coach increase when athletes attain successful sport performance, which could be measured by win-loss ratio and the proportion of representative players in the team. Of the 6 normally functioning clubs in northern Iraq, the four teams from these two clubs were consistently the top performing and, despite not being located in Baghdad, featured current international players in every team. Given these outcomes, it could suggest that coaches do not deviate from 'proven' successful approaches justified by 'good results', despite players and some assistant coaches wishing they would.

6.4 Holistic Coaching Practices

Cassidy et al. (2016) suggested that holistic coaching practices stem from a coaching philosophy that incorporates other roles and practices for a coach. These are understood as holistic practice (Cassidy et al., 2016) or coaching care (Cronin & Armour, 2019). The eight coaches were asked to describe their coaching philosophy, and the 16 players were asked specific questions around what they liked about coaching, ways in which their coach helped them improve and so on. This theme is discussed according to the evidence of player-coach relationships and motivation and team cohesion.

6.4.1 Player/Coach Relationships

When asked about the scope of his role as head coach, Adam (Furat men's team) said: "my job is to help the players with what they need and look after them...to support the positive

things and try to reduce the negative things in their life” (Adam - coach interview). Adam seemed very aware that the context of disruption to their lives could impact upon their ability to remain in the team. He knew that he could make a difference to the players’ experiences of being in the team. Stephen from Furat men’s team noted: “the good thing from the coaches is that they help all players in the life. And players also should help and respect each other too” (Stephen - player interview). A number of players noted that their coaches took time to get to know their families, hosted BBQs and get-togethers for the team in mutually suitable locations (e.g., picnic in the park) and engaged in what could be regarded as team building – more of which are discussed in the next section.

Edward (Assistant coach with Furat women’s team) raised a slightly different point about player/coach relationships when coaching women: “Talking with the players is very important, especially with the female players because of the culture in Iraq. For females, it is not easy to do sport” (Edward - assistant coach interview). Edward seemed to believe that keeping communication channels open with women players would give early indication of any problems, potentially preventing loss of women players due to these cultural constraints.

6.4.2 Motivation and Team Cohesion

Holistic or ‘humanistic’ coaching approaches effectively balance chasing good results with overall player development. Within this approach, an important feature is the creation of a supportive and effective atmosphere, inducing team cohesion. Omiya et al. (2014) argued that creating a cohesive atmosphere enables the conservation of energy, training and playing in a relaxed manner and reducing stress during competition. Both coaches and players were asked how they felt coaches developed team cohesion, or whether they felt that the team had cohesion. Phillip’s answer to this question was “no”, adding further that he felt the coach “did not encourage the players” (Phillip - player interview).

Matilda identified a range of ways that her coaches motivated and supported the players in Dejlah women’s team: “the coaches encourage us and support the players with their studies. They have even invited all of the players to go outside for a picnic too” (Matilda - player interview). Olivia thought that team cohesion had been built up over many years, as the team had been together for a long time: “we help each other and my coach has been the coach for us (team) for years” (Olivia - player interview). She added that her coach has motivated her in her training by outlining her future potential: “For example, my coach told me, I will be an international player in the future” (Olivia - player interview).

Socialising with families was identified as an important way of building team cohesion, as well as managing the complex cultural relations and practices that permit women to participate in sport. Olivia said that:

The players help each other because we live in same area and we know each other. Even with our families too. Our coaches are living in same area and they like help the players (Olivia - player interview).

Sophia said: “my coach helps all the players and makes the player to like each other. We live in same area and we know each other as friends and families” (Sophia - player interview). Daisy added: “players support each other and we even know each other by our families” (Daisy - player interview) “Helping the players” had been variously revealed as providing finances, offering transport, ensuring female players travelled safely to and from venues and in these cases, putting on social events, not just for players and coaches but for entire families. Jenny (2013) confirmed that a high-quality relationship is based on the foundation of trust which becomes the precursor to athletes becoming receptive towards the life skill messages being tacitly shared by their coaches.

The coach-player-family relationships evident in these interview findings show the hallmarks of good interpersonal knowledge of the coaches, which according to Cote and Gilbert (2009), includes communication, personal availability and trust building. The coaches put much effort into socialising with players and their families to build trust and rapport and to assure the families that players were in good hands. The findings show that their remit as coaches is to provide assistance not only during practice sessions but also to guide them in situations outside of their sporting relationship. A high-quality interpersonal relationship between coaches and players helped them to remain focused on their objective as high performance athletes and assists with whole-team motivation.

6.5 Coach Professional Learning

Experienced and effective coaches can foster an environment or climate of enjoyment, promoting positive opportunities for growth and encouraging social interactions. Martens (2012) asserted that when there is a void of adequate coach education or opportunities for professional learning, coaches rely on their personal experience and prior knowledge when leading their coaching initiatives. Olson (2014) argued that professional learning of coaches can occur in a combination of informal and formal situations. In this study, the primary form of coach professional learning appeared to be head coaches mentoring assistant coaches, in an

apprentice-in-waiting style, as described by Lyle (2002). This theme is further explored via the sub-themes of coach knowledge and playing experience, players' perceptions of coaching quality, and tactical aspects of coaching, including findings around game-based coaching models such as TGfU.

6.5.1 Coach Knowledge and Playing Experience

The coach's interviews indicated that the four main coaches believed they know what they are doing and are delivering the best possible program for the players. All coaches were former elite players, and one was on the international men's coaching staff. The dissenting views came from some assistant coaches and male players. The female players were very reluctant to criticize their coaches, either avoiding the question about their coach's knowledge, or saying very tentative things when pressed such as Amy admitting: "he could ask the players more" (Amy - player interview).

Milo had clear opinions about the apparent stagnation in his Dejlah coach's knowledge:

I told you, coaches still have the same routine in volleyball, and it's been the same program for long time. The coaches teach their players the same skills which they gained when they played the volleyball a long time ago. (Milo - player, interview).

Michael, the Dejlah assistant coach supported Milo's thinking:

I wish (he) had more recent knowledge and modern thinking in volleyball. I want him to move far away from this classic program. I wish he would not transfer the same volleyball program now to these players that he learned playing volleyball for a long time" (Michael - assistant coach interview).

Victor from Dejlah women's team raised the idea that watching other teams - such as the international Italian team - might offer new strategies and tactics, but he was adamant that new knowledge would not come from the players: "my players do not have more experience or knowledge than the coaches" (Victor - assistant coach interview). His idea that watching other teams on the internet to learn new things was shared by the players. Milo said:

To be honest...the coaches must change a bit in their training by getting on to websites. It's very easy for coaches to know more about volleyball by

connecting with social media. Social media is everywhere but our coaches still follow one way and the use the same routines (Milo - player interview).

Michael from Dejlah men's team could see the internet having an impact on coaches' knowledge: "I think the future will change a lot because of the internet and the media will change [how we do things] in the future" (Michael - assistant coach interview). This could overcome the main barrier identified by Zack from this team. Zack argued that: "because Iraq has no contact with the other countries, that's why volleyball in Iraq is not good" (Zack – player interview). Social media and the internet could re-establish contact with volleyball clubs, associations and communities overseas. The finding implied that even though Iraqi volleyball coaches are engaged in some knowledge seeking and knowledge transfer behaviour, some barriers were present related to the accessibility of sport science for instance. Successful knowledge transfer required direct communication to these sources and many players thought that their coaches did not engage with freely available knowledge over the internet. It was clear that their access to high performance centres, such as the FIV high performance centre in Bahrain, was limited, but self-education seeking behaviour by coaches were not indicated in these findings.

6.5.2 Players' Perception of Coaching Quality

Martens (2012) confirmed that coaches should teach different skills such as facilitation, negotiation, problem solving, as well as motivating and teaching. This could mean providing guidance to less experienced players, by developing their trust, as well as modelling positive coaching behaviours. The players identified quality routines as indicators of coaching quality, or "Good coaching" as they described it. Tayla identified "good coaching" as "when my coaches are serious with exercises and good training is had with all the team" (Tayla- player interview). Tayla's comment was interesting as the video analysis had shown that all four teams had long periods of waiting around for participating in the technical drills, because of the limited number of players who could be involved at once with their head coach controlling it.

Ollie, from Dejlah men's team, appeared to want more exercises too: "The coaches (need) to give me more programs to do and to support me to improve in my skills and fitness" (Ollie – player interview). The male players were more likely to identify what they thought was a weakness or area needing improvement with their coaches' repertoire. Milo in particular had a lengthy response to this question:

To be honest, the training is very important for players to improve more in volleyball. We get some fitness and skills, but the coach must change a bit in their training. Thanks to websites, it's very easy for the volleyball coaches to know more about volleyball. They can connect (with other coaches) through social media. Social media is everywhere but the coaches still coach in one way with the same routine. Maybe it's difficult to change because of the circumstances (the war). But the coaches stay with a traditional program and strategy (Milo, player interview).

As will be discussed shortly, players were very willing to do their own research on YouTube, but the coaches did not seem to be doing the same.

One last point to note about players' perceptions of coaching quality was that giving feedback, which is addressed in more detail shortly, was *not* identified as part of quality coaching by the women players. When it was noted that her coach did not verbally encourage the players, Amy laughed and said: "sometimes, the coach has some nice words, for example 'good serving' (but) my coaches do not have time to explain more" (Amy – player interview). When asked to pinpoint what she liked about her coach's coaching, Amy said: "He is a good man, and everyone likes his attitude" (Amy – player interview). Women players appeared very reluctant to even admit that they had a perspective on how good their coaches were, let alone how they could be better, and generally praised their coaches, even when contrasting prompts were provided as a consequence of the video analysis.

6.5.3 Tactical Aspects of Coaching – (No) Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU)

Gilbert, Gallimore and Trudel (2009) asserted that there are six integral elements of Teaching Games for Understanding also known by the acronym as TGfU. The elements include teaching the whole game, then breaking the game down into simple formats, then progressively increasing the level of complexity. The participants are recognised as intelligent game performers, where all learners are important and should be involved, participants are required to know something about the subject matter, in this case, about volleyball. And finally, coaches should match the challenge to the skill level of participants.

The findings related to tactics, specifically looking for evidence of TGfU approaches, indicated that *none* of the teams had experienced a TGfU approach. When asked "do you use teaching games for understanding with your players?", Edward replied: "What's that?". After explaining that it means you can use games more in training, even to develop fitness and skills, he replied: "No, it is not the right one" (Edward - assistant coach interview). Samuel, the head

coach of Furat women's, was asked if TGfU could assist with developing players' game play during training sessions. He replied: "No way. It is not possible to use game play in training" (Samuel, coach interview). When asked if he could use TGfU to enhance skill development, again he replied: "No way. I have to teach my players fitness, then skills, and after that, they can play a volleyball game" (Samuel, coach interview). Max, from Dejliah men's team, also stated that "I do not think that, in Iraq, you can use TGfU. For me, I use fitness and skill development to be able to play a volleyball game" (Max, coach interview). Adam, head coach of Furat men's team seemed to know a little bit about TGfU (that is, that such a thing exists) but not enough to implement into his own practice:

RESEARCHER: can you use games to improve your players in skills and fitness?

ADAM: No way, maybe with kids but not with young adults. If it's possible, I need more training and more knowledge to know about TGfU.

RESEARCHER: Are you sure TGfU is only for the children, not for young adults?

ADAM: hmmm I think I have a lack of knowledge about TGfU, I need more knowledge to know more about the TGFU and about how it relates to volleyball. (Adam, coach interview)

Several players showed minimal understanding of TGfU concepts, mostly gleaned from YouTube videos and watching other international teams. They were not convinced that TGfU was useful. When Phillip was asked what he thought about TGfU, he said: "no, it's not correct. I like the Brazillian and Italian approaches" (Phillip - player interview). Phillip didn't explain if he had been researching training sessions based on TGfU on the internet or watching the matches of his favourite international teams. If he had been watching matches, it was unlikely he would have seen TGfU in action, nor acquire an understanding of how it works in coaching practice. Stephen, a player from Furat Men's team stated that everyone would have to learn a lot more about it for it to work:

RESEARCHER: Some countries are using TGfU - using the game for training. Can you imagine that in the future we can do it in Iraq?

STEPHEN: it depends, coaches need more knowledge and players too need more thinking about volleyball. In addition, we all need to know more about

volleyball overseas, too. I guess to get new knowledge is not easy at the moment in Iraq. It takes time to get more knowledge in volleyball. (player interview)

In an effort to unpack opportunities for TGfU, Victor, assistant coach of Dejlal Women's team was asked how he improved players' skills via game play in a coaching session. He was given the example of modifying poor player positioning during a practice game. Victor asked, "What do you mean?". He was confused by the concept. It was further explained:

RESEARCHER: For example, out of 6 players on the court, one is in a poor position – what would you do?

VICTOR: I have to tell the player after finishing the game.

RESEARCHER: After the game?

VICTOR: Yes, after the game. (Victor - coach interview).

Edward shared a similar view, stating that neither he nor the head coach would modify a player's position during a practice match. Samuel, head coach with Edward's team Furat Women's, emphasised that "I am not that person who uses games for teaching." (Samuel - coach interview). Michael, assistant coach with Dejlal Men's team, was adamant that "It is impossible to teach skills through game play" (assistant coach interview).

Most players needed further explanation of what TGfU meant. Daisy, from Furat Women's team confirmed that "the team does not get something like TGfU at training" (Daisy - player interview). Tayla, from Dejlal women's team concurred "we do not have TGfU" (Tayla - player interview). Arthur, from Furat Men's team, knew what TGfU was but did not believe it was a feature of Iraqi volleyball coaching:

RESEARCHER: Do your coaches using TGFU for training?

ARTHUR: My coaches use fitness and skills to improve but they are not using TGFU.

RESEARCHER: do you guess we can use it TGFU in future?

ARTHUR: I think so, we do not have new knowledge in the sport. In Iraq, we've been using the traditional coaching approach for long time. The coaches are using the same program, every year. Traditional in the training, in all games, in volleyball and soccer too.

RESEARCHER: Do you think the coaches are using the same coaching style from when they were players?

ARTHUR: Yes sure. They do not have new knowledge.

Côté and Gilbert (2009) asserted that TGfU approach is heavily reliant on the abilities of coaches to identify issues and problems as they occur in real time during game play. Deep knowledge of the game and how it is played is required. Although all the coaches and assistant coaches interviewed have a deep knowledge of the game, the lack of engagement with a teaching model like TGfU stems from the hierarchical beliefs and practices which already configure coaching in Iraq. There is no pedagogical practice in place to encourage questioning and response as a means of improving player ability.

6.6 Player Development

The final theme of player development accounted for five important codes, including when and how players had learning opportunities, feedback, player self-learning, what they enjoyed about coaching, and opportunities for women players.

6.6.1 Players' Opportunities to Learn

The interviews provided extensive evidence that both male and female players wanted to talk more with their coaches regarding volleyball. Players wanted to understand, to improve, to generally have their wishes acknowledged. Amy said “the coaches need to sometimes listen to the players” (Amy - player interview) but with little evidence of democratic coaching, extended periods of silence and the absence of questioning in training it seems unlikely that players will have their learning needs met. There was little to no opportunity to learn from player decision making.

Player-coach dialogues during training are not the only way in which player learning could occur. Varied activities, opportunities for games with constraints and new training models and concepts could also enhance player learning. Players were aware that there was room for new approaches:

Most of coaches teach their players what they believe and how they played when they were players [themselves] a long time ago. The coaches have had the same program for long time. That's why the coaches cannot introduce new strategies for the future...It's not right, because it's just routine exercises without us actually improving in volleyball. (Milo - player, interview). He added: “my coaches need more knowledge in volleyball programs”.

Although the coaches were basing their work on past playing experiences, the lack of evidence-based coaching strategies, new ideas and new methods were stifling players' opportunities to learn. Mathew, from Furat men's team shared a similar opinion to Milo above, who was from the other men's team, Dejliah:

RESEARCHER: According to your opinion, how do you think your coach's strategies during coaching sessions improve your understanding of the game?

MATHEW: I will tell you the truth. It doesn't. I watch the internet a lot and it's completely different with Iraqi coaches.

RESEARCHER: Do you watch volleyball and the training in volleyball by internet?

MATHEW: Yes, sure. I watch YouTube a lot. A lot of international teams have a high level in volleyball skills and fitness because they have the knowledge of volleyball. These teams have a new modern style in volleyball but here in Iraq, we are stuck with the classic style in the training.

Adam, head coach of Furat Men's team, was asked how and when players had the opportunity to develop tactical knowledge and receive feedback on their game play – during coaching drills, coaching games, during competitive matches and/or after each of these types of sessions. He commented:

ADAM: I think the best way is using 3-5 groups and doing exercises to improve players in the volleyball.

RESEARCHER: How can you modify players' position during game play in coaching sessions?

ADAM: after the training, I talk with the players in general for different reasons.

RESEARCHER: just after the training?

ADAM: and before matches, if we have matches with another team.

In this exchange, Adam confirmed that he did not structure the session or speak or question his players about tactics or positioning errors or similar whilst the drills or practice

games were in play. The debriefing would occur afterwards (in the instances of coaching sessions), or before a competitive match.

From these examples, it appeared as though players' opportunities to learn were based around doing, not asking. Schempp (1993) argued that procedural knowledge of coaches, such as knowing "how" to run a coaching session, should include questioning. Jowett (2017) reiterated the importance of questioning, while Facao and Bloom (2018) and Falcao et al., (2017) argued that humanistic coaching should enable players to take increasing control of their own destiny. These kinds of exchanges were not evident in the cultural-discursive arrangements of coaching sessions, which appeared to reflect the broader societal expectations that (male) coaches were to be obeyed.

6.6.2 Feedback

Chapter 5 findings showed very little feedback was provided during coaching, with long periods of silence taking up a significant proportion of training time, and only one short example of "hustle" in a men's session. The periods of silence were greater in women's training sessions. Furthermore, when asked about when feedback was provided, some coaches responded with "After the game" (for example, Adam, Furat men's coach). Performance feedback was conveyed through negative comments such as "not good", with little redirection to, or sharing of, knowledge of performance. The coaches did not debrief players at the end of the game which concluded the session, being absent from any warm-down or concluding type activities. Questions and answers during training were non-existent. Players departed the sports hall as soon as sessions were finished. There appeared to be insufficient time to converse with coaches in any meaningful way, or to ask for training feedback. Coaches did not carry notebooks or other ways of recording reflections as training unfolded. In the absence of any written observations, how did feedback occur, if at all, and did players seek it?

Victor, assistant coach with Dejlah women's team, agreed that they did not provide feedback after training, but thought perhaps feedback did occur during training. Amy, from the same team, said: "the coaches use feedback when we have matches with other teams but do not use feedback in the sessions" (Amy - player interview). When asked about feedback:

RESEARCHER: I watched the video recording and I did not notice encouragement from the coaches to the players. Why?

AMY: (laughing) I do not know. Sometimes, the coach has some nice words, for example, "good serving". Sometimes, the players are doing the

serving without thinking. My coaches do not have time to explain more details (about where to place the hands and feet) in volleyball.

When asked how her coaches helped her to become a more successful player, Matilda from Dejliah women's team suggested that she could benefit with more feedback:

If I get more exercises from the coaches, and if I get more feedback from the coaches ... If the coach helps me with some skills. For example, I need to know how to do the spike because I have no idea to do it exactly. (Matilda - player interview).

Tayla said that her coaches provided feedback "in general and doing some fitness, which is very important" (player interview). This was a surprising comment because the male coaches of the female teams did not appear to take much interest in the warm-up stages – using them for setting up the practice drills – and most comments noted in later stages were negative - "not good enough". However, this implies that feedback about fitness is more likely to come from how she felt doing the exercises, rather than anything the coaches said.

de Faria Pastore et al. (2016) suggested that feedback is vital for coaches to build solid player/coach and player/player relationships. Feedback also improves the coach's reputation as an educator. Monitoring and recording the actions and learning needs of players could return massive benefits for any coach, providing more opportunities for meaningful feedback. The fact that every coach was either a teacher or a lecturer was ironic in this finding – that feedback was so rare yet such an important part of coaching:

RESEARCHER: I watched the video record; I did not hear a nice word from your coaches to you, like "great serve" or something.

MURRAY: hmmm yes, it's not. My coaches do not encourage the players during the exercises in training" (Murray - player interview)

Positive and negative comments from coaches to the players about their skill performance can be important to improve their performance and results in a game.

RESEARCHER: I watched the video recording, and I did not hear any motivational words from the coach to you.

OLIVIA: Maybe after the video recording, he told me some words.

RESEARCHER: during the session, do the coaches have encouraging words to the players?

MILO: they do not have and that's not good. I can say, my coaches are silent during the session.

Feedback could be used for player learning and motivation during coaching sessions, as well as for motivation during the championships, as the players indicated, but it did not seem to be occurring in training.

6.6.3 Player Self-Coaching: Researching on YouTube

The players interviewed admitted to accessing YouTube videos for self-learning. Players stated that they sought out new ideas from the internet, often keeping their research secret from their coaches and team-mates. Players outlined that the video research was helpful for fixing different problems in volleyball techniques, useful for showing the right position for players, generally good for enhancing the game, tactics and skills. Matthew, from Furat men's team, said: "I found a really nice exercise watching volleyball on YouTube" (Matthew - player interview) and Megan, from Furat women's team said: "I have the internet and I do some exercises using the internet" (Megan - player interview). Zack from Dejlal men's team admitted he too "watched volleyball matches through YouTube" (Zack - player interview). Despite there being no evidence of coaches encouraging players to do their own research on YouTube, learning new things in this way – clandestine self-learning - was clearly valued by them.

The interview findings confirm that watching match videos was considered a significant tool for learning skills, developing tactical knowledge and getting motivated. Videos were considered as an effective tool for performance improvement. Cassidy et al. (2016) noted that reviewing videos is an effective self-coaching strategy for athletes to improve their understanding of skills and the game.

Irwin et al. (2004) mentioned that social media is also an effective tool for online learning of technical sport skills. The responsible use of this tool can be beneficial to ensure effective communication within and across teams, and useful for learning new information. Overall, it was evident that watching YouTube videos was considered useful for enhancement of performance by athletes but little evidence, apart from Michael, that coaches thought the

same. The players were accessing YouTube for their own research, away from the team, and particularly noted by some women players, without the knowledge or consent of their coaches.

6.6.4 What Players Enjoy About Coaching

Each player was asked ‘what is your favourite part about the coaching sessions?’ Amy said: “the practical part of volleyball” (Amy – player interview). When asked why, she said: “to understand the movement and how to do it. It is more important than theory” (Amy – player interview). Hannah, Matilda, Tayla, Daisy and Olivia also highlighted technical skills as their favourite part. This finding was not surprising as the women’s teams valued learning new sports skills more highly than the men’s teams in the PSPP findings. Milo queried whether the question meant “theory or practice” and confirmed that “the practical part” was also his favourite (Milo – player interview). Murray, Matthew, Stephen and Arthur referred to this part (using the ball, technical skills) as “the main part” of the coaching session, but Murray also introduced the idea that playing the game was also important (Murray – player interview).

Also unsurprising was the number of players who said “fitness” was their favourite part of coaching. Sophia said: “it’s all very important, but the best part is the warmup and fitness” (Sophia – player interview). Megan said: “the warm-up and the exercises with the ball” (Megan - player interview). Megan and Sophia were both from Furat women ‘s team, where the team captain was allowed to lead the warmup and fitness exercises. Ollie, from Dejlal men’s team, said: “the fitness part is very important. Fitness is important for everybody” (Ollie – player interview). Zack and Phillip from the same team identified fitness as their favourite part because of its importance, with Phillip confirming what was already evident from the video analysis that Dejlal men’s team spent a lot of time on fitness in training: “my coach spends a long time on fitness because it is very important for volleyball players...Volleyball is not easy. Volleyball needs more fitness than football” (Phillip – player interview. Zack’s views on how outdated and stagnant their training routines and program were having already been shared so perhaps it is also not surprising that he enjoyed that part of his training where improvement (in fitness) over the season could be measured.

There were no responses to this question that identified dialogue, questioning, small sided or conditional games, player input or any other decision-making capacity as something the players enjoyed. It appeared to be beyond their experience of training. The findings implied that empowering players to take control of their learning (cf. Falcao et al., 2017) was not a practice architecture of coaching in Iraqi volleyball – a definite constraint to the empowerment of players. A hierarchal controlling culture was evident in those situations.

6.6.5 Women's Opportunities

Armour and Chambers (2014) asserted that coaches have to account for many varied issues, including gender discrimination. Although volleyball offers equal opportunities for participation across the genders, female players experience additional issues arising from the constraint of social norms, specifically in the Muslim world. The customary restraint of any culture can affect the different activities related to tradition and cultural norm about female athletes.

The interview findings and video analyses concerned with coach-player relationships affirmed differences in the ways in which male and female players experienced volleyball. In Iraqi culture, specifically beyond secondary school, there appeared to be limited sporting opportunities for women. Training as an elite player is constrained by societal norms and expectations, such as girls being forbidden from going into a gym for fitness or weight training. Amy stated that: “the culture in Iraq does not allow for many girls to play volleyball in the club” (Amy - player, interview) and Daisy added in her interview that “the culture in Iraq still is not easy for women to play a sport” (Daisy - player interview).

This implied that there is massive constraint related to involvement of women in sport. Additionally, pressures of time, financial cost, responsibilities, familial expectations and cultural disapproval impacted on sports participation. Northern Iraq is dominated by Christian and Kurdish participants. The issue of disapproval or prevention of sport participation is more likely in Islamic states and Arabic countries (Roy et al., 2009), which includes Iraq. Amy gave the example that she asked her coaches for advice about how to do resistance exercises at home, because “my brother will not allow me to go to the gym” (Amy – player interview).

Several players stated that in Iraqi culture, female players are more reluctant to get engaged in open communication with coaches. Megan noted that her culture “did not allow me to talk about my coach” (Megan – player interview). The proportion of the coaching session spent in silence for both women's teams would suggest that there is little conversation between the coaches and players, or between players.

The fact that there were two fully subscribed, elite women's teams in this region indicated that there was something additional occurring with the coach-player relationship. Sophia admitted that “my family has been in contact with my coach every training session” (Sophia - player interview), calling to check on her until she makes it safely back home. Tayla also stated that “my family has connected with the coach too”. The video analyses showed that coaches paid more attention to family members than players when they entered the sports hall,

taking time to engage in extended conversation. This meant that the coach-player relationship was actually a coach-player-family relationship. Weinberg and Gould (2014) asserted that good communication with players and other stakeholders, such as family members is a vital management function and particularly for youth sport. These players were all adults, between the ages of 18-25, yet the coaches needed to build strong relationships with family members as though players were children – especially for the women’s teams.

In other Islamic states, female sports are subjected to different rigid challenges ranging from the absence of female physical education to restricted opportunities in playing sport. The segregation of sexes in schooling and sport, and the scarcity of sports facilities for women can lead to low participation rates and exclusion of women from sport (Stiller et al., 2004).

6.7 Discussion of Interview Findings

The interview findings as presented via six identified themes were the Iraqi participant context, coaching philosophy, coaching approach, holistic coaching practice, coach professional learning and player development. This discussion reveals how these themes were interconnected. The participant context showed the far-reaching impacts of the war in Iraq and illuminated how the widespread poverty undermining player participation in elite sport affected their coaching and playing experiences. As outlined by Matthews (2020) and Vernez et al. (2016) in the review of literature, such far-reaching effects included the disruption or loss of community amenity and options for youth sport.” Coaching approaches developed around these existing social-political and material-economic arrangements, including player poverty, unsalaried coaching, cultural restrictions on women’s participation (such as travel to and from venues), and interrupted or stagnated coach education from war sanctions. This translated into holistic coaching practices such as trying to source equipment and team uniforms from the IVF, coaches paying for student players to catch buses and having to cancel fixtures in other regions or city locations at short notice for their personal safety. All four teams were engaging in “as professional” coaching practices “as best” they could.

The interview findings related to the theme of coaching philosophy centred around the hierarchical coaching traditions of Iraqi volleyball coaches, such as the “apprentice-in-waiting” (Lyle, 2002) assistant coach behaviour and practices, which were again grounded in the Iraqi patriarchal context. As Cassidy et al. (2018) explained, a coaching philosophy is something that both coaches and players possess - even if players are not aware of theirs – driving what *they expect to see their coaches doing* in their coach-player relationships and expectations of coaching quality. The assistant coaches knew that it was not their place usurp the role of the

head coach by offering additional planning input or corrective feedback. Their practices to play a supporting role to the head coaches in their actions were apparent in Victor and Edward's descriptions of how they saw their role and were consistent with an autocratic coaching philosophy. These autocratic coaching approaches were tacitly revealed by the women's interview responses, as the women players were less likely to criticize their coaches, even with the protection of anonymity. They were not prepared to jeopardise their opportunity to participate in sport, which reflected more broadly their participant context with the cultural-discursive arrangements of women in Iraqi society and for them to avoid embarrassing their families (who held the power and control over their ability to play). The men's teams were more open in their criticism of their coaches, particularly the view that coaching approaches were routinized and stagnant, which again reflects patriarchal arrangements in this participant context.

The interrelated themes of coach learning and player development were also underscored by the context. The coaches said that conflict meant that competitive opportunities were limited or cancelled, with such tournaments being likely "informal opportunities" of coach learning (Cushion et al., 2010). The lack of professional salaries for coaches meant that mentors for coaches would be limited, another important source of coach education identified in the literature (cf. Cushion, 2006, Cushion et al., 2010). Coach education was shaped not only by engaging in the process of coaching but also has what each coach has done before, serving what Sage (1989) described as an "apprenticeship of observation" as once athletes and now as coaches (cited in Cushion et al., 2010, p. 35). Finally, player development is dependent upon the interrelationships of all identified themes: the context, coaching philosophies, coaching approaches, holistic coaching practices and coach education. Autocratic coaching approaches described – such as Milo saying "no way" would his coach take player input into his programming and Victor's explanation that they would not provide feedback to the women's teams whilst games were in play – directly impact on opportunities for player development. What was also clear from the interview findings was that the coaches and the players embraced the opportunity to be as fit, strong and technically proficient as they could be in their war-impacted coaching environments.

Lastly, it is important to reflect upon my insider status as a researcher and the nature of the interview responses I was able to record. There were instances where players were very happy to talk to me because they or their family members knew of me from my past coaching experiences. There was one instance where a female player was very reluctant to talk to me in case her coach found out. My repeated assurances that her identity and club would not be

revealed translated into a short interview after three attempts. The candour displayed by the coach responses to questions, particularly about who is in charge and what he expects of his other coach and/or players, reveals that the coaches did not appear conflicted or concerned about speaking openly about their beliefs, approaches and practices, nor their criticism of the IVF. They appeared to speak honestly without fear of reprisal. My duty of care to them is to ensure the anonymity of their interview responses in the reporting of these findings.

Chapter 7 will now synthesise the findings from all three findings chapters. The implications for stakeholders in Iraq volleyball and for future research into sport coaching and development in regions like Iraq will be outlined.

7 DISCUSSION

7.1 Introduction

This research focuses on coaches', assistant coaches' and players' perceptions of volleyball coaching and coaching practices to understand how and why they are valued. The study particularly focused upon coaching philosophies, coaching preferences and approaches of coaches and players. It sought to identify dominant approaches, any differences between coaching approaches for men's and women's teams and players and the priority given to fitness, technical and tactical skill development (player learning) and game knowledge. Player physical self-perception was assessed for its explanatory potential affecting coaching preferences and coaching approaches in elite volleyball in Iraq.

This chapter provides a synthesis of findings of the study drawing on the combined analyses of the three main data sets sequentially collected, analysed and presented in Chapters 4, 5 and 6. Chapter 4 presented the player Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP) findings, drawn from Fox and Corbin's (1989) widely cited paper and Fox's (1990) subsequent PSPP protocol. Chapter 5 presented the analyses of practices within four video recorded coaching sessions, one per team. It was guided by an adaptation of Cushion et al. (2012) Coach Analysis and Intervention System (CAIS), allowing multiple viewings, post-session, for point-in-time data collection. Chapter 6 presented the interview findings, conducted after the PSPP and video analyses, in which players and coaches were asked to describe their coaching philosophies, approaches and practices with respect to player development (fitness, technical skill or tactical game play) in coaching.

This chapter seeks to complete the final phase of the mixed methods sequential explanatory design, whereby the findings of three data sets are analysed together to answer the research problem. The chapter is organised into six sections. After 7.1 Introduction, Section 7.1.1 revisits the over-arching research problem and 3 sub-questions, and a summary of the mixed methods sequential explanatory research design. A summary of major findings in the language of the theoretical framework of Practice Architectures chosen for this study is presented in Section 7.3. Section 7.4 presents the synthesis of findings to specifically answer each research question, concluding with Section 7.5.

7.1.1 Restatement of the Research Problem and Sub-Questions

In seeking to understand coach and player perceptions of coaching in elite volleyball in Iraq, the three focused research questions were:

1. What are the coaching philosophies that inform volleyball coaching approaches in Iraq?
2. What coaching approaches do the coaches and players value?
3. How and to what extent do coaching practices align with valued coaching approaches of men and women players of volleyball?

These questions were refined from understandings in the literature of the importance of and relationships between coaching philosophies, coaching approaches and practices in particular sites with particular athletes (Cassidy et al., 2016; Martens, 2012; Cushion & Armour, 2016).

7.2 Summary of Research Process

To answer the research questions, there were three primary sources for data including questionnaire survey data, video observation data and interview data, collected via mixed methods sequential explanatory design. The questionnaire comprised of the Physical Self-Perception Profile, known as the PSPP. The primary data obtained from the PSPP questionnaire was analysed with the help of ANOVA. The results for all four teams were found to be statistically significant for some of sub-domains. No significant differences were observed between men and women or between clubs around total physical self-worth, sports competence or body attractiveness. There was slight significance (differences in responses) between groups around the importance of physical strength and conditioning. Additionally, small differences were identified at individual construct level in the value ascribed by women players around pride in themselves from sport participation and learning new sports skills, which was not as important to the men.

As discussed in Chapter 3, the data was collected at an opportunistic time of the season, due to the dangers and logistical factors of a film crew being able to film an entire session in safety and with permission. The timing of the filming in the season was early, on the cusp of pre-season and competition, just as formal competition was about to begin. It is reasonable to assume that the pre-season coaching is typically dominated by fitness and conditioning work,

to return players to elite standards for competition. However, the combined findings paint a picture of a phase of coaching centring on physiological states (Cushion et al., 2012) lasting for more than just the pre-season stage that was filmed. Filming only in the pre-season can be considered another limitation of this study. However, as will be discussed in this chapter, the practice architectures of coaching in Iraq point to the consistency of the behaviours and approaches described herein.

7.3 The Theoretical Framework of Practice Architectures

The analysis and synthesis of the findings were informed by the theory of practice architectures overviewed in Chapter 2. Kemmis and Grootenboer (2008) proposed that practices within sites are constituted by interactions between individuals and groups, within and between sites and across society. These arrangements that facilitate or constrain practices are called practice architectures and are configured in cultural-discursive, material-economic and socio-political ways. Figure 37 presents an illustration of the practice architectures of Iraqi Volleyball practices, from the synthesis of the findings in Chapters 4, 5 and 6.

Figure 37. Practice architectures of elite Iraqi volleyball.

Figure 37 illustrates how practice architectures, or arrangements, within an individual's practice, within a site, within society and across sites within the practice (i.e., volleyball coaching practices across different sites) inform, validate or contest each other. The left-hand column of the figure shows how practices are interactionally secured by the practitioner (coaches and players) and the practice (volleyball coaching). Players expect their coaches to coach in particular ways, and coaches expect to coach in particular ways, based on their prior experiences of playing volleyball. These experiences can be drawn from within one site (i.e., a single club) or also from within "the practice of volleyball coaching", which has characteristics

shared across sites (around the world). On the right-hand side of Figure 37, the cultural-discursive practice architectures, or arrangements, underpinning the practice of volleyball coaching include uninterrupted cultural norms, the patriarchy and hierarchy of Iraq society and religious doctrine concerning the roles of men and women. Material-economic arrangements of the practice of volleyball in these clubs include the impoverishment of the general community, the amateur status of coaching as a profession and the inability of the Iraqi Volleyball Federation to resource individual clubs, coaches or players in their pursuit of elite sport. Long held practices are handed down via coach to assistant coach, who one day become the head coach from 1) their experiences as elite players and 2) as “apprentices” watching coaching practices acquired many years ago, rather than from the resourcing of coach education or professional learning. Social-political arrangements are also preconfigured by the lack of resourcing of northern Iraq as a region by the Government based in Baghdad, due to its primarily Kurdish and minority Sunni populations, and the exclusion of Iraq from Olympic status (and further resourcing opportunities) due to its inability to meet minimum human rights standards, including rights of women, of recognised member nations.

Just as the theory of practice architectures can assist with determining constraints upon practice, it operationalises potential to see how arrangements can be reconfigured to enable changes to practice. In the following sections, the specific research questions are addressed, raising further implications which are presented in Section 7.4.

7.4 Findings

7.4.1 Research Question 1

What are the coaching philosophies that inform volleyball coaching practices in Iraq?

Coaching philosophies comprise values, beliefs and principles that stem from “knowing one’s own mind” (Martens, 2012) and guide a coach’s practice (Cassidy et al., 2016). They can develop over time, based upon coaches’ perceptions of how to be the best possible role models for their players, what they believe effective coaching should include and the best approaches to meet the needs of their players. Knowing one’s coaching philosophy enables coaches to be self-aware (Cushion & Partington, 2016), to address performance and ethical issues via an established set of principles, in ways that encourage and respect athletes. How coaches enact their coaching philosophy impacts upon the experiences, enjoyment and performance of players.

None of the coaches in the study articulated having or following a coaching philosophy in the way they answered the questions about what makes them an effective coach or how they helped their players to meet their goals. But the three data sets revealed dominant arrangements for configuring coaching and a consistent way of relating to assistant coaches, players and families. There was much evidence of autocratic coaching philosophies, evidenced by coach-centred approaches - literally, the head coaches were at the centre of every technical drill, as more capable and knowledgeable role models - and a clear hierarchy of importance and authority in assistant coaching staff and players. Coaching philosophies evolve over time and are shaped by pre-existing conditions and expectations of coaching by multiple stakeholders such as coaches, players and families (Weinberg & Gould, 2014; Cassidy et al, 2016). The patriarchy and hierarchy of Iraqi society meant that the head coaches would take a 'sage on the stage' approach to leading sessions, based on a genuine belief that their superior knowledge, playing experience and position gave them unquestioned authority to act in these ways. The same societal rules dictated the ways in which assistant coaches and players could relate to the head coach, which meant with deference, no direct questioning or criticism and no input into the design of the program. It also stifled any emphasis on reflection upon coaching, with no evidence from video analysis or coach interviews of any form of reflective practice.

Coaching philosophies are the cornerstone to developing player trust. Holistic coaching philosophies take into account individual, social and cultural differences and shape the way in which coaching "care" is enacted (Dohsten, et al, 2018). There was much evidence from player interviews, particularly women players, that they trusted their coaches and that all coaches took the time to get to know them and their families. Coaches knew the importance of building team cohesion, through wider family socialisation, which, with the exception of one male player, Phillip, was well supported by men and women. The coaches prioritized and valued getting to know families, particularly women's families, which was clear in the interview statements from players and coaches, and from the observed behaviour coaches when families entered the court. These coaches recognised 1) the criticality of family support for players, 2) the impoverishment of the region and subsequent impact on sport participation and, 3) the 'gift' of their time and expertise to overcome the impoverishment of elite sport in war torn Iraq. Holistic coaching philosophies were evidenced by the amount of time and energy that coaches demonstrated and said they put into ensuring families were comfortable with their sons' and daughters' involvement in the sport. They regularly donated a portion of their own salaries, not derived from professional coaching fees, but from their regular day jobs as teachers and academics, to pay for uniforms, shoes, transport and competition fees of their players. They offered their own

modes of transport to ensure teams made it to the occasions where they played out of club or region. They ensured the women's teams were properly chaperoned to the satisfaction of every family. Hours and hours of their donated, unsalaried time was spent meeting the needs and expectations of the whole family group, not only the player.

A coaching philosophy does not set coaching approaches in stone but can bias a coach's view on the best way to coach (Cassidy et al., 2016). The head coaches consistently said that superior fitness, conditioning and technical proficiency was the purpose of coaching, which would then enable better performance in match play. Some assistant coaches and male players dissented and thought that more time spent on tactics and game play in coaching would result in better performance. They were not prepared to share these views with the head coach as it would be disrespectful to the hierarchy. The prioritizing of physiological training states within coaching sessions did align with the players' physical self-perception - that is, men and women players derived identity support from having superior strength and conditioning. The PSPP data showed that all players were happy with the physical side of themselves and thought physical strength and conditioning was important. Some teams valued sport skills and some teams, particularly one women's team, were very proud of themselves for having the opportunity to play sport. The holistic coaching philosophies of these very patriarchal, hierarchical coaches was to recognise that ensuring family support for female sport participation was essential in order for these women's teams to even exist.

To the outside observer, it appeared that coaches did not want women players' input, provided them with fewer forms of feedback, yet enabled Captains to lead parts of the session that were deemed less important (such as the warmup and warm down). The percentage of coaching spent in silence with the women's teams (an average of 34.76% across both women's teams), as found in Chapter 5, would suggest that the coaches did not care about women's player learning, but a bigger, more complicated participation issue was being managed by the coaches. The young women showed great reluctance in criticizing their male coaches in the interviews and the coaches seemed to be avoiding consternation of families, and further repercussions, which could be generated by criticizing the young women in front of family members who regularly watched. These coaches appeared to be managing the cultural-discursive arrangements of Iraqi society dictating acceptable roles for young women in order to ensure their teams could continue to play.

A more enduring problem for coaching in Iraq is the apparent unwillingness to permit assistant coach and player input into coaching. The lack of input was observed in the findings from Chapter 5 and established via interviews in Chapter 6. Being unwilling to see players and

assistant coaches as having resources or knowledge to contribute to coaching programs and future learning stems from the autocratic coaching philosophies underpinning the coaching practices on display. None of the coaches described themselves or their coaching philosophy as autocratic, but they freely admitted that consulting others was not part of their job. In terms of practice architectures of coaching, culturally-embedded patriarchal relations between coaches and ‘subordinate’ assistant coaches, and players meant that the authority of the coach was never to be challenged in person. Not wanting to be seen to be challenging their authority ensured that coaching approaches which require questioning and answering would not succeed, player decision-making would not be enabled and assistant coach agency over program design would not be invited. Martens (2012) argued that autocratic coaching is fairly common in Western coaching contexts and his work centred around collegiate sport in the USA. Autocratic coaching per se is not unique to Iraq, but as Cushion et al (2012) noted, coaching behaviours are usually somewhere *on a continuum* between autocratic and democratic, changing over time, over performance level, and in relation to stages of the season. What appeared consistent in Iraq was that there was no continuum of behaviours. Rather the coaches tended to stick towards the autocratic end”.

7.4.2 Research Question 2

What coaching approaches do the coaches and players value?

Related to the autocratic coaching philosophies entrenched and supported by traditional Iraqi societal norms was the remarkable similarities in coaching approaches favoured by coaches and many players, both men and women. As described earlier, both coaches and players supported coaching approaches that favoured technical practice and physical strength and conditioning. This was in evidence in the PSPP findings from Chapter 4, the video analyses in Chapter 5 and the coach and player interviews in Chapter 6. Players and coaches reported in Chapter 6 that completing the fitness work in coaching sessions met their expectations of preparation for elite performance, was enjoyable, was essential, and generally undisputed. The analysis of the proportion of time spent on physical fitness in training showed it was a significant phase with between 17-35% of total training time across the four teams, with Dejlal men’s team devoting the most time (Refer to Figure 38).

KEY

COACHING PHASE Sub-category	Description of observed coach and player behaviours
TRAINING Warm-up	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as warm-up.
TRAINING Fitness training	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as physical conditioning.
TRAINING Technical practice	Individual or group activity covering isolated technical skills under limited or no pressure
PLAYING Full sided game	Full court in play, all players on court, regulation rules with both teams scoring in the same way.
TRAINING Warm-down	Primary goal relates to physiological aspects of the game such as warm-down.
MANAGEMENT Rest	When players are taking a break from practice – e.g. water break.

Figure 38. Percentage of time in coaching phases for Dejlal Men’s, Dejlal women’s, Furat men’s and Furat women’s teams (adapted from Cushion et al. 2012, p.212).

Figure 38 shows the previously separate pie charts for each team in Chapter 5 as one combined bar graph for all four teams. It compares the percentage of the coaching session devoted to each phase rather than number of minutes, as the length of coaching sessions varied between 63 to 70 for three out of four teams and 99 minutes for Dejlal women’s team. The key was adapted from Cushion et al. (2012) as not all sub-categories were evident. For example, contemporary coaching practices drawing upon Games Sense (Stolz & Pill, 2016), Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) (Butler & Griffiths, 2016) and non-linear pedagogy (Chow

et al., 2007; Chow, Davids, Button & Renshaw, 2016) highlight the importance of small-sided games, conditional games or games or skill development activities with constraints. None of the four teams observed implemented any kind of conditional game or constraints-based activities. Even the traditional coaching progression of *warm-up - skill development - modified game - full game*, as outlined by Stolz and Pill (2016) was not evident, as Figure 35 shows that the Iraqi sessions were typically *warm-up - fitness - skill development - full game*. Technical practice, with limited or no pressure from the opposition, dominated the sessions in three out of the four teams observed, ranging from 26.98% to 33.83% (Dejlah Men's, Furat Men's and Furat women's teams). The exception was Dejlah women's team which, in this particular session, a full sided game (39.42%) dominated the session. Figure 35 clearly indicates that the four coaching sessions privileged physiological training states, especially physical conditioning, and isolated technical practice showing no features of contemporary games sense coaching approaches. Management such as introducing the next new technical drill or game time comprised less than 1% of the total coaching time and has not been displayed. Player rest, such as taking a water break, occupied 9.52% to 14.1% of total coaching time

There was more dispute and contestation over the nature and proportion of time spent on technical skill development as a dominant coaching approach across the four teams. Learning new sport skills was valued more by women than by men in the PSPP results. Men were more likely to criticize their coaches for repeating the same routines in technical drills, year after year, as shown in the interviews. The male players and some assistant coaches expressed views that head coaches do not necessarily have the best approach to coaching, or up to date knowledge. In Iraq, there had been interruption to the delivery of coach education programs delivered by the IVF due to the war. Only recently, in late 2019, have volleyball coaches from Iraq had the opportunity to undertake formal coach education programs via the Asian Confederation in the FIVB in Tehran, Iran (see Asian Confederation, n.d.). A number of women coaches from other countries also participated in the same coach education program.

As discussed in Chapter 2, such traditional approaches to coaching produce players who can perform skills competently but lack appropriate tactical development for game-play, making players reliant on coaches for decision making in games (Thorpe et al., 1986; Hay and Macdonald, 2008). TGfU gradually increases tactical awareness of the game in learning phases (i.e., such as in coaching sessions) by engaging players in modified games, thereby presenting opportunities for making decisions on game strategy (Miri, 2015). Male players tended to say that their coaches' knowledge was out of date or "from a long time ago" and they confirmed that tactics did not comprise coaching sessions. Men and women players admitted to watching

other nations play games on YouTube, *but they are not watching how these other nations train*. The players may research new drills to practice in isolation but this still does not show how a skill is situated within a TGfU coaching session or season cycle. YouTube alone cannot introduce a genuine understanding of games-based coaching in practice. TGfU or games sense can only emerge in coaching practice if the coaches value players' input (requiring a shift in their coaching philosophy) and if coaches are educated to understand the key differences in TGfU models of practice and their traditional autocratic practices (requiring new coach education opportunities). Their coaching philosophies have to support player choice, player decision-making and accept player expertise, but as discussed above, the autocratic coaching philosophies operationalised in these coaching sites regard players as having nothing to offer program design or coaching approaches.

Perhaps the most significant finding around coaching approaches employed by Iraqi coaches is the amount of time coaching sessions are spent on direct management and in silence. As shown in Figure 39 below, coaches were silent more than one quarter of the entire session for all teams, but particularly so for women's teams (average 34.76%). This figure combines the previously presented pie charts for each team from Chapter 5 into one comparative bar graph for the discussion.

Figure 39. Comparison of primary coaching behaviours by team gender.

The high percentages of direct instruction (i.e., coach talking) and silence (i.e., coach not talking) gives confidence to the claim the opportunity for player questioning and input into coaching sessions is not a typical ‘cultural-discursive arrangement’ (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008). Players then are not discursively enabled to solve movement problems, as you would expect with game sense and TGfU pedagogical models (Stolz & Pill, 2016) to work in groups or unsupervised - their performances are highly regulated under the watchful eye of the main coach, who is always controlling the drill. Other players stood around and watched - waiting for their turn under the coach’s direct gaze - or completed mundane waiting drills such as digging and setting the ball to each in pairs.

As discussed earlier, the greater proportion of time that coaches of women’s teams spent in silence is linked to how they are managing the gender relations in Iraqi society and ensuring that their players keep coming back each season. Chastising players in the form of negative feedback in front of their family could result in the loss of players, and indeed the loss of a viable team, so the coaches convey their displeasure with performance via silence. It is a unique form of Islamic holistic care, which is both an enabler and a constraint to practice. This way of “relating” is acceptable to Iraqi society and the families of players, but the women players know that they are not getting the most out of their coaching sessions. It is then also a constraint, with firm evidence that women players’ learning is stymied more than the men. The practice architectures of Iraqi ways of relating mean that little to no feedback, no player questioning, no opportunities to problem solve or develop and refine tactics in coaching sessions constrain player learning. But it also means that the one aspect of coaching sessions in which players will see best tangible results is, of course, physical strength and conditioning. How this has been identified as something the players value is now discussed in 7.4.3.

7.4.3 Research Question 3

How and to what extent do coaching practices align with valued coaching approaches of men and women players of volleyball?

Despite the findings from Chapters 5 and 6 that coaches are autocratic, do not seek assistant coach or player input and seem to be enacting knowledge acquired from many years ago, there was a significant aspect of coaching practice that aligned with what players valued: developing superior fitness. “Fitness” was often the answer to the lead question posed to both the men and women players about “what is your favourite part about your coaching sessions?”. As presented in Chapter 4, the male players of both clubs tended to place a high value on the

physical side of themselves. Physical conditioning was an important construct in their athlete identity and supports physical self-esteem, which has been found in previous studies (Fox and Corbin, 1989; Fox, 2000; Loland, 1999). Coaching practices that enabled a higher proportion of time spent on strength and conditioning would validate and support male player identities. Female players also valued the physical side of themselves, but also drew identity and physical self-esteem from their pride in playing sport. Thus, coaching practices that enabled a higher average proportion of playing states, or game time, in their observed coaching sessions would validate and support their player identities. As then presented in Chapter 5, the findings showed that coaches of the men's teams, and particularly the Dejlal men's team, prioritised physiological states, given that for Dejlal men, it comprised almost 35% of the coaching session, in addition to the warm-up and warm-down. This team rated the *importance of physical conditioning* the highest maximum average in the PSPP, with least dissension around valuing the *physical side of themselves*. The attention given to fitness in the coaching session would support the development of their physical self-perception and global self-worth. Dejlal women's team was also observed to allocate the highest proportion of their training session to full game practice (39.42%) and the least amount of training time to fitness (17.12%). This team also returned the highest maximum average for the *physical side of themselves* in the PSPP results, with minimum variation in being *proud of themselves* and their achievements.

As Dejlal women's team did have the highest allocation of time spent on game play, the PSPP constructs with the most variation were considered, searching for views supporting more learning time and less fitness time. The Dejlal women's team had maximum variability on the PSPP construct of *being good at sports*, showing that some players valued it highly and other players not much. The *importance of being good at sports* was also rated overall minimum value of the PIP items. As discussed in Chapter 5, the Dejlal women's Assistant Coach privately expressed the opinion that fitness should be the responsibility of players, undertaken in their own time, but as the assistant coach, Victor had no power to enact his beliefs around fitness and tactics. But as Dejlal women's team was the only team to show a significant proportion of full game time (with no modifications or constraints and full international rules in play) the training session, Victor's beliefs on the importance of game play appeared to be having some impact.

Figure 40. Percentage mean comparison of phases of coaching by team gender.

Figure 40 combines the individual team findings from Chapter 5 around phases of coaching into *gender*, rather than *club*. Fitness (physiological training state) and full sided game (playing state) stood out as accruing the greatest difference in average allocated coaching time across gender barriers. The mean allocation of fitness training time was higher in the two men's teams than for the women's teams. Full sided game time was on average higher for women's teams than for the men's teams, remembering that Dejliah Women's team had an extraordinary higher proportion of game time which elevated the mean across both women's teams. However, Furat women's team had more game time than Furat men's team and a similar game time to Dejliah Men's.

The technical (training state) phase of coaching appeared consistent across both men's and women's teams. According to Cushion et al. (2012) CAIS system, both Iraqi men's and women's teams spent the majority of their coaching time in a physiological/training state instead of a playing state. Physical strength and conditioning was valued by all teams, but the PSPP findings also indicated that female players want to play volleyball for skill acquisition, social reasons and pride in playing sport at a high level. The previous section discussed that Iraqi ways of relating, or cultural-discursive arrangements were a practice architecture that is both a constraint on player development and learning, but also an enabler of the physiological aspect of coaching from which they derive satisfaction and elite identity support.

Despite these two areas of difference, what is apparent from the representation of these coaching sessions in Figure 36 how *similar* they are. The format and timings are more similar than dissimilar, despite being from different clubs and of men's and women's teams. It reflects coaching styles that have little variation across clubs and genders. The pattern of reproduction - the enduring practices, underpinned by ways of sayings, doing and relatings across and within different sites - seem to be linked to the unbroken chain of coach appointments from former player to assistant coach to head coach., and the absolute acceptance of male authority.

7.5 Conclusion

This chapter has fulfilled the aim of this study to understand what coaches and players value in coaching in the context of elite volleyball in Iraq. The study particularly focused upon coaching philosophies, coaching preferences and approaches of coaches and players. It sought to identify dominant approaches, any differences between coaching approaches for men's and women's teams and players and the priority given to fitness, technical and tactical skill development (player learning) and game knowledge. The research design sought to elicit player perceptions of what counts towards their physical self-perception as elite volleyball players, what coaching practices were observed, and coach and player perceptions via interview of how they thought coaching should "hang together" and unfold in practice" (Kemmis & Grootenboer, 2008).

The combination of the findings revealed that in some critical areas, there was good alignment with approaches described and observed and what both coaches and players valued. For example, it was overwhelmingly clear that both male and female players, and most coaching staff, valued coaching time spent on developing high levels of fitness, strength, and conditioning.

In many other critical areas, such as coach and player development, there is much to improve. For example, the coaching routines and practices of all teams, male and female, were very similar. There was no evidence of gender-specific approaches to coaching. The only marginal difference was the lower amounts of verbal feedback provided to female players.

The following chapter focuses in detail on the implications for important stakeholder groups in elite volleyball in Iraq.

8 IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

This concluding chapter discusses the importance of the findings and its implications for the vital stakeholders in elite volleyball in Iraq. The first two sections (8.1 & 8.2) pull together the connection between autocratic coaching philosophies and practices and the societal constraints upon coach professional learning, in short what the *key implications are for elite volleyball coaches*. The next section (8.3) considers the evidenced discrepancies between experiences of coaching between men and women at the intersection between gender and culture and the *implications for elite volleyball player development*. Next, in Section 8.4 the implications for *regional and national development in volleyball in Iraq* and the wider Middle East are presented. In section 8.5, the implications for *volleyball administration*, both within Iraq and internationally are considered. This chapter also proposes *what next for sport coaching research in Iraq* in Section 8.6, as a consequence of this study. The thesis is complete with three final sections on strengths, limitations and concluding remarks.

8.1 Autocratic Coaching and the Constraints upon Professional Learning

The literature review established that the traditional autocratic coaching style has been perceived as unfair upon female athletes (Harkness, 2012), although they clearly do not wish to criticize. Female athletes in Iraq prioritize social and inclusive participation which supports their identity and boosts their morale as players, as demonstrated in their PSPP responses and interviews. The need for participative coaching has encouraged and recommended promoting an inclusive style which supports both genders (Afonshin et al., 2016).

However, the autocratic style is closely linked to an extremely patriarchal society. Coaches are not likely to give up their authoritarian approach as it is part of their identity as Iraqi men when status is afforded by hierarchical authoritarian norms. It is also necessary – and in fact an enabler – for women players to be involved in sport coaching. In this sense, it is a

different enactment of holistic coaching practice because the autocratic relationship between male coaches and female players is what enables family permission to play. Much broader level societal changes would be necessary before this practice architecture could or should change as everyone within this coaching environment wants the women to be able to play and potentially become coaches themselves.

Even with broadening coach awareness of the multitude of sport pedagogies in use overseas, to encourage the development of their intrapersonal knowledge and relational skills (Cote & Gilbert, 2009), there are many enduring practice architectures that will constrain coaching innovation. Pedagogic models evolved from teaching, like TGfU and Games Sense, disrupt the part-part-whole skill progression model of motor learning theory, or the privileging of procedural knowledge (Schempp, 1993), but the Figures in Chapter 5 and Chapter 7 show that the linear format of warm-up-fitness-technical skill practice - full game progression is still dominant (Doozen & Bae, 2016).

An opportunity to disrupt and reconfigure the sources of expert coach knowledge beyond former playing experience and apprenticeship assistant coaching could be found in strategic relationships between the clubs, the schools and the local university. Just being a teacher or lecturer alone is clearly not enough to change autocratic practices, as every coach was already one or the other. But the introduction of the foreign sports colleges-Iraqi schools partnerships, as indicated in the Iraq2030 plan (Ministry of Planning, 2019), and the existing connections with the university that could learn from these partnerships could serve as an important source of disruption. Iraqi and foreign staff involved in these partnerships could become the change agents, coupled with the media savvy youth players. An epistemic revolution in coaching practices driven by Iraq's young population could occur within coaching.

This study has shown that autocratic coaching approaches enable the men's and women's competition to survive in challenging circumstances. In this sense, autocratic coaching is an enabler of sport competition, rather than a constraint. However, autocratic coaching practices are not necessarily conducive to learning new approaches. Coaches who are shown to have greater efficacy have a significant impact on player performance (Jenny, 2017: Falcao, & Bloom, 2018: Noddings, 2003). These coaches placed greater emphasis upon being able to keep teams together under societal expectations about the roles of male coaches, male players and female players, which provided evidence of their efficacy under those circumstances.

8.2 Gender and Culture: Women's Participation in Sport and Sports Coaching

The analysis of Iraqi coaching philosophies, approaches and practices via the lens of practice architectures shows that elite women's teams receive a diminished form of coaching, as revealed in the characteristic sayings, doings and relatings (Kemmis and Grootenboer, 2008) of these teams. Due to cultural-discursive arrangements, the women players are receiving less actual coaching than the men. They experience greater periods of silence, lower proportion of direct management and longer periods of often unsupervised game play. The male players receive more direct management, instruction and feedback, and, quite simply, the male coaches speak to the male players more often than they do to the women. These coaching practices are more aligned with hegemonic masculinity for competitiveness and boosting the morale of male players but also maintaining respectful relationships with the families of players who watch their daughters and sisters train and play under close scrutiny. Amy and Daisy's replies revealed that cultural-discursive arrangements constrain women's communication with their coaches. They wished that they could ask more questions and be provided with more answers but they noted that their coaches did not encourage this through tense exchanges or via being ignored.

There is one significant PSPP finding that is not addressed further in the other two data sets and distinguishes this study from previous studies. The women do not place much weighting or value on body appearance, unlike other international studies such as Fox and Corbin's (1989) original study and many others conducted with collegiate athletes (Lindwall, 2004; Zason Chian & John Wang, 2008; Wang et al., 2010). The women in this study are happy to be able to learn new skills and play sport. They are not playing sport to show off their fit bodies as a source of identity support, unlike international counterparts (especially typical in beach volleyball). The findings of PSPP and interviews confirm that Iraqi female players have positive attitudes towards volleyball which did not appear to be undermined by concerns about their physical appearance. Nonetheless, uniforms worn by elite players would have to conform to the culture and society of Iraq which emphasizes Islamic values including modesty in appearance.

It appears that the women in this study have more social-political agency than women in other parts of Iraq and the Middle East. It is more culturally acceptable to play sport as a woman in northern Iraq, where Kurdish and Christian populations are found. There are (mostly) Muslim women in other areas of Iraq who do not still have the chance to play sport beyond schooling years. The women in this study really valued the opportunity to play – this was

evident in their PSPP findings and interviews. They took training seriously – evident in the video analysis. Investing in women’s sport would be extremely effective in meeting the intentions of the Iraq 2030 plan (Ministry of Planning, 2019). Being on the team enables social mobility for the women in ways that normal societal roles do not.

8.3 Implications for Player Development

The findings suggest that player learning is *not* limited to that which their coaches already know. Many players are engaging in self-directed learning on the internet but the coach-player inter-personal relationships (Cote & Gilbert, Cote, et al., 2010) and focus on procedural knowledge (Schempp, 1993) prevents players from sharing what they know in coaching sessions. Recall from Chapter 6 that players and one assistant coach already conducted their own research on YouTube, but kept it secret from their head coaches, for fear of being disrespectful. The internet has opened up the possibility of bringing new ideas and approaches into volleyball in Iraq, as it could in any country. As a source of knowledge for players, for assistant coaches and head coaches, coaching knowledge shared in this way could be leveraged to come out into the open as an important, low cost, far reaching form of coach education and player learning.

Additionally, just as video technology enabled this research to be conducted remotely, the athletes and coaches could use more opportunities to video and review their performance in-depth. It also offers the scope for critical gains by enhancement of performance from accelerated and different learning made possible by video review (Lees, Cabello and Torres, 2009). The technology can be embraced by watching after match video and statistical analysis of relevant session of practice (Hughes and Franks, 2004). Practice video footage can be viewed at any time – in much the same way as players were watching YouTube in secret. Feedback of coaches can be immediately communicated in ways that can support competition enhancement. As shown in the interview findings, technology itself is useful for creating new and different communities of practice. The communication with coaching staff and peers on particular perspectives of performance would also be useful for knowledge sharing and developing coach education practices.

Another avenue for player development, particularly for women players, is to recruit these young, university-educated students into coaching pathways. The Iraq2030 plan (Ministry for Planning, 2019), despite calling it “man building”, and recognises that education for young people is essential for nation (re) building. The multi-ethnic, multi-religious teams are already predisposed to putting social-political and cultural differences aside in the quest of

elite sport. The players and coaches are already driving social cohesion through sport, where university students and academics are at the forefront of sport development. The career pathway potentially continues for the male players in future coaching roles but it currently ends for women here as advanced players.

Tied to investing in women's coaching is the development of international women's competition. Having more experiences of international competition, and the expanded roles that come with it, is an important way to further develop players. One of the ways to achieve this is to consider expanded coaching opportunities and experiences through regional and national development initiatives.

The players and some of the coaches expressed their sensitivity to cultural issues affecting various cultural groups' ability to play. Knowing their teams, their families and socio-economic circumstances was also evident in coaches' interviews. Being committed to broadening participation of players from all cultural groups can be considered as part of the holistic coaching remit of a coach and one that deserves regional and administrative support. One of the ways to achieve this is to consider expanded coaching opportunities and experiences through regional and national development initiatives. These opportunities are discussed in the following sections.

8.4 Implications for Regional and National Development

This study was shaped by looking at the research problem within the defined scope of volleyball from afar in Australia. However, the findings transcended the site and the context of volleyball in northern Iraq to point to broader implications for nation building. Borrowing from the sociology of schooling from Western countries, schools are a microcosm of society, characterised by social values, social norms and inequalities of race, class and gender reflecting broader society. The same can be said about sports clubs and the coaching environment. In Chapter 2, the racial conflict and cultural divides between the north and the south of Iraq were introduced, along with defining features of Iraqi society such as patriarchy, religious and ethnic hierarchies and the social structures and practices underpinned by Islam.

The fact that women participated in volleyball at all in these clubs in northern Iraq was in stark contrast to prevailing norms where women had few rights. However, despite their presence and participation in volleyball, it was clear that women's experience of coaching was different to the men. There was little evidence that women had the opportunity to further participate in regular international competition, whereas men regularly played in the Asian confederate of the Fédération Internationale de Volleyball, (FIVB). More opportunities to

experience international competition would be a positive step in supporting women's volleyball. Additionally, there were no women coaches in this study and little evidence that coaching is a legitimate and permitted role for women presently in Iraq society. As discussed in Chapter 2, having women coaches as role models is something that has been put forward in sport development and gender in sport research which could be foregrounded in future development of the sport.

The Iraq 2030 plan suggests that partner-building is a key phase for sustainable development. Existing activities in Baghdad and Erbil have been highlighted for continued support and enhancement. Sport has not been explicitly mentioned in the Iraq2030 report, but youth development has. A set of national priorities around youth development, using the vehicle of volleyball, could advance these goals.

8.5 Implications for Volleyball Administration in Iraq

The role of the Iraq Volleyball Federation contributes to the administration of national tournaments where coach training and styles of coaching are most likely to be acquired by top coaches, and hence influence players' training (Mili, 2016). The interview findings indicated that the IVF requires more funding resources to encourage national and international tournaments, particularly for women. Symptomatic of the lack of funding for northern Iraq in general, the lack of vision and investment in the IVF has been observed by coaches and players and requires consideration to support the success of Volleyball in Iraq.

Few Iraqi sports coaches have formal training opportunities if they are not exposed to coaching development opportunities at international level. That is, only coaches who travel with national teams are likely to be exposed to newer coaching knowledge. However, there are some training pathways for those interested in coaching. An Iraqi coaching certificate is usually obtained after successfully completing a formal coach education program conducted by a club under experienced coaches. It can also be obtained as part of a university undergraduate program, embedded in sport pedagogy classes. Despite formal training being available, most academic and professional coach education programs are outdated partly as a result of Iraq's extended isolation from the international sporting community (Al-Wattar, Hussein, & Hussein, 2011). Once the basic coaching certification is obtained, there are few opportunities to obtain advanced coaching qualifications as there are no advanced certification courses for coaches in Iraq.

To support elite volleyball in Iraq, the IVF needs to consider what it would take to achieve International Olympic Committee (IOC) recognition. The IOC states that "while

conserving their independence and autonomy in the administration of their sports, International Sports Federations seeking IOC recognition must ensure that their statutes, practice and activities conform with the Olympic Charter” (IOC, 2020). Iraq has much to do to comply with the Olympic Charter and having parity with women’s teams and coaching staff will be one the larger hurdles to overcome. A starting point could be with the women in these two top teams. Young, university educated women, whose families are already supporting their involvement in the sport are best suited to targeted coach-identification programs and coach education opportunities.

Jameel Azeez, President of the IVF, recently met in May 2020 with the FIVB President via video conference to discuss development in the Western Asian region of AVC (<https://asianvolleyball.net/new/fivb-president-meets-with-western-asia-zone-via-videoconference/>). Development support for volleyball in Western Asian region of the AVC is based in Bahrain, which supports 22 countries in the Arabic region. They discussed matters as the FIVB’s commitment to digitalisation, and the coaching support that can be provided to countries as part of the Nucleus Project through the FIVB Projects Platform. A key priority for this centre, in addition to online coach education, would be to open up the sporting competition within Iraq and between its neighbours, to increase player and coach movement and experiences between the north and the south of Iraq. Their support should work towards fostering a true national, open federation instead of a secular one.

There are models for online communities of practice such as the Commonwealth Games Federation (CGF) women in coaching mentoring program, which launched at the 2018 Commonwealth Games. The CGF model mentors elite players and assistant coaches with lead coaching aspirations, as they are playing in and or attending international tournaments (Morgan, 2018) on natural opportunities to bring players and coaches together through competition currently works for male players, but not so for women in Iraq who have sporadic international playing opportunities. This kind of coaching leadership, which could be initiated by the coaches in this study, would provide the succession planning needed to sustain elite sport competition (Martens, 2012).

The FIVB also could learn from the International Council for Coaching Excellence (ICCE)’s framework for developing coaches (ICCE, 2014). Launched during the 2014 Commonwealth Games as a part of Global Coaches House, the framework “articulate(s) the key roles, competences and standards for coach developers” (p.1). Generating experiences that high performance coaches value is something within the remit of the IVF. Mallett, Rynne and

Billett (2016) found that high performance coaches highly valued on the job experience, reflection, access to consultants and the opportunity to observe others (p.95).

8.6 Implications for Sports Coaching Research in Iraq

As Palao et al. (2004) demonstrated, there is a culture of high-performance research associated with top international, such as Olympic, competition, to which Iraqi coaches are not privy. Existing research traditions prioritize technocratic and biomechanics research upon players, with a view to enhancing player performance. Research which would develop coaches' reflective capacities and intrapersonal knowledge (Cote & Gilbert, Cote, et al., 2010) is an area of need.

There is also a need for more research into the different influences of regional context upon coach learning. Whilst this research was limited to coaches within Iraq, it has potential for wider adaptation in and contribution to coach professional learning within the entire Middle East region. Coaches are presently required to self-educate about the tools to and benefits of creating technical and tactical learning environments for young athletes. Increasing opportunities for regional coach education and therefore coach effectiveness closely connected to coaching efficacy research can empower coaches even further as they have greater resources and power then for changing existing (poor) provisions of coach education, such as that experienced by these volleyball coaches in Iraq.

Another implication of this research project is that it provides a platform for other researchers for evaluating coaching practices across other developmental sports in the context of Iraq and the Middle East. There is a distinctive absence of research related around effective sports coaching in context of Iraq. As demonstrated in the literature review, most current research in Iraq is about player performance, not coach performance. Hence, this area required to be investigated further. More incentives and funds are required to stimulate research in this field of inquiry. Moreover, the concerns related to the obvious disparities between observed practices and coach behaviours and their perceptions of their practice requires further attention of researchers. This would be of interest to sports coaching scholars for whom interviews are an important data collection method.

There are a number of research priorities arising from this investigation which could enhance coach development in Iraq. First of all, research could focus upon developing effective player to coach transitions and pathways, particularly for elite women players. Research would need to unpack the practice arrangements that constrain the recruitment of women into coaching roles. The school setting may be the best place to commence such work, given the

dual employment of coaches as teachers. Secondly, research could focus on how to create sustainable and effective online communities of practice, as defined and described by Lave and Wenger (1991) and Goodyear and Casey (2015), including the effectiveness of mentor-mentee networks within Iraq and between countries with free travel. This could be developed around the idea of reading clubs and via developing cross sport networks within Iraq, to learn from the resourcing and infrastructure in place from better resourced sports like football. Such communities of practice could extend to professional exchanges, which in turn could generate recommendations for IFV, FIVB and Olympics Committee to examine how capacity is evolving for coaching in other countries, like Iraq, who face significant challenges in re-establishing elite competition.

The utility of the theory of practice architectures as a framework for analysis in international sport coaching contexts is also an area recommended for further research. The studies drawn upon in this thesis are situated in Australia (Kemmis, & Grootenboer, 2008; Whatman, 2016), England (Goodyear, & Casey, 2015; Goodyear, Casey, & Kirk, 2016; Phelan, & Griffiths, 2019) and New Zealand (Petrie, 2016; Petrie & Kernaghan, 2017). Application in Arabic countries like Iraq could make an important contribution to the development of this theory.

The mixed methods approach to this case study may also offer future researchers a useful design for this kind of investigation. Mixed methods enabled me to overcome distance and civil unrest but also, when combined together, enabled a richer and more compelling story of coaching practices in Iraq to be interpreted. The voices of the participants were privileged in the interviews, which were conducted over Viber – a free, internet-based communication tool that considered the socio-economic circumstances of the participants. But their narratives were enriched by the video-recorded observations and the self-reported PSPP questionnaires. Observation of coaching practice is a very common methodological approach but this study has made a strong case for choosing multiple and mixed methods.

8.7 Strengths of the Study

It is highly likely that this is the first English language investigation into elite level coaching practiced in Iraq. As established in previous chapter, sports research in Iraq focuses on player performance rather than coach performance, coach practice or coach learning. This study has made an important contribution to what sports coaching research in Iraq should be invested in. Publishing it in English also opens the findings up to a much larger sports coaching audience.

One significant strength of this study was that it systematically integrated three phases of data collection within the mixed methods sequential explanatory approach adopted. The unique combination of research methods acted to reduce design weaknesses that typically characterise studies adopting a single method of investigation (Lingard, Albert & Levinson, 2008).

The study began with the collection and analysis of quantitative data through the use of the PSPP for a relatively large number of male and female player-participants. This was followed by the video- and audio recording of four coaching sessions (one coaching session each for a male and female team at each participating club). Finally, based on the analysis of data in the first two phases, interview data was collected for coaching staff at both clubs ($n = 8$) and four players each from a male and female team at each club ($n = 16$). The collection of multiple data sets enabled the researcher to develop a much deeper and more sophisticated understanding of the research topic than the use of one single research method (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Moreover, the research design enabled some of the limitations associated with self-reported perceptions, gathered through interviews alone, to be overcome, as video- and audio-recording of actual coaching sessions enable the researcher to compare player and coach reported perceptions with actual observations of practice.

In addition, the decision to interview both coaching staff and players provided rich data around coaches' perceptions of their own practise which could then be compared with player's experiences of coaching programmes and practises. Also, as noted in Chapter 3, potential benefit may have accrued to all participants by providing them with the opportunity to reflect critically on coaching practise. Moreover, because the researcher was an insider known to the participants in this study interview questions and ad hoc discussions around coaching practise may have brought participants into contact with knowledge about practise which would normally have been outside of their experience. An extremely rich case of elite coaching in volleyball in Iraq has been established.

There were a number of methodological innovations associated with his study. First, the requirement that all data be collected in a second language, resulted in the PSPP now being available in an Arabic translation. Moreover, The PSPP in the case of this study was used in a novel way. Fox's (1990) Physical Self Perception Profile (PSPP) is typically used as an instrument in pre-post design evaluation studies. However, this research highlights that the PSPP can be repurposed and adapted as a single point in time measurement, to establish player preferences in coaching behaviour relating to their status as elite volleyball players. Finally, how the CAIS tool, developed by Cushion et al. (2012), was used in this study enabled useful

findings to be generated, which can be compared to other data sets in Western coaching contexts.

8.8 Limitations of the Study

Irrespective of the size, budget, robustness of design and fidelity with respect to data collection and analysis, research projects are limited to some degree. A number of limitations of this study should be acknowledged when considering its findings. First, the study's location was northern Iraq and therefore the findings are specific to the social, cultural and economic conditions extant in that region. It is possible, were the study replicated in another Arabic country or in a different region within Iraq, the findings may have varied considerably.

A strict hierarchy of authority exists in Iraq that mediates the behaviours of individuals and their ability to express various viewpoints in the coaching context, and, for a range of complex cultural reasons, this situation particularly affected women players. In the volleyball context analysed here, the hierarchy of authority clearly ran from the Head Coach to Assistant Coach and lastly to the players themselves. While participants freely gave their consent to take part in the study and to be interviewed, it is possible that assistant coaches and female players in particular may have tempered their responses against possible repercussions—either real or imagined—if their responses were personally identified. Indeed, there is some evidence within the interview transcripts that this was the case for some women players. Accordingly, this issue may bring into question the validity of interpretations of some of the interview data.

There are limitations with respect to the method of sampling and sample size of participants who took part in this study. First, the sample of participants from two volleyball clubs was an opportunistic and convenience sample, accessible because of professional relationships between the researcher and coaching staff and players at those clubs. The participating clubs represented two of the six clubs established in northern Iraq still participating at an advanced level of competition. In addition, there are an additional six clubs at that level located around Baghdad in southern Iraq. Accordingly, the participant pool was drawn from one men's and one women's team each from two clubs out of a possible 12 clubs competing in elite (advanced) level volleyball in Iraq. Clubs in the Baghdad region were not accessible to the researcher due to political reasons however, different findings may have resulted from the inclusion of a larger and more diverse of selection clubs and participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Creswell & Poth, 2016; Luborsky & Rubinstein, 1995).

The CAIS tool developed by Cushion et al. (2012), was usually used to capture real time evaluation of coach behaviours over several sessions or over an entire season. In this

study, due to geopolitical constraints, it was only used for one coaching session for each team as a single, point in time appraisal of video- and audio-recorded coaching practices. If the circumstances had allowed, videoing several sessions over a season may have enabled different emphases on dominant coaching practices to be revealed. For example, at the end of the season, the high proportion of time spent on fitness may have decreased compared to game practice.

Finally, researching the issue of participating in sport and coaching in Iraq, as this study has demonstrated, is complex in a religiously, ethnically and politically divided country which has recently begun to emerge from a protracted period of armed conflict (Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, 2019). Moreover, this social context is constantly evolving and in Iraq with social and economic conditions being the subject of change with Iraq's intended commitment to the UN's sustainable development goals (Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, 2019). This study was a point-in-time research undertaking, and it could be expected that the social and cultural conditions that provided the context of this study will evolve over time. A longitudinal study might capture how social and cultural changes in Iraq might impact coaching practices in volleyball and other sports over time.

8.9 Concluding Remarks

This study began with a focus on what appeared on one level as a technical problem - understanding coach and player perceptions of what constitutes effective coaching - with a view to improving coaching practices at the elite level in Iraq. The findings of this study point to a tradition of coaching in Iraq that privileges coaching knowledge derived from the coaches' experience as former players and where former players become the next generation of coaches. This tradition in sports coaching appears to reproduce practice across generations of players and coaches. This dynamic has further led to the privileging of sports science knowledge (e.g., Biomechanics and Physiology), meaning that some of its equally important disciplines (such as motor learning, pedagogy and sport psychology) play a limited role in sports coaching programming, coaching practices and coach education in Iraq. This resistance has been captured by Cushion et al. (2019) who have argued that "coaches tend to valorise practitioner knowledge and its associated sources of informal learning making the delivery of transformative coach education something of a challenge" (p. 533). They go on to conclude that changing coaching practice is problematic partly because coach educators themselves "operate in an inherently conservative and sometimes anti-intellectual learning culture ... where informal learning experiences contribute more to the development of coaching knowledge and practice than formal education." (p. 533).

It would be tempting to suggest that the problem of improving sports coaching in Iraq relates to coaches' exposure to technical coaching knowledge. As established in the thesis, this knowledge has been unavailable due to circumstances such as war and consequent isolation of Iraq from the international community, where knowledge exchanges routinely occur through internationally networked communities of practice. This context has, no doubt, played some part in constraining coach professional learning in Iraq. However, to suggest that limited access to knowledge and training is the key constraint to coach development would be to overlook more fundamental issues concerning the social construction of coaches' identity and the social context of learning in volleyball.

This study drew on the work of Côté and Gilbert (2009) who argued intrapersonal knowledge gained through critical reflection and self-awareness was an important form of knowledge for coaching and critical for developing an individual's disposition towards continuous improvement. Critical self-reflection is not a naturally occurring human psychological trait, but rather a mode of self-identity construction that is culturally and historically specific. In many western countries, for example, critical reflection has been valued as an aspect of selfhood for people engaged in the professions and is a key aspect underpinning attitudes and behaviours associated with lifelong learning (Darbyshire and Fleming, 2008). However, it has been argued throughout this thesis that Iraqi culture is characterised by strict social norms and social hierarchies based on long-standing cultural traditions and fundamentalist Islamic belief systems. In such societies, social roles are prescribed for individuals together with norms governing behaviour. Data gathered from the coaching settings showed that the hierarchy of authority was clearly demarcated beginning with the coach — the 'sage on the stage' — who retained absolute authority for all significant decisions relating to the program and the conduct of training sessions, followed by the assistant coach (the apprentice in waiting), the team captains, and finally, the players themselves. This context explains why the behaviours and reported viewpoints of all coaches across all the four volleyball teams were consistent with an autocratic coaching philosophy with little variation across individual coaches. This strictly observed hierarchy of authority is not an environment conducive to the emergence of 'pluralistic and creative spaces' for critical self-reflection and creative self-formation. Moreover, the data suggests that the autocratic coaching behaviours were an important aspect of these coaches' professional identities and social standing amongst the players and their families.

Two major implications flow from this observation. The first is that coaches themselves may have little incentive to develop intrapersonal knowledge for coaching and to open up a

space for critical reflection on their own coaching practices. In the absence of social incentives that encourage or value self-criticism, it is unlikely that exposure to sports science knowledge such as sport psychology or alternative tactically based sport pedagogies will be valued as a resource by coaches for improving their coaching practice. The second is that, even given exposure to tactics-based sport pedagogies, these approaches are unlikely to be acceptable to or gain traction with the current generation of coaches. The data analysis suggested that the social standing and professional identities of these coaches derived from their status as authority figures and possessors of specialised coaching knowledge from their own personal experience as players. Tactics-based sport pedagogies (e.g., TGFU and Games Sense) require more democratic approaches to coaching practices that encourage players to ask questions, offer solutions, problem-solve and make autonomous decisions (Butler & Griffin, 2010). Such approaches may be regarded by these coaches as a challenge to their ultimate decision-making authority in the coaching setting with the potential to undermine their social standing and professional identity and has also been demonstrated to be largely absent from their traditional sources of coach learning.

While social norms in Iraq appear to favour the reproduction of current coaching behaviour, this is not to conclude that this study has not identified potential focal points for the disruption of current practices and reconfiguration of practice architectures. This study has revealed that social changes including the widespread use of social media (e.g., YouTube) is exposing young players to alternative approaches to skill learning and the importance of game play for tactical understanding and development. Findings from this study suggested that exposure to social media for some players and assistant coaches was prompting them to question current coaching approaches. Social media platforms are adopted by diverse stakeholder groups, for instance, sports events, teams, managers, athletes and coaches. For women volleyball players, social media provides the effective avenue for sharing professional and personal news and developing in-depth interaction with sport coaches. Coaches can create different groups on Facebook for player management and learning in formal and informal contexts. It is also useful for managing communication among players and coach.

Another potential source for change may be in the appointment of more women to coaching roles. Because the behavioural expectations of women in Iraq are not prescribed by hegemonic, patriarchal social relations, women coaches may be more open to adopting more democratic coaching philosophies and coaching styles. A potential model for this change in Iraq is the recent training camp attended by Iranian women for coach training in Tehran, as discussed earlier. Finally, Iraq's current plan for modernisation and nation building and its

adoption of the UN's sustainable development goals, may provide opportunities for Iraq's integration into the global sporting community. Moreover, as noted above, this initiative may provide opportunities for regional development including through sport and a recognition for trained coaches who may support this initiative.

A young population pyramid is Iraq's strongest asset and real wealth which can face all forms of future challenges. This goal covers people's lives, roles, and social functions and expresses the values of freedom, justice, fairness and future aspirations. (Iraq Ministry of planning, 2019, p. 13).

Iraq is a country currently emerging from a long history of armed conflict and is a country characterised by marked gender inequality and religious and ethnic divisions. The Sustainable Development Framework in Iraq provides (Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, 2019) provides a vision for a safer and more prosperous future for young people in Iraq including its commitment to a version of citizenship grounded in the values of solidarity, tolerance, justice, and freedom. Sport, like any other social activity reflects the broader social values and sport and sports coaching may evolve alongside these broader social transformations. However, sport may also act as a potential tool for engaging young people in Iraq's social transformation agenda. Recognition that regional and national development might be supported by community organisations and partnerships around sport may be a driver for the development of more engaging approaches to coaching with the view to attracting more young people to organised sport and realising its significant personal and social and cultural benefits.

The suggestions and implications of this research will be useful for raising the consciousness of players of Iraq about the rights of Iraqi women for experiencing a full contribution in society. Giving support and right to Iraqi female players for participation in sport is the sign of improved equity in context of Iraq. The implication of such changes intends for better society in Iraq where male and female players can share more equitable format of social participation specifically for Iraqi female volleyball players.

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10 APPENDICES

Appendix 1: The Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP)

Appendix 2: Interview questions for coaches

Appendix 3: Interview questions for players

Appendix 4: Full ethical consent

Appendix 5: Coach and player consent forms

Appendix 6: Participant information sheet

Appendix 7: Coach assessment and information system, primary behaviour checklist

Appendix 1: THE PHYSICAL SELF PERCEPTION PROFILE (PSPP)

These are statements, which allow people to describe themselves. There are no right or wrong answers since people differ a lot.

First, decide which one of the two statements (on the left or on the right) BEST describes you. Then, go to that side of the statement and check if it is just "sort of true" or "really true" FOR YOU.

Really True For me	Sort of True for me		Example		Sort of true for me	Really true for me
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are very competitive	BUT	Other are not quite so competitive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

REMEMBER to check only ONE of the four boxes.

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are not very good when it comes to playing sports.	BUT	Others feel that they are really good at just about every sport.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are not very confident about their level of physical conditioning and fitness.	BUT	Others always feel confident that they maintain excellent conditioning and fitness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that compared to most, they have an attractive body	BUT	Others feel that compared to most, their body is not quite so attractive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are physically stronger than most people of their sex	BUT	Others feel that they lack physical strength compared to most others of their sex	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel extremely proud of who they are and what they can do physically	BUT	Others are sometimes not quite so proud of who they are physically	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are among the best when it comes to athletic ability	BUT	Others feel that they are not among the most able when it comes to athletics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people make certain they take part in some form of regular vigorous physical exercise	BUT	Others don't often manage to keep up regular vigorous physical exercise	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they have difficulty maintaining an attractive body	BUT	Others feel that they are easily able to keep their bodies looking attractive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Chapter 10: Appendices

	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that their muscles are much stronger than most others of their sex	BUT	Others feel that on the whole their muscles are not quite so strong as most others of their sex	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are sometimes not so happy with the way they are or what they can do physically	BUT	Others always feel happy about the kind of person they are physically	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are not quite so confident when it comes to taking part in sports activities	BUT	Others are among the most confident when it comes to taking part in sports activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people do not usually have a high level of stamina and fitness	BUT	Others always maintain a high level of stamina and fitness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel embarrassed by their bodies when it comes to wearing few clothes	BUT	Others do not feel embarrassed by their bodies when it comes to wearing few clothes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	When it comes to situations requiring strength some people are one of the first to step forward	BUT	When it comes to situations requiring strength some people are one of the last to step forward	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	When it comes to the physical side of themselves some people do not feel very confident	BUT	Others seem to have a real sense of confidence in the physical side of themselves	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are always one of the best when it comes to joining in sports activities	BUT	Others feel that they are not one of the best when it comes to joining in sports activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people tend to feel a little uneasy in fitness and exercise settings	BUT	Others feel confident and at ease at all times in fitness and exercise settings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are often admired because their physique or figure is considered attractive	BUT	Others rarely feel that they receive admiration for the way their body looks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people tend to lack confidence when it comes to their strength	BUT	Others are extremely confident when it comes to their physical strength	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people always have a real positive feeling about the physical side of themselves	BUT	Others sometimes do not feel positive about the physical side of themselves	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are sometimes a little slower than most when it comes to learning new skills in a sports situation	BUT	Others have always seemed to be among the quickest when it comes to learning new sports skills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel extremely confident about their ability to maintain regular exercise and physical condition	BUT	Others don't feel quite so confident about their ability to maintain regular exercise and physical condition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that compared to most, their bodies do not look in the best of shape	BUT	Others feel that compared to most their bodies always look in excellent physical shape	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are very strong and have well developed muscles compared to most people	BUT	Others felt that they are not so strong, and their muscles are not very well developed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people wish that they could have more respect for their physical selves	BUT	Others always have great respect for their physical selves	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Given the chance, some people are always one of the first to join in sports activities	BUT	Other people sometimes hold back and are not usually among the first to join in sports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that compared to most they always maintain a high level of physical conditioning	BUT	Others feel that compared to most their level of physical conditioning is not usually so high	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people are extremely confident about the appearance of their body	BUT	Others are a little self-conscious about the appearance of their bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that they are not as good as most at dealing with situations requiring physical strength	BUT	Others feel that they are among the best at dealing with situations which require physical strength	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel extremely satisfied with the kind of person they are physically	BUT	Others sometimes feel a little dissatisfied with their physical selves	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How Important Are Things To You?

	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that being good at sports is vitally important to them.	BUT	Other feel that being good at sports is not so important to them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people do not feel that maintaining a high level of physical conditioning is very important to them.	BUT	Others feel than maintaining a high level of physical conditioning is extremely important to them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people believe that having an attractive physique or figure is validity important to them.	BUT	Others believe that having an attractive physique or figure is not important in their live.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people believe that being physical strong is not so important to them.	BUT	Another feel that it is extremely important to them to be physically strong.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that having very good sports ability and skills is not so important to them.	BUT	Others feel that having a high level of sports ability is really important to them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	some people feel that maintaining regular vigorous exercise is vitally important to them	BUT	Others feel that keeping up regular vigorous is not of prime important to them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people do not feel it so important to them to send a lot of time and effort maintaining an attractive body.	BUT	Others think that it is vitally important to spend time and effort maintaining an attractive body.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Some people feel that being strong and having well developed / toned muscles is virally important to them.	BUT	Others feel that being strong and having well developed/ toned muscles is not so important to them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix 2: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR COACHES

The set of 12 questions will be used as guide in the interviews with the coaches

1. What do you do to be a more effective coach?
2. How do you plan for session training goals and objectives?
3. How do you think the majority of your team met these goals and how do you collect evidence around this?
4. What did you do to help them meet their goals?
5. What coaching characteristics do you think helped your players learn?
6. Why do you think it's important to have team talks?
7. How can you improve your players' skills by game play in coaching sessions?
8. How can you modify players' position during game play in coaching sessions?
9. How can you modify players' tactical awareness during game play in coaching sessions?
10. When do you and the team discuss the tactical decisions of the players through the game play in coaching sessions?
11. What are the ways in which you prefer to develop your players' fitness or technique, for example, independently, or combined approach?
12. How is it possible to use game play in training to develop players' skills?

Appendix 3: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR PLAYERS

The set of 13 questions will be used to elicit responses from the coaches and assistant coaches.

1. What is your favourite part about coaching sessions?
2. How do you think your coach's strategies during coaching sessions improve your understanding of the game?
3. What do you think your coach does which makes him more effective?
4. What are your favourite characteristics about your coach?
5. Do you trust your coach in his coaching talents? If so, explain.
6. Why do you think your team is successful?
7. How do your coaches help you become a successful player?
8. What else could they do to help you become a better player?
9. How does your coach build team cohesion?
10. Do you think your team has cohesion? If so, what do you think made this possible?
11. How does your coach encourage you to be reflective?
12. What do you think your coach does to improve as a coach?
13. How does your coach use your feedback to improve in his coaching?

Appendix 4: FULL ETHICAL CONSENT

RIMS Griffith
Tue 6/27/2017 9:27 AM
To: anmar.abraham@griffith.edu.au; Stephen Hay; Sue Whatman
Cc: research-ethics@griffith.edu.au; Rick Williams

GRIFFITH UNIVERSITY HUMAN RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Dear Dr Susan Whatman

I write in relation to your application for ethical clearance for your project "A case study of coaches' and players' perceptions of the most effective way to coach volleyball with elite players in Iraq" (GU Ref No: 2017/243). The research ethics reviewers resolved to grant your application a clearance status of "Fully Approved".

This is to confirm receipt of the remaining required information, assurances or amendments to this protocol.

Consequently, I reconfirm my earlier advice that you are authorised to immediately commence this research on this basis.

The standard conditions of approval attached to our previous correspondence about this protocol continue to apply.

Regards

Mr Rick Williams
Manager Research Ethics and Integrity
Office for Research

Appendix 5: COACH AND PLAYER CONSENT FORMS

PLAYER CONSENT FORM

A case study of coaches' and players' perceptions of the most effective way to coach volleyball with elite players in Iraq

Research Team Dr. Susan Whatman
School of Education and Professional Studies
Griffith University
Contact Phone +61 7 5552 9240
Contact Email s.whatman@griffith.edu.au

Dr Stephen Hay
School of Education and Professional Studies
Griffith University
Contact Phone +61 7 37355650
Contact Email s.hay@griffith.edu.au

Anmar Abraham
Contact Email anmar.abraham@griffithuni.edu.au

By signing below, I confirm that I have read and understood the information package and in particular have noted that:

- I understand that my involvement in this research will include completion of a questionnaire which will remain confidential between myself and the research team;
- I understand that my involvement in this research will include giving consent to be filmed during one volleyball training session.
- I understand that my involvement in this research will include participation in an interview of approximately 30 minute duration concerning my viewpoints and reflections on volleyball coaching;
- I have had any questions answered to my satisfaction;
- I understand the risks involved;
- I understand that there will be no direct benefit to me from my participation in this research;
- I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary;

Chapter 10: Appendices

- I understand that if I have any additional questions I can contact the research team;
- I understand that I am free to withdraw at any time, without comment or penalty;
- I understand that I will be able to access the written summary of the results of the research; (The report will be emailed to the participants at the conclusion of the study);
- I understand that I can contact the Manager, Research Ethics, at Griffith University Human Research Ethics Committee on +61 7 3735 4375 (or research-ethics@griffith.edu.au) if I have any concerns about the ethical conduct of the project;

I agree

- to participate in the project,
- to complete the questionnaire;
- to be filmed during a training session, and;
- to participate in an audio-recorded interview via Skype/Viber.

Name	
Signature	
Date	
Club	

COACH CONSENT FORM

A case study of coaches' and players' perceptions of the most effective way to coach volleyball with elite players in Iraq

Research Team Dr. Susan Whatman
School of Education and Professional Studies
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Contact Phone +61 7 5552 9240
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Dr Stephen Hay
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Contact Phone +61 7 37355650
Contact Email s.hay@griffith.edu.au

Anmar Abraham
Contact Email anmar.abraham@griffithuni.edu.au

By signing below, I confirm that I have read and understood the information package and in particular have noted that:

- I understand that my involvement in this research will include giving consent to be filmed during one volleyball training session.
- I understand that my involvement in this research will include participation in an interview of approximately 30 minute duration concerning my viewpoints and reflections on volleyball coaching;
- I have had any questions answered to my satisfaction;
- I understand the risks involved;
- I understand that there will be no direct benefit to me from my participation in this research;
- I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary;
- I understand that if I have any additional questions I can contact the research team;
- I understand that I am free to withdraw at any time, without comment or penalty;

- I understand that I will be able to access the written summary of the results of the research; (The report will be emailed to the participants at the conclusion of the study);
- I understand that I can contact the Manager, Research Ethics, at Griffith University Human Research Ethics Committee on +61 7 3735 4375 (or research-ethics@griffith.edu.au) if I have any concerns about the ethical conduct of the project;

I agree

- to participate in the project,
- to complete the questionnaire;
- to be filmed during a training session, and;
- to participate in an audio-recorded interview via Skype/Viber.

Name	
Signature	
Date	
Club	

Appendix 6: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Project Title: A case study of coaches' and players' perceptions of the most effective way to coach volleyball with elite players in Iraq

Research Team

SUPERVISOR	SUPERVISOR	PhD Researcher
Dr. Susan Whatman School of Education and Professional Studies Griffith University Contact Phone: +61 7 5552 9240 Contact Email: s.whatman@griffith.edu.au	Dr Stephen Hay School of Education and Professional Studies Griffith University Contact Phone: +61 7 37355650 Contact Email: s.hay@griffith.edu.au	Anmar Abraham School of Education and Professional Studies Griffith University Contact Phone: +61 402 564 259 Contact Email: anmar.abraham@griffithuni.edu.au

Why is the research being conducted?

The aim of this study is to explore coaches' and players' perceptions of the most effective way to coach volleyball with elite players in Iraq. The result from this investigation will add to the Iraqi coaching literature a new study about the coaches and more information of existing knowledge on coach effectiveness. Additionally, it will advance the profession's understanding about gender differences in perceptions of and preferences for coaching, as this is absent from the existing research in Iraq. It shall help the coaches to understand the differences that are present in terms of their training techniques and those that are used abroad. In the similar manner, it can provide in-depth information related to national coaching competitiveness through improved coaching knowledge in skills and fitness. With the help of this study, players can also realize that it is equally important for them to understand the coaches and coaching approaches that are integrated by their coaches. Additionally, coaches may understand the importance of TGFU and may implement it to

realize better results. This research is conducted as a doctoral dissertation in fulfilment of the requirements of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) at Griffith University.

What you will be asked to do?

As a volleyball professional, we invite you to participate in this study into volleyball coaching and coach effectiveness in Iraqi context. You will be asked to:

- 1) Players will be asked to complete a questionnaire, which should take approximately 25 minutes.
- 2) Participate in a volleyball training session which will be filmed by a member of the club on behalf of the research team. Attending the training session on this agreed date means giving consent to be filmed and for that material to be included in data collection.
- 3) Participate in an audio-recorded interview of approximately 30 mins in length via distance over Skype or Viber. A member of the research team (Anmar Abraham) will seek your viewpoints and reflections on different issues of coaching. Interviews will be audio-recorded and fully transcribed, and a copy will be provided to you upon request. Transcripts will be analysed thematically, and techniques to enhance trustworthiness and credibility of data (e.g. checking meaning with you and with other members of the research team) will be employed.

Please note you will not be paid or remunerated in other ways for your participation in this research

Risks to you

The risks involved in participating in this research are minimal.

Your confidentiality

Pseudonyms will be used in the reporting of the results of this research. Electronic data files of recordings will be password encrypted and stored in a confidential electronic drive that one of the named researchers will have access to. Audio data from interviews will be securely retained until transcription and data analysis is complete and for a designated period up to and including examination of the PhD thesis (which may be a further 3 years) in accordance with ethical guidelines. After this designated storage period has elapsed, all audio recordings will be permanently destroyed. The recordings will be used for the sole purpose of data analysis and will not be utilised for any other purposes, including conference presentations, or for instructional purposes.

Your participation is voluntary

Participation in this research project is entirely voluntary. If you do not wish to take part, you do not have to. Your decision whether to take part or not, or to take part and then withdraw, will have no bearing on your relationship with Griffith University, the coaching programs in Iraq, or the members of the research team whatsoever. Should you choose to withdraw after giving consent at any stage, any questionnaire and interview data collected from your participation will be deleted and your participation in filming will not form part of the data analysis.

Questions / further information

If you require any further information about this research project, or if you have any questions or concerns about participation, please contact the research team.

Ethical conduct of this research

This research has been approved by the Human Research Ethics Committees of Griffith University (HREC-GU- 2017/243) and will be carried out in accordance with the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research*. This statement has been developed to protect the interests of people who agree to participate in human research studies.

If you have any concerns or complaints about the ethical conduct of the research project, please contact the Manager, Research Ethics on +61 7 3735 4375 or research-ethics@griffith.edu.au.

Feedback to you

The report of this research will be emailed to participants at the conclusion of the study.

Privacy statement

The conduct of this research involves the collection, access and/or use of your de-identified personal information. The information collected is confidential and will not be disclosed to third parties without your consent, except to meet government, legal or other regulatory authority requirements. A de-identified copy of this data may be used for other research purposes. However, your anonymity will at all times be safeguarded. For further information consult the University's Privacy Plan at <http://www.griffith.edu.au/about-griffith/plans-publications/griffith-university-privacy-plan> or telephone +61 7 3735 4375

Appendix 7: COACH ASSESSMENT AND INFORMATION SYSTEM (CAIS) PRIMARY BEHAVIOUR CHECKLIST (Adapted from Cushion, Harvey, Muir, & Nelson, 2012)

Behaviour and Category	Example in volleyball coaching behaviour
Physical Behaviours	
1. Positive modelling	Demonstrating how to perform a spike correctly
2. Negative modelling	Demonstrating how the coach does NOT want the skill to be performed.
3. Physical assistance	Positioning the players' hands or body correctly to perform the skill
Feedback	
4. Specific feedback - positive	Commenting on correct hand position e.g., "I like how your palms are facing in the block"
5. Specific feedback – negative	Commenting on poor footwork – "you were standing flat footed – move your feet next time".
6. General feedback – positive	General positive praise such as "good work"
7. General feedback - negative	Negative general comment such as "not good"
8. Corrective feedback	Something which would improve the quality of the skill next time it is performed. e.g., to improve serving accuracy – look at a spot on the wall – serve at the wall a few times, then come back to the net.
Instruction	

9. Instruction	Pick the ball up and start from the serving line
Verbal/ Non-verbal	
10. Humour	Laughing at a spontaneous result
11. Hustle	"Come one, faster"
12. Praise	"you're doing well today"
13. Punishment	Physical punishment such as "do 10 push ups"
14. Scold	"I expect better from you"
15. Uncodable	Doesn't fit the above categories
Silence	
16. Silence	No comments made
Questioning	
17. Question	Coach asks a question to the players
18. Response to a question	Coach responds to a question from the players or onlookers
Management	
19. Management - direct	Controlling the session via modelling behaviours, playing, being involved in everything happening on the court at the time.
20. Management - indirect	Controlling the session such as the timing of the segments, previous setting up of the court with equipment.
21. Management - criticism	Of the organisation of the session - e.g., of the assistant coach, of the way the court is set out, of the way players engage with the organisation of the sessions.
Others	
22. Confer with assistant	Discussing coaching matters with the assistant coach

